

REBOOT
EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

Last Gender Action Plan

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

Grant Agreement: 101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01

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Reviewers: ALL PARTNERS: UNIVIE; ULIEGE; ELIAMEP; UCM; KHAS; EUR; UC3M; UGENT; SSSA; UCA; JYU; UW

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THE REBOOT PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses, and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, firstly, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of measuring, analysing and evaluating the impact of policies and strategic pathways. Secondly, the project aspires to actively prepare for future audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only "what is" but also "what has been" and "what will be" from fresh perspectives.

REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action to optimise the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the European Union (EU) in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VoD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

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1. GENDER IN RESEARCH

By implementing measures for gender equality, research institutions and projects like REBOOT contribute to overcoming barriers and promote gender equality, leading to a more diverse scientific community. Research becomes more profound by taking into account the distinct experiential viewpoints as well as subjectivities of women and men, deriving from gender diversity. This form of inclusivity is crucial for fostering creativity, improving the overall quality of research, and preventing any biases or limitations that may arise from any singular perspective.

Moreover, equal participation and recognition of contributions are policy objectives for all partner institutions, which have implemented measures to enhance women's participation. Every institution in this project's consortium provides their Gender Equality Plans via the European Commission portal.

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country
1	COO	UNIVIE	UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	AT
2	BEN	ULIEGE	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	BE
3	BEN	ELIAMEP	Elliniko Idryma Evropaikis kai Exoterikis Politikis (HELLENIC FOUNDATION FOR EUROPEAN AND FOREIGN POLICY)	EL
4	BEN	UCM	UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID	ES
5	BEN	KHAS	KADIR HAS UNIVERSITESI	TR
6	BEN	EUR	ERASMUS UNIVERSITEIT ROTTERDAM	NL
7	BEN	UGENT	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	BE
8	BEN	UC3M	UNIVERSIDAD CARLOS III DE MADRID	ES

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9	BEN	SSSA	SCUOLA SUPERIORE DI STUDI UNIVERSITARI E DI PERFEZIONAMENTO S ANNA	IT
10	BEN	UCA	UNIVERSITE COTE D'AZUR	FR
11	BEN	JYU	JYVASKYLAN YLIOPISTO	FI
12	BEN	UW	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	PL

Table 1: List of partners

2. PRELIMINARY GENDER RESEARCH FINDINGS IN REBOOT

Within WP3, REBOOT developed a comprehensive public database mapping EU and national legal and policy frameworks relevant to the European Film Industry. While gender equality is not treated as a standalone analytical category, the mapping highlights the limited and fragmented integration of gender considerations within existing film governance structures. This finding provides valuable baseline evidence underlining the need for stronger gender mainstreaming in audiovisual policies. The methodology and open design of the database offer clear potential for future integration of gender-sensitive indicators and gender-disaggregated data, reinforcing REBOOT's commitment to inclusive and equitable cultural industries.

3. GENDER DIMENSIONS IN REBOOT

In accordance with 'Article 14 – Values – Gender mainstreaming of the Grant Agreement', Project REBOOT aligns with the requirement for each beneficiary to act in accordance with the Gender Equality Plan of their organisation (examples provided in the Annex). REBOOT aims, to the extent possible, for gender balance in every form and level, and promotes equal personnel assignment of all genders. When it comes to performing tasks within the research phase, it is important to note that REBOOT takes all necessary steps to ensure that it provides equal opportunities to all genders to participate, act, and take the lead. The following sections describe the structures of the REBOOT consortium and its gender action plan. This is characterised by gender awareness and sensitivity from the design of the project and extends to its implementation and management processes. REBOOT supports staff in achieving a sustainable work-life balance in accordance with each institution's policies. To further elaborate, REBOOT's approach aligns with EU values and norms

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which aim to enhance equality, inclusivity, and diversity. This Gender Action Plan will be implemented with reference to EU policies:

The Gender strategy of REBOOT aligns with the European Union's regulations such as the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (especially Articles 21, 22, 23, 24, and 26), the Treaty of the European Union (Articles 2, 2(3)), EU Directives, and the Charter for the Research Code of Conduct. Collectively, these instruments support REBOOT's commitment to gender equality, and a strategic approach is taken to address gender-related issues within the project's lifetime. These references substantiate the implementation strategies, including equal recruitment opportunities, support for researchers during pregnancy, facilitation of maternity leave, and other relevant measures.

3.1. Project internal gender mainstreaming

Work Package 1 focuses on gender within the project management and project monitoring processes:

WP1 addresses consortium administrative and ethical management, which includes reporting, intellectual property and ethics issues management, financial and risk management, personal data and **gender management**, coordination, and liaising with the Advisory Board. The objectives of WP1 are to:

- a) efficiently manage (technical) and coordinate (core content) the REBOOT project, ensuring that all objectives are successfully achieved on time and in quality. This involves monitoring, controlling and overseeing achievements in terms of quality, impact, costs, time and effort according to the Grant Agreement (GA); identifying critical situations, suggesting and taking remedies;
- b) provide overall project administration support to the partners, comprising of all issues regarding the mandatory fulfilment of the GA, its annexes and the Consortium Agreement (CA);
- c) communicate with the European Commission on behalf of the consortium, prepare and submit all reports related to the project and facilitate communication among the consortium partners;
- d) facilitate and organise project meetings; liaise with partners;
- e) identify, manage and mitigate risks affecting the project implementation; and
- f) identify and address research ethics and gender issues throughout the project lifetime.**

In particular, Task 1.4 emphasises the gender dimension:

Task 1.4 Responsibility towards subjects: Personal data, ethics and **gender**

Leading partner: UNIVIE with support of all Participating partners

T1.4 consists of the following areas of project responsibility:

- a) managing privacy and personal data according to the GDPR and ensuring compliance with ethics requirements;
- b) managing the implementation and further development of the project's open science standards; and
- c) guaranteeing the project's full commitment to gender equity;**
- d) overall Ethics compliance.

The task involves: designing the project data management policy, with a focus on data collection, processing and security; formulating the project open science policy, with a focus on project publications and research data; designing and implementing measures to ensure compliance **with gender equality both in terms of project organisation and management and gender equality as a research dimension.**

Gender equity is concerned not only with quantitative aspects and therefore the number of participants and researchers throughout the life of the project but also with the gender-related aspects within research itself, its outcomes, and policy implications, as well as with the ways in which gender is recognised and mainstreamed in processes of deliberation, decision-making, and credit given throughout the life of the project. Gender denotes, on the one hand, women's roles and thereby gender-specific dimensions of work, research, representation, and recognition, paying attention to the historically persistent inequities between women and men. Moreover, the term 'gender' includes non-binary identities as well as diversity in gender expression, identification, and ways of life, socially expressed through the LGBTQI+ self-determination communities. The consortium is committed to equal representation of female and male researchers, and this extends to the research subjects. In addition, the consortium commits to gender inclusivity and diversity. When necessary, a proactive approach is taken to maintain gender balance in the research dissemination activities and in the policy outputs.

3.2. REBOOT gender dimensions in research

REBOOT's conceptualisation and methodology reflect strong gender equity concerns; this is evident in the decision to 'mainstream' gender parameters from design to dissemination. That is, gender

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issues are considered throughout all stages of research, from the design of the methodology and the analysis of historical dimensions, for example, in interviews, to focus groups and the design of indicators, as well as the conceptual and contextual elements shaping the project's work (i.e., data analysis also takes into consideration the gender of creators and of their audiences; gender data on the film industry; analytical tools used such as discourse analysis and qualitative data analysis). Furthermore, data collection combines with a strong concern for gender representativeness, with actions including interviews and surveys among gender experts. This is accompanied by an intersectional approach, which pays attention to the overlap of gender with other social, cultural, economic, and demographic markers and dimensions in the responses of consulted stakeholders. By integrating gender measurement in the project's data management, REBOOT aims to deliver detailed insights related to gender inequities in the creative sector and hence contribute to overcoming what UNESCO's report on the implementation of the 2005 Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions describes as "a multifaceted gender gap" characterised by the fact that, namely, women are 'severely under-represented in key creative roles'¹.

Specifically, mapping and analysing different categories of cinema professionals entails a gender-sensitive study, with the objective being to understand the perceptions of these professional categories towards the competitiveness of the EFI. Moreover, throughout the study and deliverables, REBOOT maintains gender neutral/aware language and sensitivity.

The consortium is designed to accommodate the beneficiaries' gender equity plans and is based on balanced gender diversity, with all institutions having gender equity policies in place. The project implementation relies on balanced gender equity in the leadership of research work packages. The management structure is monitored to ensure a fair distribution of tasks according to gender.

3.3. Gender distribution among researchers of REBOOT

The following table shows the updated gender distribution of researchers in REBOOT at the time of the Gender Action Plan, May 2023, the Updated Gender Action Plan, May 2024, and the distribution as of January 2026.

Partner	Female (2023/2024/ 2026)	Male (2023/ 2024/ 2026)	Non-Binary	Total (2023/ 2024/ 2026)	Team Leader		WP Leader
					F	M	

¹ UNESCO (2018). Reshaping cultural policies: advancing creativity for development, p. 189.

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UNIVIE	3 / 4 / 4	0 / 0 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	3 / 4 / 6	X		WP1, WP5, WP7, WP8
ULIEGE	1 / 2 / 3	2 / 2 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	3 / 4 / 5		X	WP4
ELIAMEP	3 / 8 / 8	1 / 1 / 1	0 / 0 / 0	4 / 9 / 9	X		WP3
UCM	2 / 1 / 2	1 / 1 / 1	0 / 0 / 0	3 / 2 / 3		X	WP2
KHAS	2 / 3 / 3	0 / 0 / 0	0 / 0 / 0	2 / 3 / 3	X		
EUR	1 / 1 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	0 / 0 / 0	1 / 1 / 2	X		
UGENT	0 / 0 / 0	1 / 2 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	1 / 2 / 2		X	
UC3M	2 / 2 / 2	1 / 1 / 1	0 / 0 / 0	3 / 3 / 3		X	
SSSA	5 / 4 / 4	1 / 2 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	6 / 6 / 6	X		WP6
UCA	1 / 2 / 2	2 / 2 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	3 / 4 / 4		X	
JYU	2 / 2 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	0 / 0 / 0	2 / 2 / 2	X		
UW	2 / 2 / 2	2 / 2 / 2	0 / 0 / 0	4 / 4 / 4		X	
TOTAL	2023: 24 (69%) 2024: 31 (70%) 2026: 34 (70%)	2023: 11 (31%) 2024: 13 (30%) 2026: 15 (30%)	2023: 0 2024: 0 2026: 0	2023: 35 2024: 44 2026: 49	6	6	

Table 2: Gender distribution of the researcher in REBOOT, in the years 2023, 2024 and 2026

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REBOOT demonstrates a significantly high level of participation from female researchers, who now comprise 70% of the total project participants, reflecting a sustained commitment to the active involvement of women in scientific research. This represents a positive contribution of REBOOT to gender equality in research more broadly. Regarding leadership of work packages, there is an equal distribution of Team Leaders, with 50% male and 50% female, demonstrating gender balance at decision-making levels.

While no researchers currently identify as non-binary, REBOOT affirmed its commitment to inclusivity for individuals of all gender identities. Efforts have been made to focus on maintaining gender-balanced participation in internal meetings, workshops, and external conferences or events.

3.4. Gender distribution of REBOOT public events, publications and interviews

Partner	Public events	Publications	Interviews/Activities
UNIVIE	<p>Presentation at Cannes festival: One female presenter</p> <p>Conference presentation in Ljubljana, Slovenia – September 2024: Three female presenters</p> <p>Conference presentation in Zagreb, Croatia – November 2024: Two female presenters</p> <p>Conference presentation in Rotterdam, Netherlands – June 2025: One female presenter</p> <p>Conference presentation in</p>	<p>Book chapter: 4 female authors</p> <p>Book chapter: 3 female authors</p> <p>Article – Special issue Journal: 2 female authors</p> <p>Book chapter: 3 female authors, 2 male authors</p> <p>Book chapter: 4 female authors, 1 male authors</p> <p>Book chapter: 3 female authors, 2 male authors,</p> <p>Policy Brief: 4 female authors, 3 male authors</p>	<p>Two female Advisory Board members, two young male film makers, female film school director and a female young film director</p> <p>T3.3 one of the deliverables (Governance of Public value) produced by this task conducted 8 interviews where 4 interviewees were female</p> <p>T3.3 the second deliverable (Fringes) conducted 66 interviews where 35 female, 30 male and 1 as non-binary.</p> <p>T5.1. included a survey with teenagers and</p>

	<p>Ljubljana, Slovenia – August 2025: one female presenter, one male presenter</p> <p>Conference presentations in Vienna, Austria – October 2025: Three female presenters, one male presenter</p> <p>Conference presentation in St. Pölten, Austria, November 2025: Two male presenters</p>	<p><u>Reports:</u> D3.2 (4 female authors) D3.4 (3 female authors, 4 male authors) D5.1 (4 female authors, 1 male authors) D5.6 (10 female authors, 5 male authors) D7.14 (20 female authors, 6 male authors)</p>	<p>youth. In fulfilment of this task, UNIVIE had 512 participants, of which 65.7% identified as female, 31.4% as male and 0.2% as non-binary.</p> <p>The total number of participants across all participating partners was 4,453, of which 63.1% identified as female, 33.2% as male and 1.5% as non-binary.</p> <p>T5.5. included focus group interviews with teenagers and youth. In fulfilment of this task, UNIVIE conducted interviews with 102 young people, of which 61 were female.</p> <p>The total number of participants across all participating partners was 607, of which 390 identified as female, 216 as male and 1 as non-binary.</p>
<p>ULIEGE</p>		<p>Authors: one male, three female</p> <p>Policy Brief: one female, one male</p>	<p>The survey from T4.1 had questions about the gender of respondents, The interviews in the T4.1 focused implicitly on gender and youth. As such, WP4 researchers highlighted both issues in the T4.1 common report.</p>

			T4.1 conducted 37 interviews of which 20 were female. On the survey, 47% of respondents (n=432) were women.
ELIAMEP	<p>Festival presentation 05.2024: 1 female</p> <p>Conference presentation 06.2024: 1 female</p> <p>Conference presentation 12.2024: 1 male</p> <p>Workshop 02.2025: 3 females</p> <p>Roundtable discussion 04.2025: 2 females</p> <p>Conference presentation 1, 05.2024: 2 females</p> <p>Conference presentation 2, 05.2025: 1 female, 1 male</p> <p>Conference presentation 3, 05.2025: 3 females</p> <p>Conference presentation 4, 05.2025: 1 female</p> <p>Conference presentation 09.2025: 1 female</p>	<p>1 Book chapter (forthcoming): 2 females, 1 male</p> <p>2 Articles in peer review journals: 4 females, 1 male</p> <p>1 Book (forthcoming): 2 females, 1 male (total authors: 5)</p> <p>Reports: D2.1: 1 male, 2 females (total authors: 5) D3.5: 1 male, 4 females (total authors: 22) D3.6: 1 male, 3 females (total authors: 19)</p> <p>Policy brief: 1 male, 2 females (total authors: 5)</p>	<p>For T3.4, 4 out of the 6 interviewees were female.</p> <p>For T3.5, 4 out of the 10 interviewees were female.</p> <p>For the T5.5 university student focus groups, some groups had a balanced mix of male and female participants, while others were predominantly female. Likewise for the school student focus groups, while some consisted entirely of female students, others included both male and female participants.</p>

	<p>Conference presentation 10.2025: 3 females, 1 male</p> <p>Film Festival Workshop 11.2025: 3 females</p> <p>Podcast 11.2025: 1 female</p>		
UCM	<p>Research tool presentation 2023 (female)</p> <p>Round table, 04.2023 (male, female)</p> <p>Conference presentation, 06.2024 (male)</p> <p>Participation research seminary, 10.2024 (male)</p> <p>Participation round table, 01.2025 (male)</p> <p>Moderation of round table, 03.2025 (male, female)</p> <p>Organisation and moderation, conference, 05.2025 (male)</p> <p>Conference presentation, 06.2025 (male)</p> <p>Conference presentation, 10.2025 (male)</p>	<p>Authors: 2 authors (male, female) in 2 texts for the upcoming volume of the REBOOT project; One male is also co-editor of the volume and contributes to the conclusions.</p> <p>3 Book chapters (3 females)</p> <p>2 Articles in peer review journals (2 males)</p> <p>Reports: D2.2: 1 male, 2 females. Total authors: 6. D2.3: 1 male. Total authors: 3. D2.4: 1 male, 1 female. Total authors: 4.</p> <p>Policy brief: 1 male, female (total authors: 4)</p> <p>Other texts: - 1 male</p>	<p>Results: The first, and most obvious, is the absence of female interlocutors. Of the 24 interviews conducted, only six (25%) have been answered by women. Of these, three were representatives of public film institutions (related to D2.3), compared to three professionals from the private industry. This reality reflects the under-representation of professional women within a male-dominated film industry.</p> <p>This situation is even more relevant in positions of high responsibility, where women only occupy 20% of management and production positions, according to Association of Women Filmmakers and Audiovisual Media CIMA (2022).</p>

	<p>Final conference presentation, 10.2025 (male)</p> <p>Participation research seminary 12.2025 (male)</p>	<p>- 1 female, 1 male 1 female</p>	
KHAS	<p>Presenters in conferences: three female</p> <p>Presenter at Istanbul film festival: one female</p>	<p>Authors: three females</p> <p>2 Book chapters (forthcoming): 3 females</p> <p>1 Article (forthcoming): 3 females</p> <p>2 Reports: 3 females</p> <p>2 Policy Briefs: 3 Females</p> <p>Other texts: 2 Blogposts: 2 females</p>	<p>For WP3.6, where we interviewed film festivals supported by the EU in non-EU countries (Türkiye, Chile, Argentina), all festival coordinators were female.</p> <p>For WP4.3, where we interviewed Turkish film industry professionals, we talked to 16 professionals: 9 of them were female.</p>
EUR	<p>Presenter in European Parliament presentation: female;</p> <p>Presenter in Rotterdam Film Festival: three females, one male;</p> <p>Presenter in ANIMAR conference in Brussels: one female</p>	<p>Two male, seven females in two chapters for upcoming volumes of the REBOOT project</p>	<p>T4.3 was led by EUR. It combined interviews and a survey. In Argentina, 17 interviews were conducted, of which 5 were with women. In Brazil, 16 interviews were conducted, of which 11 were with women. In Mexico, 14 interviews were conducted, of which 6 were with women. In South Africa, 18 interviews were conducted, of which 15</p>

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			<p>were with women. In South Korea, 17 interviews were conducted, of which 7 were with women. Finally, in Türkiye, 16 interviews were conducted, of which 9 were with women. In total, 98 interviews were conducted, of which 53 were with women.</p> <p>Regarding the survey, it led to 425 valid responses, of which most respondents (61.4%) were male. Conversely, female respondents were 36.9% of the sample and 1.6% of respondents were non-binary/third gender. In terms of their ethnic origin, 59.8% of survey respondents were white, 19.8% identified as mixed/multiple ethnic groups, 7.8% asian, 3.3% black/african/caribbean, 5.2% preferred not to say, 4.2% identified as other.</p> <p>An intersectional analysis was made. This was included as an Annex to the report. However, results were not strong enough to suggest that either the variables under</p>
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			consideration or their intersection influenced the findings significantly
UGENT	N/A	Authors: two male	For WP2.2 [and T3.3], where we are interviewing senior professionals in the Flemish and European Film Industry, we have included several questions related to inclusion, diversity, youth and gender related fringes in our interviews. On top of this, we look for as much gender parity as possible in the number of people we interview, but this remains a challenge due to structural over-representation of men in the industry in the positions we are interviewing (e.g. senior producers, distributors and exhibitors). For now, we have interviewed 17 men and 5 women. We also plan to undertake further specific interviews focusing on these fringes, including with film festivals (JEF) and experts within the Flemish public broadcasting organisation (VRT). We see various discourses emerging around diversity and inclusion, ranging from

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			conservative (diversity as quota, something that inhibits creativity) to progressive (diversity as a necessary and positive shift in the industry) and more.
UC3M	<p>Presenter in conferences: one or two female</p> <p>Presenters at Cannes festival: two female</p> <p>Presenter at panel at Rotterdam festival: 1 female</p>	<p>Authors: (upcoming) collective volume: One male and two females.</p> <p>Policy brief: One male, two females</p>	<p>For Task 3.4 nine interviews were conducted with representatives of Spanish public film institutions: three women and six men.</p> <p>For Task 4.3 47 interviews were conducted with key film industry stakeholders in Argentina, Brazil and Mexico: 25 male, 22 female.</p> <p>Argentina 17 interviewees: 12 male /5 female</p> <p>Brazil 16 interviewees: 5 male/ 11 female</p> <p>Mexico 14 interviewees: 8 male/ 6 female</p> <p>didn't mention any instances where gender equality has not been achieved or where individuals have been treated poorly due to their gender. We will prioritise achieving gender parity among the remaining interviewees for T4.3</p>

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SSSA	N/A	<p>Authors: two females in the upcoming volume of the REBOOT project;</p> <p>Two females for a peer-reviewed journal article;</p> <p>two females for the policy briefing;</p> <p>One female and one male for the project deliverable.</p>	<p>Four participants were interviewed for the WP3 (T3.3) for the stakeholders in the Italian context: two female and one male representative of public institutions (Ministry and legislative bodies) and one male representative from state-owned companies and associations.</p>
UCA	Presenter at Cannes festival: one male	Authors: Two female, two male	<p>Workshop held by one female and one male moderator, two invited music composers, one female and one male. The ratio of the audience/participants was 60/40 male and female.</p>
JYU	Presenters in conferences, seminars and research events: two females	Authors: two females	<p>The interviews carried out for the preparation of D2.3 in the Finnish context have highlighted the following gender issues: Four of the nine interviewees from the Finnish Film Foundation were women. In the interviews, women were underrepresented compared to the Foundation's current staff: more than half of them are women. The female interviewees did</p>

			<p>not bring up situations where equality between the sexes has not been realised or they have been treated badly because of their gender.</p> <p>The questions related to (gender) equality are emphasised in the Foundation’s strategy. The Foundation states on its website: “The Foundation was involved in publishing the guidelines prepared in collaboration by several organisations for the prevention of sexual harassment in our industry.”</p> <p>In T5.1, an interviewed expert from the European Film Academy was female. In T3.4, the two interviewed experts were both females. In T3.6, the interviewed experts included 4 females and 6 males.</p>
UW	TV interview: one female	Authors: Two female, two male	<p>The interviews carried out for the preparation of WP in the Polish context have highlighted the following gender issues: 11 interviewees from the Polish film industry were women and 10 were men. The female interviewees did not emphasise that they were mistreated in</p>

		<p>the industry and the issue was not highlighted. Equality between the sexes has not been the focal point of the discussion. Famous Polish film directors (Małgorzata Szumowska and Agnieszka Holland) were mentioned in the interviews as the most striking and positive examples of female careers in the film industry.</p> <p>Worth mentioning in this context is the major shift in the political situation in Poland recently, from the right and conservative approach toward the more liberal one. The Polish Film Institute director and Polish Film Archives Institute will have new directors, there is open position due to recent election and changes in all major public institutions.</p>
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Table 3: Gender distribution of REBOOT public events, publications and interviews

Cannes May 2025:

REBOOT was presented once again at Cannes 2025 through the panel “Circulation of European Films: Youth Preferences and Latin American Markets.” The panel explored how European films reach Latin American audiences, focusing on both the challenges and opportunities for European cinema in the region.

REBOOT researchers shared insights alongside industry experts, addressing key topics such as distribution strategies, the growing role of streaming platforms, and shifting youth preferences. The

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

discussion highlighted the importance of understanding regional markets and audience dynamics to improve the visibility and circulation of European films beyond Europe.

The panel was composed by:

Katharine Sarikakis, Professor of Media Governance, Media Industries and Media Organisation, REBOOT Consortium Coordinator, University of Vienna (Austria)

M^a Trinidad García Leiva, Associate Professor and REBOOT Researcher, Carlos III University of Madrid (Spain)

Isabela Vargas Miranda, REBOOT Researcher, Carlos III University of Madrid (Spain)

Marianna Vargas Gurilieva, Film Commissioner, Dominican Republic Film Commission (DGCINE)

Marcio Migliorisi, Head of International Affairs, Uruguayan Film and Audiovisual Agency (ACAU)

3.5. Gender distribution of the Advisory Board

The following table shows the gender distribution of the Advisory Board. Those who signed the Advisory Board Letter on behalf of their organisation or as an individual and thus granted support were selected.

Advisory Board Organisations	Female	Male	Non-binary
Austrian Film Institute, Simon Fraser University, Documentary Association of Europe e.V., European Broadcasting Union, EUROCINEMA, Europa Distribution, Universidad Autonoma Metropolitana, International Federation of Coalitions for Cultural Diversity, RMIT University - School of Media and	7	5	0

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Communication, University of Toronto, University of the Witwatersrand			
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Table 4: Gender distribution of the Advisory Board of REBOOT

The gender distribution of the Advisory Board is balanced. There are seven female and five male participants as representatives of the advisory board institutions. However, since it can be assumed that other representatives of the participating organisations may, on occasion, participate in project meetings, a constant across all Advisory Board meetings cannot be assumed, however an overall balance can.

3.6. Gender distribution of the coordinator team (UNIVIE/Universität Wien)

Role	Gender		
	F	M	N-B
Project legal signatory	X		
Project financial signatory	X		
Project leader	X		
Team member 1	X		
Team member 2	X		
Team member 3		X	
Team member 4		X	
Team member 5	X		

Table 5: Gender distribution of the coordinator team as of January 2026

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

ANNEX 1: SAMPLE OF GENDER EQUALITY PLANS

This annex includes the gender equality plans of the following partners:

1. UNIVIE
2. ELIAMEP
3. JYU
4. SSSA
5. KHAS

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Mitteilungsblatt

Studienjahr 2018/2019 - Ausgegeben am 13.05.2019 - 21. Stück

Sämtliche Funktionsbezeichnungen sind geschlechtsneutral zu verstehen.

Satzung

120. Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien

Satzung

Nr. 120

Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien

Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien

Der Senat hat in seiner Sitzung am 9. Mai 2019 auf Vorschlag des Rektorates und des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen den nachstehenden Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien beschlossen:

Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien

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Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien

Präambel

Die Universität Wien bekennt sich zur Frauenförderung und zu einer aktiven Gleichstellung von Frauen und Männern, zu einer Gleichstellung von Personen mit Behinderung und/oder chronischer Erkrankung, sowie zu einem respektvollen Umgang mit Trans-, intergeschlechtlichen und nichtbinären Personen. Sie lehnt jede Diskriminierung sowie eine Benachteiligung im Zusammenhang mit Betreuungspflichten ab.

Die Universität Wien strebt an, den Anteil der Mitarbeiterinnen in allen Organisationseinheiten, auf allen Hierarchieebenen und in allen Funktionen und Tätigkeiten an der Universität Wien, in denen Frauen unterrepräsentiert sind, sowohl in befristeten als auch in unbefristeten Arbeitsverhältnissen und in Ausbildungsverhältnissen mittelfristig auf 50 % zu erhöhen.

Die Organe und Angehörigen der Universität Wien sind dem Grundsatz der Gleichstellung verpflichtet und bekennen sich zur Diversität. Die leitenden Grundsätze ergeben sich aus den Bestimmungen des Bundes- Gleichbehandlungsgesetzes in der geltenden Fassung, im Folgenden B-GIBG, insbesondere aus dem allgemeinen Frauenförderungsgebot gemäß § 11 Abs 1 B-GIBG, sowie aus der sinngemäßen Anwendung des § 11b B-GIBG, § 11c B-GIBG, § 11d B-GIBG, aus dem Frauenförderungsplan im Wirkungsbereich des Bundesministeriums für Wissenschaft und Forschung (BGBl II 97/2008) sowie aus dem Universitätsgesetz 2002 (insbesondere §§ 2Z 9 und 10 Universitätsgesetz 2002). Die Aufgaben der Universität ergeben sich ebenfalls aus dem Universitätsgesetz 2002.

Die Universitätsangehörigen unterlassen jedes Verhalten, das eine Diskriminierung aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion und der Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung sowie Mobbing, sexuelle Belästigung und Gewalt darstellt und tragen zur Verhinderung solcher Verhaltensweisen bei.

Die zuständigen Organe der Universität Wien haben den erreichten Standard der Antidiskriminierung und Geschlechtergleichstellung kontinuierlich auszubauen und zu dokumentieren. Sie tragen zur Bewusstseinsbildung bei und unterstützen von Diskriminierung betroffene Personen bei der Durchsetzung ihrer Rechte.

Es wird festgehalten, dass es sich bei den aufgezählten Diversitätsdimensionen nicht um eine abschließende Liste handelt. Die Erscheinungsformen von Diskriminierungen können je nach Kontext variieren und unterliegen einem zeitlichen Wandel. Die Universität Wien fördert einen flexiblen Ansatz, der offen bleibt für Schutz vor anderen Formen der Diskriminierung. Außerdem wird darauf Bedacht genommen, die verschiedenen Dimensionen nicht nur isoliert, sondern auch intersektional zu betrachten, indem auf die wechselseitige Beeinflussung mehrerer Diskriminierungsformen und die dadurch entstehenden eigenen Diskriminierungserfahrungen Rücksicht genommen wird. Genauso ist der Universität Wien die faktische Diversität unter ihren Angehörigen ein Anliegen.

Durch Gender Mainstreaming und Frauenförderungsmaßnahmen in Personalplanung, Personalentwicklung, Forschung und Lehre wird bzw. werden

- auf die Beseitigung der Unterrepräsentation von Frauen in allen Bereichen hingewirkt,
- gleiche Arbeitsbedingungen, gleiche Aufstiegschancen sowie gleiche Entlohnung für gleichwertige Arbeit für Frauen und Männer sichergestellt,

- Frauen und Männern ein gleichberechtigter Zugang zu allen Mitteln und Möglichkeiten im Bereich von Infrastruktur, finanziellen Ressourcen, Entlohnung u. a. gewährleistet,
- Frauen bei Forschungsprojekten und der wissenschaftlichen Weiterqualifikation mit dem Ziel eine zur Berufungsfähigkeit führende Qualifikation zu erreichen, gefördert.

Durch Gleichstellungs- und Antidiskriminierungsmaßnahmen fördert die Universität Wien

- die Chancengleichheit von Frauen und Männern in allen universitären Bereichen,
- ein diskriminierungsfreies Arbeits- und Studenumfeld für alle Angehörigen der Universität Wien,
- die Vereinbarkeit von Betreuungspflichten mit Beruf und Studium,
- eine würdevolle, durch sexuelle Belästigungen nicht beeinträchtigte Studien- und Arbeitsatmosphäre,
- die Information und Kommunikation über Fragen der Gleichstellung, Antidiskriminierung und Frauenförderung.

Die Universität Wien strebt an, dass

- eine adäquate Infrastruktur zur Verwirklichung von Antidiskriminierung, Gleichstellung und Frauenförderung besteht,
- Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung verstärkt in Forschung und Lehre integriert werden.

Die Universität Wien strebt an

- entsprechende Rahmenbedingungen zur Förderung der Vereinbarkeit von Familie, Beruf und Studium,
- insbesondere Maßnahmen in den Bereichen: Kinderbetreuung, Förderung einer familienfreundlichen Unternehmenskultur, familienfreundliche Arbeitsbedingungen und Karrieremöglichkeiten, Infrastruktur, Beratungsangebote und Informationsbereitstellung bereit zu stellen.

A. Allgemeine Bestimmungen

§ 1. Anwendungsbereich

Der Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan gilt für alle Angehörigen der Universität Wien (§ 94 Universitätsgesetz 2002) sowie für die Bewerberinnen und Bewerber um Aufnahme in ein Arbeitsverhältnis zur Universität Wien oder um Aufnahme als Studierende.

§ 2. Gebrauch von diskriminierungsfreier und geschlechtergerechter Sprache

(1) Alle Organe und Angehörigen des wissenschaftlichen und allgemeinen Personals der Universität Wien bedienen sich in Aussendungen, Formularen, Protokollen, Reden und anderen an die Öffentlichkeit oder an die Universitätsangehörigen gerichteten Mitteilungen wie auch im Internet diskriminierungsfreier und geschlechtergerechter Sprache. Es sind die weibliche und männliche Form oder geschlechtsneutrale Bezeichnungen zu verwenden.

(2) Die Formulierung von Generalklauseln, in denen z.B. zu Beginn, am Ende oder in Fußnoten eines Textes festgehalten wird, dass die gewählten personenbezogenen Bezeichnungen für beide Geschlechter gelten, ist unzulässig.

(3) Auf dem Gelände der Universität Wien dürfen weder von der Universität noch durch Dritte Verlautbarungen, Plakate oder andere Materialien angebracht oder verteilt werden, deren Inhalte den Grundsätzen der Antidiskriminierung und Gleichstellung widersprechen oder diskriminierende Rollenstereotype verwenden oder vermitteln.

§ 3. Umsetzung von Gender Mainstreaming an der Universität Wien

(1) Gender Mainstreaming ist umzusetzen bei

1. der Erstellung des Entwurfs einer Satzung, der Erlassung oder Änderung einer Satzung,
2. der Erstellung und Zustimmung zu dem Entwicklungsplan sowie bei der Genehmigung des Entwicklungsplans,
3. der Erstellung und Genehmigung eines Entwurfs der Leistungsvereinbarung sowie bei deren Verhandlung und Abschluss,
4. der Erstellung und Genehmigung der Wissensbilanz,
5. Stellungnahmen.

(2) Bei der Erlassung von Richtlinien für die Tätigkeit von Kollegialorganen gemäß § 25 Abs. 1 Z 15 Universitätsgesetz 2002 durch den Senat ist ebenfalls auf die Grundsätze von Gender Mainstreaming, Gleichstellung der Geschlechter und Antidiskriminierung zu achten.

§ 4. Entwicklungspläne und Zielvereinbarungen

(1) Die Ziele der Gleichstellung der Geschlechter, Frauenförderung und Antidiskriminierung sind in die Leistungsvereinbarung, den Entwicklungsplan und in die Zielvereinbarungen zwischen dem Rektorat und den Organisationseinheiten einzubeziehen. In den Zielvereinbarungen zwischen dem Rektorat und den Organisationseinheiten sind bei bestehender Unterrepräsentation quantifizierte Frauenförderungsziele zu formulieren.

(2) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist in diesem Zusammenhang bei Erstellung der Entwicklungspläne sowie der Zielvereinbarungen von den jeweiligen Organisationsleiterinnen und Organisationsleitern anzuhören.

(3) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist über die im Rahmen der Zielvereinbarungen zwischen dem Rektorat und den Organisationseinheiten getroffenen Maßnahmen zur Frauenförderung zu informieren.

§ 5. Benachteiligungsverbot

(1) Kollektivverträge und Betriebsvereinbarungen dürfen keine Bestimmungen enthalten, die zu Diskriminierung aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung führen können. Die Vertreterin oder der Vertreter der Universität Wien wirkt im Dachverband der Universitäten darauf hin, dass Kollektivverträge keine potenziell unmittelbar oder mittelbar diskriminierenden Bestimmungen enthalten.

(2) Im Zusammenhang mit einem Arbeitsvertrag darf niemand aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung mittelbar oder unmittelbar diskriminiert werden. Das gilt insbesondere bei der Festsetzung des Entgelts und sonstiger geldwerter Leistungen (Zulagen, Beiträge) und Einstufungen. Dasselbe gilt für Zusagen von Ressourcen im Rahmen von Berufungsverhandlungen.

(3) Universitätsangehörige dürfen beim Zugang zu Ressourcen oder Infrastruktur und der Zuteilung von Räumen etc. nicht aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung diskriminiert werden.

§ 6. Förderung von Diversität

Sämtliche zur Frauenförderung vorgesehenen Instrumente sind, soweit möglich, auch im Sinne einer antidiskriminierenden, diversitätsfördernden und gleichstellungsfördernden Universitätspolitik anzuwenden (z.B. Vergabe von Stipendien, Entwicklung und Ausführung von Mentoringprogrammen, Coaching und ähnliche Maßnahmen).

Karriereplanung, Aus- und Weiterbildung

§ 7. Arbeitszeitflexibilität

(1) Forschungsarbeit und familiäre Verpflichtungen sind bei der Festlegung der Arbeitszeit, insbesondere auch bei der Festlegung von Vorlesungs-, Prüfungs- und Sitzungszeiten zu berücksichtigen.

(2) Die Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter sind über die gesetzlichen oder vertraglichen bzw. kollektivvertraglichen Möglichkeiten zur Herabsetzung der Wochendienstzeit oder Teilzeitbeschäftigung, zur Gestaltung flexibler Arbeitszeiten, zur Inanspruchnahme von Sonderurlaub und Karenz aus familiären Gründen und zur Pflegefreistellung zu informieren. Die Möglichkeit zur Wahrnehmung dieser Rechte ist durch organisatorische Maßnahmen sicherzustellen. Bei der Herabsetzung der Wochendienstzeit auf die Hälfte bzw. bei

Teilzeitarbeit sind die Aufgabenbereiche entsprechend zu reduzieren. Arbeitszeitflexibilität ist bei Karriere- und Mitarbeiterinnen- und Mitarbeitergesprächen zu erörtern.

(3) Für eigene Forschungstätigkeit sind allen Forscherinnen und Forschern ausschließliche und zusammenhängende Forschungszeiten einzuräumen.

(4) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist bei der Entwicklung von neuen Modellen zur Gestaltung und Erfassung der Arbeitszeit und An- und Abwesenheitsverwaltung hinzuzuziehen.

(5) Die Inanspruchnahme von Teilzeitbeschäftigungs- und Karenzierungsmöglichkeiten insbesondere zur Erfüllung familiärer Verpflichtungen darf nicht zur unsachlichen unmittelbaren oder mittelbaren Diskriminierung von Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeitern im Zusammenhang mit ihrem Beschäftigungs- oder Ausbildungsverhältnis führen.

§ 8. Mentoring

(1) Die unmittelbaren Vorgesetzten sind verpflichtet, für eine bedarfsgerechte Einführung neuer Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter in ihre Aufgabenbereiche zu sorgen. Vorgesetzte haben als Mentorin oder Mentor zu wirken; bei diesen Aufgaben können sie sich durch erfahrene Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter unterstützen lassen. Für eine entsprechende Ausbildung der Mentorinnen und Mentoren ist Sorge zu tragen.

(2) Die Vorgesetzten haben auf die daraus erwachsenden zusätzlichen Belastungen bei der Verteilung der Dienstpflichten besondere Rücksicht zu nehmen. Mentoring-Aktivitäten sind bei Evaluationen positiv zu bewerten.

Infrastruktur und Aufgaben

Einrichtungen zur Frauenförderung und Gleichbehandlung

§ 9. Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen

(1) Gemäß § 42 Universitätsgesetz 2002 ist an der Universität Wien ein Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen eingerichtet (Mitteilungsblatt vom 23. 12. 2003, 4. Stück, Nr. 16 idgF).

(2) Die Erfüllung der Aufgaben als Mitglied oder Ersatzmitglied im Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen oder Kontaktperson (Abs. 8 und Abs. 10) ist als wichtiger Beitrag zur Erfüllung der sich aus dem Ausbildungs- oder Beschäftigungsverhältnis ergebenden Pflichten bzw. Dienstpflichten im Bereich der Verwaltung anzusehen und auf die Arbeits- bzw. Dienstzeit anzurechnen.

(3) Bei der Festlegung von Dienstpflichten ist die nachgewiesene zusätzliche Belastung aus der Tätigkeit als Mitglied oder Ersatzmitglied des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen, als Kontaktperson oder Genderbeauftragte bzw. Genderbeauftragter zu berücksichtigen.

(4) Den Mitgliedern und Ersatzmitgliedern des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen darf aus ihrer Funktion weder während der Ausübung ihrer Funktion noch nach dem Ausscheiden aus dieser Funktion ein beruflicher Nachteil erwachsen. Bei Leistungsbeurteilungen ist in begründeten Fällen auf den tatsächlichen Zeitaufwand der Tätigkeit für den Arbeitskreis Rücksicht zu nehmen.

(5) Die Tätigkeit als Vorsitzende oder als Vorsitzender des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist bei etwaigen Qualifikationsfeststellungen zu berücksichtigen.

(6) Der oder dem Vorsitzenden des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist nach der Beendigung ihrer oder seiner Tätigkeit im Arbeitskreis, sofern ihr oder sein Arbeitsverhältnis andauert, eine Freistellung für Forschung unter Beibehaltung der vollen Bezüge sowie der Aufwandsentschädigung für ein Semester zu gewähren, sofern sie oder er ihre oder seine Funktion als Vorsitzende oder Vorsitzender mindestens eine Funktionsperiode ausgeübt hat. Der Vorsitzenden oder dem Vorsitzenden ist während ihrer oder seiner Tätigkeit eine Funktionszulage von € 5.000,00 brutto/jährlich zu gewähren.

(7) Den Mitgliedern und Ersatzmitgliedern des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen sowie den Kontaktpersonen ist die Teilnahme an regelmäßigen Schulungen und Informationsveranstaltungen zu ermöglichen.

(8) Die Mitglieder und Ersatzmitglieder des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen und die Kontaktpersonen sind berechtigt, ihre Aufgaben in Gleichbehandlungsfragen an ihrem Arbeitsplatz zu erfüllen und hierfür die dem Arbeitsplatz zur Verfügung stehenden Einrichtungen zu benützen.

(9) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen kann pro Studienkonferenz, sofern dies notwendig und zweckmäßig ist, eine Kontaktperson nominieren. Die Kontaktperson berät die Studienprogrammleiterin oder den Studienprogrammleiter bei der diskriminierungsfreien Gestaltung und Organisation der Studienprogramme, insbesondere bei der Evaluation der Studienprogramme, der Vergabe von Lehraufträgen und der Gestaltung von Curricula. Zu diesem Zweck ist die Kontaktperson beratendes Mitglied der Studienkonferenz und informiert den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen.

(10) Auf begründeten Wunsch von Angehörigen der betreffenden Subeinheiten kann der Arbeitskreis für diese Subeinheit, sofern dies notwendig und zweckmäßig ist, eine Kontaktperson nominieren. Diese berät die Subeinheitsleiterin oder den Subeinheitsleiter in Fragen der Gleichbehandlung, Frauenförderung, Antidiskriminierung und Gleichstellung und berichtet an den Arbeitskreis.

(11) In den Fällen des § 42 Abs. 8 Universitätsgesetz 2002 beginnt die Frist zur Anrufung der Schiedskommission durch den Arbeitskreis am Tag nach Zugang der Entscheidung an den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen zu laufen.

(12) Dem Arbeitskreis zur Verfügung gestellte Informationen sind vertraulich zu behandeln. Die Mitglieder und Ersatzmitglieder des Arbeitskreises sind zur Verschwiegenheit verpflichtet.

§ 10. Ressourcen

(1) Das Rektorat hat dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen die erforderlichen Ressourcen (Personal-, Raum- und Sachaufwand) zur Verfügung zu stellen.

(2) Bei der Auswahl der dem Arbeitskreis zur Verfügung gestellten Arbeitsräumlichkeiten ist auf deren zentrale Lage und barrierefreie Zugänglichkeit zu achten.

§ 11. Geschäftsbereich Gleichstellung und Frauenförderung im Rektorat

Im Rektorat ist ein Geschäftsbereich Gleichstellung und Diversität eingerichtet. Das zuständige Mitglied des Rektorats setzt Programme zur Frauenförderung, zur Diversität, zu Gender Mainstreaming und zu Gender Budgeting an der Universität Wien um.

§ 12. Abteilung Gleichstellung und Diversität

(1) Die Abteilung Gleichstellung und Diversität ist eine Serviceeinrichtung der Universität Wien gemäß § 19 Abs. 2 Z 7 Universitätsgesetz 2002 zur Koordination der Aufgaben. Ihre Aufgaben liegen in der Entwicklung und Umsetzung von Gleichstellungs- und Diversitätskonzepten sowie Gleichstellungs- und Diversitätsmaßnahmen, im Gleichstellungscontrolling, in der Durchführung von Karriereförderprogrammen für Nachwuchswissenschaftlerinnen und in der Sensibilisierung für Fragen der Frauenförderung, Gleichstellung und Diversität.

(2) Der Abteilung Gleichstellung und Diversität ist die Beratungsstelle Sexuelle Belästigung und Mobbing zugeordnet.

(3) Der Abteilung Gleichstellung und Diversität werden ausreichende personelle, räumliche und budgetäre Ressourcen zur Verfügung gestellt.

§ 13. Referat Genderforschung

Der Geschäftsbereich Gender Studies/Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung dient der Unterstützung und dem Ausbau von Forschung und Lehre im Bereich der Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung u. a. durch:

1. Service, Koordination und Information für Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler sowie Studierende im Bereich Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung und im entsprechenden wissenschaftlich-künstlerischen Bereich; Informationsweitergabe, Erstellung von Informationsmaterialien in den unterschiedlichsten Medien,
2. Unterstützung und Ausbau von Forschungs- und Lehraktivitäten der Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung; Vermittlung der Inhalte an die Öffentlichkeit und
3. Netzwerkarbeit mit anderen Koordinationsstellen und Einrichtungen im Bereich der Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung.

§ 14. Budgetangelegenheiten

(1) Bei Budgeterstellung und Budgetzuweisung im Rahmen der Zielvereinbarungen sind die Gebote der Gleichstellung und Frauenförderung als planungs- und verteilungsrelevante Gesichtspunkte zu beachten.

(2) Die Beseitigung der Unterrepräsentation von Frauen in einer Organisationseinheit ist ein Kriterium für die Vergabe von Budgetmitteln.

§ 15. Gender Budgeting

Gender Budgeting umfasst die gendergerechte Vergabe von Mitteln. Dazu gehört auch das regelmäßige Monitoring der Entlohnung sowie eine sukzessive Erweiterung des Monitorings auf neue Bereiche. Hinsichtlich der Erhebung der Entlohnung ist § 18 zu beachten.

Erhebungspflichten, Evaluation und Berichtspflichten

§ 16. Erhebung der Frauenquote

(1) Das Rektorat erhebt regelmäßig die zur Umsetzung des Frauenförderungsplans notwendigen Daten. Die Frauenquoten sind jährlich, beginnend mit dem Stichtag 1.1.2019, zu erheben und zu dokumentieren, wobei insbesondere auf den Frauenanteil unter den Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeitern, den Studierenden und den Absolventinnen und Absolventen sowie auf den Studien- und Karriereverlauf und auf das Arbeitsumfeld Bedacht zu nehmen ist.

(2) Diese Daten sind als Entscheidungsgrundlage in Personalangelegenheiten heranzuziehen mit dem Ziel, Maßnahmen zur Erhöhung des Frauenanteils zu setzen.

(3) Die Ergebnisse dieser Erhebungen sind vom Rektorat jedenfalls alle zwei Jahre zu veröffentlichen.

(4) Gelingt die Beseitigung der Unterrepräsentation in einem Bereich nicht, sind die dafür ausschlaggebenden Gründe von den verantwortlichen Entscheidungsträgerinnen und Entscheidungsträgern im Rahmen ihrer Berichtspflicht anzugeben.

§ 17. Sonstige Berichte an den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen

Neben den in §§ 4 Abs. 3, 19, 27 Abs. 2, 39 Abs. 5, 54 Abs. 1 und Abs. 2 Z 5, genannten Berichten hat das Rektorat dem Arbeitskreis bis zum Ende des Kalenderjahres insbesondere darüber zu berichten:

1. Welche Maßnahmen gesetzt wurden, um bei internen Fortbildungsseminaren die Vereinbarkeit mit Betreuungspflichten sicherzustellen.
2. Welcher Anteil der Mittel pro Organisationseinheit, der zur Finanzierung von Teilnahmen an Kongressen, Tagungen, Veranstaltungen zur beruflichen Vernetzung (Networking) und Weiterbildung zur Verfügung steht, zugunsten von Frauen verwendet wurde.
3. Wie sichergestellt wurde, dass von beauftragten externen Beraterinnen und Beratern in Personalentwicklungsangelegenheiten die Grundsätze der Geschlechtergerechtigkeit und Antidiskriminierung eingehalten wurden.
4. Welche Organe bestellt wurden und wie diese zusammengesetzt sind (§ 41).
5. Wie viele Führungskräfte an Aus- und Weiterbildungen im Sinn von § 42 teilgenommen haben.

§ 18. Erhebung der Entlohnung

(1) Weiters ist die Entlohnung von Frauen und Männern nach Maßgabe der Wissensbilanz-Verordnung 2016 idgF getrennt zu erheben und zu veröffentlichen.

(2) An der Universität Wien besteht ein Gender Controlling System mit dem Schwerpunkt Gender Pay Gap. Das Rektorat stellt den jeweiligen Entscheidungsträgerinnen und Entscheidungsträgern Analysen für die Bereiche „Geschlechterrelationen“ nach Beschäftigungsgruppen, „Einkommen/Gender Wage Gap“ und nach Möglichkeit Ressourcenverteilung nach dem Geschlecht und ausgewählten universitären Statusgruppen, unter Berücksichtigung der Seniorität sowie Fachspezifika zur Verfügung.

§ 19. Evaluation in den Organisationseinheiten

Die bei der regelmäßigen Evaluierung der Organisationseinheiten sich nach spezifischen Umständen ergebenden Maßnahmen zur Gleichstellung, Frauenförderung und Antidiskriminierung sind dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen in geeigneter Weise zur Kenntnis zu bringen.

B. Gleichstellungsplan

§ 20. Vereinbarkeit von Familie und Beruf

- (1) Die Universität Wien fördert ein gleichberechtigtes Kinder- und Familienbetreuungsmodell (z.B. Väterkarenz) sowie die Vereinbarkeit von Familie und Beruf.
- (2) Die Universität Wien fördert insbesondere Maßnahmen zur Verbesserung der Vereinbarkeit von Beruf und familiären Sorgepflichten von Universitätsangehörigen der Universität Wien, wie etwa mit Stimulierungsmaßnahmen, good-practice Beispielen und Anreizkomponenten.
- (3) Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeitern in Elternkarenz dürfen aus dieser keine unsachlichen Nachteile erwachsen. Sie sind beim Wiedereinstieg bestmöglich zu unterstützen.
- (4) Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter haben das Recht, ihren Tätigkeitsbereich betreffende Informationen zu erhalten und in alle sie und ihr unmittelbares Arbeitsumfeld betreffenden Entscheidungsprozesse im Rahmen der gesetzlichen Bestimmungen eingebunden zu werden.
- (5) Bei Personalentwicklungsmaßnahmen soll nach Bedarf Kinderbetreuung angeboten werden. Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter in Elternkarenz sind zu Personalentwicklungsmaßnahmen zuzulassen.
- (6) Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeitern ist die Wahrnehmung der gesetzlichen oder vertraglichen Möglichkeiten der Inanspruchnahme von Familienhospizkarenz/-teilzeit, Pflegekarenz/-teilzeit und Pflegefreistellung durch organisatorische Maßnahmen zu erleichtern. Bei der Verteilung von Arbeitsaufgaben und der Festlegung von Arbeitszeiten ist auf Betreuungspflichten Rücksicht zu nehmen.

§ 21. Diskriminierungsverbot

Jede Form von Diskriminierung auf Grund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion und der Weltanschauung, des Alters und der sexuellen Orientierung stellt eine Verletzung der sich aus dem Ausbildungs- oder Beschäftigungsverhältnis ergebenden Pflichten dar und ist entsprechend den (dienst- oder arbeits-) rechtlichen Vorschriften zu sanktionieren.

§ 22. Sexuelle Belästigung, Mobbing und Diskriminierung

- (1) Alle Angehörigen der Universität Wien haben das Recht auf eine ihre Würde respektierende Behandlung, insbesondere auf Schutz vor Belästigung (iSd § 8a B-GIBG), sexueller Belästigung (iSd § 8 B-GIBG), Mobbing, Diskriminierung aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion und der Weltanschauung, des Alters und der sexuellen Orientierung.
- (2) Alle Angehörigen der Universität Wien, insbesondere solche mit Leitungsaufgaben in Forschung, Lehre und Verwaltung, sind in ihrem Arbeitsbereich dafür verantwortlich, dass sexuell belästigendes und diskriminierendes Verhalten in jeglicher Form sowie Mobbing unterbleibt.
- (3) An der Universität Wien stehen Personen, die von sexueller Belästigung, Diskriminierung oder Mobbing betroffen sind, folgende Beratungsstellen zur Verfügung:
 - Beratungsstelle Sexuelle Belästigung und Mobbing

- Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen
- Betriebsräte
- HochschülerInnenschaft
- Konfliktmanagement

(4) Die Anonymität der Ratsuchenden ist auch gegenüber der Universitätsleitung zu wahren.

(5) Die ausreichende budgetäre, personelle und räumliche Ausstattung der Beratungsstelle Sexuelle Belästigung und Mobbing zwecks kontinuierlicher Aufgabenerfüllung hierfür ist zu gewährleisten.

(6) Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeitern, die mit Personalangelegenheiten befasst sind, werden regelmäßige Fortbildungen über den Umgang mit Vorfällen sexueller Belästigung, Diskriminierung auf Grund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion und der Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung und von Mobbing angeboten und deren Besuch empfohlen. Das Thema wird regelmäßig Bestandteil von Weiterbildungsveranstaltungen insbesondere für Vorgesetzte sein.

(7) Die Universität Wien bietet im Rahmen des Weiterbildungsangebots bzw. des Hochschulsports regelmäßig Kurse zur Selbstbehauptung und pro Studienjahr mindestens einen Selbstverteidigungskurs für Frauen an.

§ 23. Maßnahmen zur Verhinderung von sexueller Belästigung, Diskriminierung, Mobbing und Gewalt

(1) Alle Dienstvorgesetzten haben ihre Befugnisse zur Verhinderung von sexueller Belästigung, Diskriminierung, Mobbing und Gewalt in ihrem universitären Wirkungsbereich wahrzunehmen. Dienstvorgesetzte haben behaupteten Vorfällen von sexueller Belästigung nachzugehen.

(2) Lehrveranstaltungsleiterinnen und Lehrveranstaltungsleiter haben ein diskriminierungsfreies Klima in der Lehrveranstaltung, bei Prüfungssituationen, auf Exkursionen und sonstigen universitären Veranstaltungen zu gewährleisten und sexuelle Belästigung zu unterbinden.

(3) Betroffene von sexueller Belästigung und Gewalt haben das Recht, von der Universitäts- bzw. Fakultäts-/Zentrumsleitung Maßnahmen gegen Belästigerinnen oder Belästiger zu verlangen oder die Schiedskommission zu befragen.

(4) Betroffene und/oder Zeuginnen und Zeugen von sexueller Belästigung und Gewalt können den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen über Übergriffe informieren. Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist verpflichtet, diese Informationen vertraulich zu behandeln und geeignete Maßnahmen zur Unterstützung der Betroffenen, zur Aufklärung des Sachverhaltes und zur Verhinderung weiterer Übergriffe in die Wege zu leiten.

§ 24. Trans-, intergeschlechtliche und nichtbinäre Personen

Die Universität Wien respektiert und unterstützt Menschen, die ihre Geschlechtsidentität ändern bzw. geändert haben, sowie Menschen, die mit ihrer Geschlechtsidentität von jenem Modell abweichen, das die Menschen notwendig als Frau oder Mann definiert.

§ 25. Ausgewogenes Verhältnis der Studierenden, sowie Absolventinnen und Absolventen

(1) In allen Studienfeldern ist ein ausgeglichenes Geschlechterverhältnis der Studierenden sowie der Absolventinnen und Absolventen anzustreben.

(2) Bei signifikanten Abweichungen sind von der Studienprogrammleitung Strategien und konkrete Maßnahmen zu entwickeln. Zu diesem Zwecke werden gesondert Mittel für besonders engagierte Maßnahmen in den Zielvereinbarungen vereinbart.

§ 26. Evaluierung der Lehre durch Studierende

(1) Bei der Evaluierung der Lehre durch die Studierenden ist zu erheben, ob die Gleichbehandlung von Studierenden verwirklicht wird und ob die Lehrinhalte unter Wahrung des Gebots der Gleichbehandlung der Geschlechter und in diskriminierungsfreier Weise vermittelt werden (z.B. Verwendung einer diskriminierungsfreien Sprache, Verzicht auf diskriminierende Beispiele und Themenstellungen sowie auf eine unkritische Auseinandersetzung mit Geschlechterfragen etc.).

(2) Außerdem ist zu erheben, ob diskriminierende Prüfungssituationen auftreten; sei es aufgrund

- des Geschlechts
- der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit
- der Religion oder der Weltanschauung
- des Alters sowie
- der sexuellen Orientierung.

(3) Weiters soll erfasst werden, ob in der Lehre frauen- und geschlechterspezifische Themenstellungen behandelt werden, soweit dies fächerspezifisch möglich ist.

C. Frauenförderungsplan

§ 27. Frauenförderungsgebot bei Unterrepräsentation

(1) Frauen gelten als unterrepräsentiert, wenn ihr Anteil unter den Beschäftigten auf einer Hierarchieebene bzw. innerhalb einer personalrechtlichen Kategorie in einer Organisationseinheit oder unter den Studierenden in einer Studienprogrammleitung weniger als 50 % beträgt.

(2) Unterrepräsentation ist in allen Bereichen zu beseitigen; über die getroffenen Maßnahmen ist alle drei Jahre an den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen zu berichten.

Personal- und Organisationsentwicklung

§ 28. Allgemeine Bestimmungen

Alle Universitätsangehörigen und insbesondere Leitungsorgane sind innerhalb ihres Wirkungsbereichs verpflichtet, ihre Tätigkeit auch an den Zielen der Antidiskriminierung, Gleichstellung und Frauenförderung auszurichten.

Sie haben:

1. auf die Beseitigung bestehender Unterrepräsentationen von Frauen an der Gesamtzahl der Beschäftigten in unbefristeten Arbeitsverhältnissen und in Funktionen hinzuwirken sowie
2. bestehende Benachteiligungen von Frauen im Zusammenhang mit dem Beschäftigungsverhältnis zu beseitigen,
3. eine bereits erreichte 50%ige Frauenquote tunlichst im Rahmen der Personalstrukturplanung zu wahren,
4. bei allen sonstigen Maßnahmen, die direkt oder indirekt auf die Frauenquote Einfluss nehmen, die Ziele dieses Frauenförderungsplanes zu berücksichtigen.

Personalaufnahme

§ 29. Allgemeines

(1) Liegt in einer Organisationseinheit der Anteil der Absolventinnen über 50 %, so ist ein Anteil von 50 % der wissenschaftlichen Mitarbeiterinnen auf allen Ebenen anzustreben.

(2) Alle an der Universität zu besetzenden Stellen sind nach Maßgabe des § 107 Abs 1 und 2 Universitätsgesetz 2002 in geeigneter Form bekannt zu machen.

(3) Bei Stellenbesetzungen, bei denen keine Ausschreibung erfolgt, sowie bei Besetzungen von Gastprofessuren gemäß § 99 Universitätsgesetz 2002 sind die Auswahlverfahren so zu gestalten, dass die Auswahl nach sachlichen Gesichtspunkten erfolgt und es zu keiner Diskriminierung auf Grund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder der Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung kommt.

§ 30. Ausschreibung

(1) Ausschreibungstexte sind so abzufassen, dass sie als objektive Entscheidungsgrundlage für das Aufnahmeverfahren dienen. Sie haben außer sämtlichen Aufnahmeerfordernissen ein umfassendes Anforderungsprofil (insbesondere die maßgeblichen und erwünschten Qualifikationen) zu enthalten. Ausschreibungstexte dürfen nicht diskriminierend auf Grund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder der Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung sein.

(2) Unzulässig sind Ausschreibungstexte, die so allgemein gehalten sind, dass sie keine objektive Entscheidungsgrundlage für die nachfolgenden Personalauswahlverfahren darstellen. Gleiches gilt für eine überspezifizierte Ausschreibung, wenn der begründete Verdacht besteht, dass der potenzielle Kreis der Bewerbungen zu Gunsten oder Ungunsten einer bestimmten Person eingeschränkt werden soll.

(3) Ausschreibungstexte für die Besetzung von Stellen sowie für Leitungsfunktionen haben den Zusatz zu enthalten: „Die Universität Wien strebt eine Erhöhung des Frauenanteils beim wissenschaftlichen und allgemeinen Universitätspersonal insbesondere in Leitungsfunktionen an und fordert daher qualifizierte Frauen ausdrücklich zur Bewerbung auf.“ Bei bestehender Unterrepräsentation ist weiters der Satz anzufügen: „Bei gleicher Qualifikation werden Frauen vorrangig aufgenommen.“

(4) Nachgewiesene Kompetenzen in Frauenförderung, Gender Mainstreaming und/oder Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung sollten bei der Besetzung von Führungspositionen mitberücksichtigt werden und sind dabei in die Begründung der Auswahl mitaufzunehmen.

§ 31. Überprüfung von Ausschreibungen

(1) Die Ausschreibungstexte und auf Verlangen die Arbeitsplatz- bzw. Aufgabenbeschreibungen sind dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen durch die betreffende Organisationseinheit unverzüglich zur Kenntnis zu bringen.

(2) Hat der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen Grund zur Annahme, dass ein Ausschreibungstext eine Diskriminierung bewirkt oder § 30 widerspricht, so ist er berechtigt, innerhalb von drei Wochen ab Vorlage Beschwerde bei der Schiedskommission zu erheben. Die Besetzung der Stelle ist bis zur Entscheidung der Schiedskommission unzulässig.

(3) Ändert das ausschreibende Organ von sich aus die Ausschreibung im Sinne der Beschwerde des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen vor einer Entscheidung der Schiedskommission ab, so ist dies der Schiedskommission unverzüglich zur Kenntnis zu bringen und das Verfahren von Amts wegen einzustellen.

(4) Solange eine Unterrepräsentation besteht, ist die Ausschreibung in einer Form vorzunehmen, durch die sichergestellt ist, dass potenzielle Bewerberinnen gezielt angesprochen und erreicht werden. Auf Verlangen ist dies gegenüber dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen zu dokumentieren.

§ 32. Überprüfung der Bewerberinnen- und Bewerberlage

Sind bis zum Ablauf der Bewerbungsfrist keine Bewerbungen von Frauen eingelangt, die die gesetzlichen Voraussetzungen und die Aufnahmeerfordernisse erfüllen und den Anforderungen des Ausschreibungstexts entsprechen, ist der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen über jene Maßnahmen zu informieren, die gesetzt wurden, um

Frauen zur Bewerbung aufzufordern. Insbesondere sind die zur Sicherstellung der in § 31 Abs. 4 vorgesehenen Anforderungen getroffenen Maßnahmen nachzuweisen.

§ 33. Wiederholung der Ausschreibung

(1) Die Ausschreibung ist zu wiederholen, wenn der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen nicht auf die Wiederholung der Ausschreibung verzichtet.

(2) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen kann auf die Wiederholung der Ausschreibung verzichten, wenn die ausschreibende Stelle nachweist, dass während oder nach Ablauf der Bewerbungsfrist gem. § 32 qualifizierten Frauen Gelegenheit zu einer nachträglichen Bewerbung gewährt wurde.

(3) Langen auf Grund der neuerlichen, ordnungsgemäß durchgeführten Ausschreibung und trotz nachweislicher aktiver Suche nach geeigneten Frauen wiederum keine Bewerbungen von Frauen ein, ist das Auswahlverfahren durchzuführen.

§ 34. Bewerbungsgespräche

(1) Zu Aufnahme- oder Auswahlgesprächen sind alle Bewerberinnen einzuladen, welche die gesetzlichen Ernennungsvoraussetzungen oder die Aufnahmeerfordernisse erfüllen und den Anforderungen des Ausschreibungstexts entsprechen. In besonders berücksichtigungswürdigen Fällen (z.B. bei einer ungewöhnlich großen Anzahl an Bewerberinnen) kann ausnahmsweise und mit aktenkundigem Einverständnis des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen die Anzahl der einzuladenden Bewerberinnen reduziert werden.

(2) Dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen sind geplante Bewerbungsgespräche auf Verlangen zur Kenntnis zu bringen und dieser hat das Recht am Bewerbungsgespräch teilzunehmen.

(3) In Aufnahmegesprächen, Hearings udgl. dürfen diskriminierende Fragen nicht gestellt werden. Bei der Beurteilung der Eignung von Bewerberinnen und Bewerbern dürfen keine Auswahl- und Bewertungskriterien herangezogen werden, die sich an einem diskriminierenden, unkritischen, rollenstereotypen Verständnis der Geschlechter orientieren oder aus anderen Gründen diskriminieren.

(4) Den Mitgliedern des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist Auskunft über sowie Einsicht in alle Bewerbungsunterlagen zu geben, deren Kenntnis zur Erfüllung der Aufgaben des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen erforderlich ist. Auf Verlangen sind diese in elektronischer Form bzw. in Kopie zu übermitteln. Gleiches gilt für über die Bewerberinnen und Bewerber eingeholte Gutachten und ähnliche Unterlagen.

(5) Gremien (Panels), die Personalauswahlentscheidungen vorbereiten, haben zu ihren Sitzungen den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen zu laden. Unterbleibt die fristgerechte Ladung, hat das Gremium in einer neuerlichen Sitzung unter ordnungsgemäßer Beiziehung des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen die Beratung und Beschlussfassung in der diesem Beschluss zu Grunde liegenden Sache neuerlich durchzuführen.

§ 35. Auswahlkriterien

- (1) Die Auswahlentscheidung muss sich an den Anforderungen der künftigen Aufgabenerfüllung orientieren. Im Ausschreibungstext nicht genannte Aufnahmekriterien dürfen nicht berücksichtigt werden.
- (2) Personalentscheidungen sind schriftlich zu begründen. Insbesondere ist nachvollziehbar darzulegen, warum die ausgewählte Person die Anforderungen des Ausschreibungstextes am besten erfüllt.
- (3) Sind Frauen unterrepräsentiert und wurde keine Frau zur Besetzung vorgeschlagen, so hat das vorschlagsberechtigte Organ die Gründe für die Nichtberücksichtigung jeder Bewerberin im Einzelnen unter Bezugnahme auf die Kriterien des Ausschreibungstextes darzulegen.
- (4) Auf Karriereverzögerungen auf Grund der Betreuung von Kindern oder pflegebedürftigen Angehörigen ist bei der Auswahl Bedacht zu nehmen, um Bewerberinnen und Bewerber nicht zu benachteiligen.
- (5) Vergleichbare außeruniversitäre Karriereverläufe und dabei erworbene Qualifikationen sind angemessen zu berücksichtigen.
- (6) Hat der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen Grund zur Annahme, dass eine Personalentscheidung eine Bewerberin oder einen Bewerber mit besonderen Bedürfnissen (z.B. begünstigte Behinderte nach BEinstG) diskriminiert oder eine solche Bewerberin oder ein solcher Bewerber bei gleicher Qualifikation nicht ausgewählt wurde, ist die zuständige Behindertenvertrauensperson davon in Kenntnis zu setzen.

§ 36. Zusätzliche Bestimmungen für Berufungsverfahren

- (1) In Berufungsverfahren sind potenzielle, qualifizierte Bewerberinnen durch geeignete Maßnahmen zur Bewerbung zu motivieren. Der entsprechende Nachweis ist in den Akt aufzunehmen.
- (2) Werden im Berufungsverfahren gemäß § 98 Abs. 2 Satz 2 Universitätsgesetz 2002 auch Kandidatinnen oder Kandidaten einbezogen, die sich nicht beworben haben, ist der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen davon unverzüglich in Kenntnis zu setzen.
- (3) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen hat das Recht, zwei Vertreterinnen oder Vertreter zu Sitzungen der Berufungskommissionen zu entsenden. Diese haben das Recht, Anträge zu stellen, Sondervoten zu Protokoll zu geben sowie bestimmte Diskussionsbeiträge von Mitgliedern der Berufungskommission in das Protokoll aufnehmen zu lassen. Beide Vertreterinnen und Vertreter des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen sind fristgerecht zu jeder Sitzung der Berufungskommission zu laden. Unterbleibt die Ladung, hat die Berufungskommission in einer neuerlichen Sitzung unter ordnungsgemäßer Beiziehung des Arbeitskreises für Gleichbehandlungsfragen die Beratung und Beschlussfassung in der diesem Beschluss zu Grunde liegenden Sache neuerlich durchzuführen. Für die Wahrnehmung der Aufgaben des Arbeitskreises in den Sitzungen der Berufungskommissionen können auch geeignete Personen, die dem Arbeitskreis nicht angehören, nominiert werden.
- (4) Nachgewiesene Kompetenzen in Frauenförderung, Gender Mainstreaming und/oder Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung sowie Antidiskriminierung sind in die Auswahl positiv einzubeziehen.
- (5) Alle Bewerberinnen, die die gesetzlichen Voraussetzungen erfüllen und den Anforderungen des Ausschreibungstextes entsprechen, sind gem. § 98 Abs. 6 Universitätsgesetz 2002 nach begründeter Vorauswahl der Kommission gem. § 98 Abs. 5

Universitätsgesetz 2002 zu begutachten und auf Basis der Gutachten zu Präsentationen einzuladen.

(6) Bewerberinnen, die in gleichem Maße geeignet sind wie die bestgeeigneten Mitbewerber, sind vorrangig in den Berufungsvorschlag aufzunehmen.

(7) Enthält ein Vorschlag gemäß § 98 Abs. 7 Universitätsgesetz 2002 keine Frau, ist dies besonders zu begründen.

§ 37. Fast Tenure Track Professuren

(1) Es können höchstens 5 vH der Stellen für Professuren oder Äquivalente (vgl. Entwicklungsplan) je Leistungsvereinbarungsperiode im Schnellverfahren (Fast-Tenure-Track-Auswahlverfahren) für Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler mit Exzellenzförderung des ERC, des FWF (START, Wittgenstein) oder des WWTF (Vienna Research Groups for Young Investigators) vorgesehen/besetzt werden.

(2) §§ 32 - 35 Frauenförderungsplan sind bei der Durchführung des Fast-Tenure-Track Verfahrens nicht anwendbar.

(3) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist bei der Prüfung der Eignung einer Person für das Fast-Tenure-Track-Auswahlverfahren durch die Rektorin oder den Rektor und die Dekanin oder den Dekan beizuziehen.

(4) Der Frauenanteil der Personen, die auf Grund des Fast-Tenure-Track-Auswahlverfahrens neu eine Tenure-Track-Stelle angetreten haben, beträgt innerhalb der Periode des Entwicklungsplans (6 Jahre) mindestens 30 %.

(5) Sollte der Frauenanteil von 40 % der besetzten Stellen innerhalb der Periode des Entwicklungsplans nicht gehalten werden, kann der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen gegebenenfalls (§ 42 Abs. 8 Universitätsgesetz 2002) die Schiedskommission anrufen.

§ 38. Gutachterinnen und Gutachter

Bei der Bestellung von Gutachterinnen und Gutachtern in Habilitations-, Berufungs- und sonstigen der Feststellung einer Qualifikation dienenden Verfahren ist auf ein ausgewogenes Geschlechterverhältnis Bedacht zu nehmen. Diese sind zur Berücksichtigung der Spezifik weiblicher Lebensläufe anzuhalten.

§ 39. Berufungsverhandlungen

(1) Die Rektorin oder der Rektor hat bei der Auswahlentscheidung aus dem Besetzungsvorschlag der Berufungskommission Aspekte der Gleichstellung und Frauenförderung zu berücksichtigen.

(2) Die Rektorin oder der Rektor hat Berufungsverhandlungen so zu führen, dass Bewerberinnen gegenüber Bewerbern insbesondere hinsichtlich des Gehalts, sonstiger Geldleistungen oder der Ausstattung nicht benachteiligt werden.

(3) Wird einer Bewerberin eine Frist zur Annahme oder Ablehnung eines Rufes gesetzt, ist bei der Festlegung dieser Frist auf die konkrete Lebenssituation Rücksicht zu nehmen.

(4) Solange Frauen in den betroffenen Organisations- und Subeinheiten noch unterrepräsentiert sind, hat die Rektorin oder der Rektor den Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen über die Gründe des Scheiterns der Berufungsverhandlungen mit Bewerberinnen Auskunft zu erteilen.

(5) Das Rektorat hat dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen alljährlich über die Anzahl von Bewerberinnen, das Verhältnis von Bewerberinnen und Listenplätzen und das Geschlechterverhältnis der in diesem Jahr neu berufenen Professorinnen und Professoren pro Organisationseinheit Bericht zu erstatten.

§ 40. Maßnahmen gegen karrierehindernde Diskriminierungen

(1) Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen hat das Recht, Beschwerde an die Schiedskommission wegen Diskriminierung aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder der Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung zu erheben, wenn

1. die Dienstpflichten nicht so gestaltet werden, dass die jeweiligen Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter voraussichtlich die für ihre Laufbahn erforderlichen Qualifikationen zeitgerecht erwerben können oder auf Laufbahnunterbrechungen aufgrund von Betreuungspflichten keine Rücksicht genommen wird
2. in Eignungsabwägungen, Dienstbeschreibungen, Festlegungen der Dienstpflichten, Aufgabenzuweisungen, Beurteilungen und Zeugnissen diskriminierende oder karrierehemmende oder sich an einem diskriminierenden, rollenstereotypen Verständnis der Geschlechter orientierende Beurteilungskriterien einbezogen werden, welche zur Benachteiligung von weiblichen Beschäftigten oder zu einer Diskriminierung auf Grund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, der Religion oder der Weltanschauung, des Alters oder der sexuellen Orientierung führen
3. Frauen beim Zugang zu Aus- und Weiterbildungsmaßnahmen diskriminiert werden
4. Mitarbeiterinnen im Zusammenhang mit Weiterbildungsmaßnahmen während einer gesetzlich oder vertraglich vorgesehenen Abwesenheit vom Arbeitsplatz sowie Teilzeitbeschäftigte gegenüber Vollzeitbeschäftigten benachteiligt werden
5. bei Karrieregesprächen der Grundsatz der Nichtdiskriminierung aufgrund des Geschlechts, der ethnischen Zugehörigkeit, Religion und Weltanschauung, des Alters und der sexuellen Orientierung verletzt werden

(2) Nach Feststellung einer Diskriminierung durch die Schiedskommission ist das Rektorat verpflichtet, einen diskriminierungsfreien Zustand herzustellen.

§ 41. Universitäre Selbstverwaltung

(1) Im Rahmen der universitären Verwaltung ist in allen Gremien auf ein ausgewogenes Geschlechterverhältnis Bedacht zu nehmen. Frauen sind tunlichst in den Wahlvorschlag für den Vorsitz aufzunehmen. Dies gilt auch für Wahlvorschläge für monokratische Ämter.

(2) Vorschläge gemäß § 5 Abs. 1 und 2 sowie gemäß § 10 Abs. 3 Organisationsplan sollen, soweit möglich, zumindest eine geeignete Kandidatin enthalten.

(3) Bei der Besetzung von Studienprogrammleiterinnen und Studienprogrammleitern sowie Leiterinnen und Leitern von Subeinheiten ist ein angemessener Frauenanteil anzustreben.

§ 42. Aus- und Weiterbildung für Führungskräfte zu Frauenförderung und Gender Mainstreaming

Führungskräfte sind ihren Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeitern bei der Einhaltung der Ziele der Frauenförderung, Gleichstellung und Antidiskriminierung ein Vorbild. Sie kennen die notwendigen rechtlichen Rahmenbedingungen bzw. eignen sich diese in angemessener Zeit an.

Kenntnisse im Bereich der Frauenförderung, des Gender Mainstreamings, der Gleichstellung, der Antidiskriminierung und des Mentorings sind bei der Auswahl von Führungskräften zu berücksichtigen.

Lehre

§ 43. Beteiligung an Lehre, Frauenquote

Bei Beauftragung mit Lehre ist nach Maßgabe des jeweiligen Personalstandes die 50%ige Frauenquote in allen Studienprogrammleitungen und Organisationseinheiten einzuhalten. Bei der Vergabe von Lehraufträgen ist auf ein ausgewogenes Geschlechterverhältnis Bedacht zu nehmen.

§ 44. Gastprofessuren und Gastvortragende

Bei Gastprofessuren und Gastvortragenden ist ein Frauenanteil von mindestens 50 % pro Organisationseinheit anzustreben.

§ 45. Begutachtung der Curricula in Bezug auf Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung

(1) Bei der Gestaltung der Curricula ist die Förderung von Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung als Forschungsbereich tunlichst zu berücksichtigen. Soweit fächerspezifisch sinnvoll, ist auf die Integration von Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung in den Pflicht- und Wahlfächern zu achten.

(2) Die Arbeitsgruppen zur Erlassung der Curricula haben dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen die Möglichkeit einzuräumen, ein Mitglied bzw. eine Expertin oder einen Experten des jeweiligen Fachgebiets mit beratender Stimme in die Arbeitsgruppe zu entsenden.

(3) Eine kontinuierliche und regelmäßige Erfassung der Berücksichtigung von Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung in der Lehre ist sicherzustellen.

Studierende

§ 46. Aufnahme- und Auswahlverfahren und sonstige Verfahren zur Zulassung zu Studien

Die Aufnahme- und Auswahlverfahren nach §§ 71 b-d Universitätsgesetz 2002 (Zugang zu besonders stark nachgefragten Studien) und sonstigen Verfahren zur Zulassung zu Studien sind so zu gestalten, dass sie zu keinerlei Diskriminierung insbesondere aufgrund des Geschlechts oder der sozialen Herkunft führen.

§ 47. Stipendien

(1) Es ist sicherzustellen, dass Stipendienangebote an Frauen herangetragen werden und diese zur Bewerbung aufgefordert werden. Die Universität Wien wirkt darauf hin, dass zusätzliche Stipendien für Frauen angeworben werden, dass Stipendien durch Erziehungsurlaub oder durch Beurlaubung aus familiären Gründen unterbrochen werden können und die Altersgrenze für Stipendien bei familiären Belastungen hinaufgesetzt wird.

(2) Bei der Vergabe von Stipendien sind Frauen bei gleicher Qualifikation zu bevorzugen.

(3) Anzustreben ist zumindest jener Anteil weiblicher Stipendiatinnen, der dem Anteil weiblicher Studierender entspricht.

§ 48. Erhöhung des Frauenanteils in Studienrichtungen, in denen Frauen unterrepräsentiert sind

(1) In Studienrichtungen, in denen der Anteil der Studienanfängerinnen oder Absolventinnen unter 50 % liegt, sind in Zusammenhang mit § 25 von der Studienprogrammleitung Strategien und konkrete Maßnahmen zur Erhöhung des Frauenanteils in diesen Studienrichtungen zu entwickeln.

(2) Solche Studienrichtungen sind mit dem Ziel der Frauenförderung unter anderem bei Präsentationen, auf Messen oder bei Informationsveranstaltungen an Schulen vorzustellen und zu bewerben.

§ 49. Unterstützung bei der Karriereplanung

(1) Mitarbeiterinnen ist die Teilnahme an karrierefördernden Veranstaltungen wissenschaftlichen oder berufsfördernden Inhalts nach Maßgabe der Erfordernisse des Dienstbetriebs zu ermöglichen. Im Rahmen der dienstlichen Erfordernisse sind dafür auch in begründeten Fällen Freistellungen zu gewähren. Die Entscheidung der oder des Vorgesetzten hat binnen einer angemessenen Frist zu erfolgen.

(2) Sind zur Teilnahme an Aus- und Weiterbildungsveranstaltungen Dienst- bzw. Arbeitszeitenänderungen notwendig, sind diese von den Vorgesetzten zu gewähren, soweit nicht zwingende dienstliche Interessen entgegenstehen.

(3) Im Rahmen des Weiterbildungsprogramms der Universität Wien haben Mitarbeiterinnen Anspruch auf spezielle Seminare zur Frauenförderung.

Beruflicher Aufstieg und Karriereplanung

§ 50. Förderung von Frauen des Allgemeinen Universitätspersonals

Die Universität fördert die Karriere von Frauen des allgemeinen Universitätspersonals durch:

1. Entwicklung, Umsetzung und begleitendes Monitoring von gendersensiblen Karrieremodellen für das allgemeine Universitätspersonal
2. Entwicklung von Aus- und Fortbildungsmaßnahmen (Qualifikationsprogrammen) im universitätsspezifischen Verwaltungsbereich (Personalentwicklung)
3. Gezielte Förderung der Teilnahme von Frauen an diesen Maßnahmen (Berücksichtigung familiärer Situation etc.)

4. Berücksichtigung der speziellen Arbeitsbedürfnisse von Frauen auch beim allgemeinen Personal (Familie, Schwangerschaft, Wiedereinstieg etc.) durch geeignete Arbeitszeitmodelle, alternative Arbeitsmethoden, wenn möglich und Wiedereinsteigerinnenprogramme.

§ 51. Geschlechterverhältnis bei Leitungsfunktionen

(1) Bei der Betrauung mit Leitungsfunktionen ist auf die Erreichung eines ausgewogenen Geschlechterverhältnisses zu achten.

(2) Bei Unterrepräsentation sind Bewerberinnen, die für die angestrebte höherwertige Verwendung (Funktion) bzw. Beförderung in gleichem Maße geeignet sind wie der bestgeeignete Mitbewerber, vorrangig zu berücksichtigen.

§ 52. Weiterbildungsmöglichkeiten

(1) Mitarbeiterinnen während einer gesetzlich oder vertraglich vorgesehenen Abwesenheit vom Arbeitsplatz und Teilzeitbeschäftigten werden die gleichen Fortbildungsmöglichkeiten geboten wie Vollzeitbeschäftigten.

(2) Wird dem Verlangen einer Mitarbeiterin auf Teilnahme an einer Fortbildungsveranstaltung nicht entsprochen, kann der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen eine schriftliche Begründung der Ablehnung anfordern. Im Fall des begründeten Verdachts einer Diskriminierung kann der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen eine Beschwerde bei der Schiedskommission erheben.

§ 53. Ausbildungsmaßnahmen für weibliche Nachwuchsführungskräfte

Frauen sind in Ausbildungsmaßnahmen für Führungskräfte und zukünftige Führungskräfte (High Potentials) so einzubeziehen, dass der Universität eine ausreichende Anzahl von Frauen zur Besetzung von Führungspositionen zur Verfügung steht.

§ 54. Förderung von Frauen in der Forschung

(1) Vorgesetzte haben geeignete Mitarbeiterinnen und Studentinnen zur Dissertation bzw. wissenschaftlichen Weiterentwicklung mit dem Ziel eine zur Berufungsfähigkeit führende Qualifikation zu erreichen, zu ermutigen und zu unterstützen. Solange habilitierte Frauen unterrepräsentiert sind, sind darüber hinaus Maßnahmen zu ergreifen, die dem entgegenwirken. Der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen ist über die gesetzten Maßnahmen zu informieren.

(2) Habilitation:

1. Für Frauen, welche kein Dienstverhältnis zur Universität Wien haben und die Stellung eines Habilitationsantrages an der Universität Wien beabsichtigen, ist auf deren Wunsch durch die Dekanin/den Dekan bzw. die Zentrumsleiterin/den Zentrumsleiter eine Professorin oder ein Professor zu bestellen, welche/r die Habilitationswerberin vor und während des Habilitationsverfahrens als Mentorin oder Mentor unterstützt.
2. Alle Dienstvorgesetzten haben darauf zu achten, dass auf Frauen kein Druck zur Unterlassung von Habilitationsanträgen oder deren Zurückziehung ausgeübt wird;

ebenso ist darauf zu achten, dass es wegen der (beabsichtigten) Einbringung eines Habilitationsantrages nicht zu Diskriminierungen oder Mobbing kommt.

3. Dienstpflichten sind so festzulegen, dass die Vereinbarkeit von familiären Betreuungspflichten und Erreichung der Habilitation möglich ist. Habilitandinnen können zu Forschungszwecken von der Anwesenheitspflicht entbunden werden.
 4. Das Rektorat hat mit Organisationseinheiten, in denen während der abgelaufenen Leistungsvereinbarungsperiode weniger als 50 % der Habilitationen von Frauen erreicht wurden, in den Zielvereinbarungen Maßnahmen zur Förderung von Habilitandinnen zu vereinbaren.
 5. Das Rektorat berichtet dem Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen nach jeder Leistungsvereinbarungsperiode über die zur Steigerung der Habilitationen von Frauen in den Organisationseinheiten ergriffenen Maßnahmen und deren Auswirkungen.
- (3) Das Rektorat fördert die Karrierechancen von Frauen, die eine wissenschaftlichen Weiterentwicklung mit dem Ziel eine zur Berufungsfähigkeit führende Qualifikation zu erreichen anstreben, durch spezielle Programme (Mentoring, Berufungstraining).

Inkrafttreten

§ 55. Tag des Inkrafttretens

Der Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplan der Universität Wien tritt mit dem auf die Kundmachung im Mitteilungsblatt der Universität Wien folgenden Tag in Kraft. Mit seinem Inkrafttreten tritt der bisherige Frauenförderungsplan der Universität Wien (Mitteilungsblatt der Universität Wien vom 20.12.2005, 10. Stück, Nr. 94) außer Kraft.

§ 56. Überprüfung des Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplans der Universität Wien

Vier Jahre nach Inkrafttreten des Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplans der Universität Wien überprüfen der Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen, das Rektorat und der Senat die Wirksamkeit des Frauenförderungs- und Gleichstellungsplans der Universität Wien.

Der Vorsitzende des Senates:

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HELLENIC FOUNDATION FOR EUROPEAN AND FOREIGN POLICY (ELIAMEP)

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TARGET } Taking a Reflexive approach
to Gender Equality for
institutional Transformation

HELLENIC FOUNDATION FOR EUROPEAN AND FOREIGN POLICY (ELIAMEP)

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Introduction

ELIAMEP highly values gender equality. Demonstrating its strong commitment to it, it adopted in 2019 a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) aiming to promote equality and to mainstream gender within the internal workings of our Institute. We are proud to be the first research and policy institute in Greece to have developed and to be implementing a customized GEP, when most research institutes and innovation and higher education institutions in Greece are only now starting this process. The impetus for developing a GEP was the participation of ELIAMEP in the TARGET project funded by the EU Horizon 2020. It is a structural intervention project aimed at building the capacity of research and academic organizations to mainstream gender in their internal structures and activities, and promoting organizational and cultural change¹. ELIAMEP seized this opportunity to formulate a gender equality policy at the organizational level. It also took action to promote GEPs and to transfer its newly acquired expertise in this area to the broader academic and research community in Greece.

The past few years have witnessed a growing realization around persistent gender disparities in research and academia in Greece. It has been accompanied by strong demands among a significant cross-section of the scientific and academic community to tackle these disparities. Customized GEPs have increasingly attracted attention and support as tools of organizational, structural and cultural change. They are promoted by the European Commission and already widely implemented in several EU countries (mostly in Western and Northern Europe), while less actively so in Southern and Eastern Europe. At the start of the TARGET project, the idea of an organization adopting a GEP was rather unknown in Greece. Subsequently, external developments since 2019 have elevated GEPs as key tools of organizational and gender change in research and academia, and sharply expanded broad interest in these.

Research institutes and universities in Greece are not required by law to adopt a GEP. Yet, legislation passed since 2019 indirectly rendered their development at the organizational level quasi-mandatory. Legislation to promote substantive equality between the sexes (substantive, and not only formal, equality, being explicitly endorsed in the Greek constitution since 2001) encourages universities and research organizations to integrate gender in their study programs and research content and to adopt GEPs². Furthermore, the development of GEPs has been defined as a central mission of the recently established Gender Equality Committees in Greek universities and research organizations (their establishment is required by law)³. These developments present a unique and timely opportunity for academic and research organizations to identify and redress gender inequalities and implicit bias in higher education and scientific research. Undoubtedly, the requirement of Horizon Europe (2021-2027) for all research centers and universities that compete for funding to have a GEP, is a powerful catalyst accelerating this process.

1 "Taking a reflexive approach to gender equality for institutional transformation" (TARGET). Project web-site at <https://www.gendertarget.eu/>

2 Law 4604/2019 on "Promoting substantive equality between the sexes and combatting gender-based violence".

3 Law 4589/19, which aims at the restructuring of some universities, includes an article stipulating the establishment of Committees for Gender Equality (CGE) in all Greek universities (, Article 33). It envisions such committees as consultative bodies to assist the university administration in its efforts to promote gender equality.

ELIAMEP is an internationally reputable research and policy institute in the fields of foreign policy, EU integration and European affairs. It has a relatively small-sized staff (38 in 2020), the vast majority with advanced post-graduate education, that is gender-balanced overall, albeit with significant variation in the different categories of employees and associates. From 2017 until now, developing a GEP at ELIAMEP took place through successive phases of a gender audit, designing the action plan, implementing its activities and monitoring the extent to which they promote general and specific goals. This report provides an overview of this process at ELIAMEP, the activities that have been carried out, and the main changes that took place. It draws on quantitative and qualitative data collected in the frame of monitoring their implementation. It also lays out a sustainability strategy for ELIAMEP's gender equality policy and its action plan beyond the end of the TARGET project.

1. Why a Gender Equality Plan? Main objectives

ELIAMEP adopted its first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in 2019, defining gender equality as a key goal of our organization with concrete actions to advance it in practice for the first time. The GEP seeks to effectuate a long-term process of organizational change. It seeks to embed a gender-sensitive culture in ELIAMEP's internal structures and functioning, and in the content of its re-search and policy work. By pursuing this initiative, ELIAMEP also aspires to generate interest in and diffuse information about the value of GEPs among its extended network of academics, re-searchers, and external associates.

The GEP was adopted on the basis of a Gender Equality Audit (hereby GEA or 'audit'), which we had conducted during the previous year. In order to determine the institutional and structural parameters of our foundation, the audit provided a detailed description of ELIAMEP's organizational characteristics, its structure, size, staff composition, decision-making bodies, and gender balance in its different bodies. Through a critical reading of the organization's core documents – the 1988 Presidential Decree that established ELIAMEP, the Foundation's Internal Rules of Operation (IRO), and its Guide on Research Ethics (GRE) – it also assessed the pre-existing level of commitment to and awareness of gender equality. While ELIAMEP firmly laid down the principles of equality and non-discrimination as fundamental values, its documents did not include an explicit commitment to gender equality. Its staff composition exhibited gender balance overall (with frequent fluctuations due to the temporary contract employment of most researchers), yet the presence of women in decision-making bodies (the Foundation's Board of Directors (BoD)) was small. The audit also found that, notwithstanding the high-quality research that its scientific staff conducts, there was limited recognition of the importance of incorporating gender as a dimension in research projects and proposals.

Based on the audit's findings, we defined the following main objectives for ELIAMEP's GEP: a) to institutionalize the Foundation's commitment to gender equality, b) to build its organizational capacity for mainstreaming gender equality, c) to promote gender balance in its research management and decision-making bodies, d) to integrate the gender dimension in research content, and e) to promote gender equality in Greek research institutes and academia. From 2019 until present (October 2021), a series of actions were planned and subsequently implemented to achieve these objectives. They pertained to the management of human resources, data collection, changes to internal documents of operation, training activities, and knowledge transfer and dissemination of GEP-related expertise to the broader research and academic community in Greece.

2. Designing and Approving a GEP

Our GEP was designed by the ELIAMEP team involved in the TARGET project, Dia Anagnostou (lead expert), Natalia Avlona (research fellow, until December 2020), Elizabeth Phocas (Gender Equality Officer), and Alexia Mitsikostas (Project Manager). Its development involved a continuous process of engagement with the staff and followed a reflexive methodology. Feedback from and discussions with staff members at every step of the process contributed to the formulation of broad objectives and the planned activities, as well as to periodic modifications. The GEP's implementation has incorporated a monitoring phase that allows us to assess progress towards achieving its goals on the basis of a logic model⁴: it defined a set of indicators, and the kind of data (or evidence) necessary to measure these indicators as “signs of progress” towards achieving the GEP's goals. Monitoring indicators are comprised of outputs (activities), outcomes (behavioral change), and impacts (cultural change). In order to assess progress on the basis of these indicators, we have collected both quantitative data (i.e., number of projects proposed or implemented with a gender dimension, number of researchers, etc.) and qualitative data (through questionnaires and interviews)⁵.

From the outset, the development of a GEP at ELIAMEP enjoyed the strong commitment of the top management that recognized its value and facilitated its preparation. They also provided continuous support throughout the process and acted as a critical nexus between the staff and the Board of Directors (BoD). In the course of conducting the audit and formulating the GEP, the TARGET team at ELIAMEP presented the project and its goals at a BoD meeting in December 2017. Many of them were not familiar with GEPs as tools used by various kinds of organizations to stimulate gender equality change.

The TARGET team at ELIAMEP also consulted informally with several members of the administrative and research staff in order to formulate the overall objectives of the GEP, to communicate the importance of developing a GEP, and to garner the support of colleagues. It also used e-mail communication to inform everyone about it at every step of the process. Several researchers and staff members also participated in the first two institutional workshops of TARGET, where they became familiar with the GEP as a tool. ELIAMEP's relatively small size and its well-connected staff and external collaborators made it possible to reach out, spread the information to the vast majority of them, and stimulate awareness-raising.

From the outset, we established a Community of Practice (CoP), in line with the methodology followed in the TARGET project. It is composed primarily of ELIAMEP staff and members of its BoD, but also of external academics and researchers, who had strong awareness and motivation around gender issues – approximately 12 people in total. Even though the CoP never met as a group, largely due to the difficulty of finding suitable dates for regular meetings, and in the absence of any specific common task, it still provided inspiration, assistance and sharing of experience. From the beginning of the process, the ELIAMEP team liaised with the Greek Association of University Women (ELEGYP), whose members provided

⁴ A monitoring and evaluation plan is a document that helps to track and assess the results of the interventions throughout the implementation of the GEP.

⁵ In order to assess behavioral and cultural change (i.e. change in gender awareness), we collected qualitative data. In the first place, we developed in 2020 a questionnaire for ELIAMEP's research and administrative staff, in order to assess the impact of the activities that we implemented in the frame of the GEP. In addition, in 2021 we also conducted 11 interviews with staff, management and BoD members to understand the extent to which the GEP stimulated greater gender awareness and cultural change.

support and helped diffuse information about the TARGET project and GEPs to the larger academic community in Greece. The team regularly interacted with CoP members from outside ELIAMEP in the frame of other collaborative activities, like teaching at the university.

Many of the CoP members though, who were ELIAMEP researchers, gathered together with other staff members in regular monthly meetings that were well-attended. These meetings turned out to be a very important and continuous forum in which the ELIAMEP team of TARGET communicated the goals of the GEP and updated everyone about its implementation and progress. The presentations that were periodically given often stimulated further discussion among researchers and staff about issues such as the use of gender-neutral language and how to integrate gender in the research content, among others. They also provided an occasion and context for expressing disagreements and raising new issues. Updating the ELIAMEP staff and having discussions about the GEP at these meetings has been useful and very productive. New ideas and suggestions have been generated by researchers from other areas and programs. Members of the CoP from within ELIAMEP who were present at the meetings engaged in these discussions, in very supportive ways, highlighting the significance of the GEP and endorsing its goals and activities.

A draft of ELIAMEP's GEP was prepared in mid-2018 and it was circulated via e-mail to all ELIAMEP staff and its management. A couple of staff members sent remarks and feedback that were taken into account during its revision. One of the main issues discussed with staff members and with the Foundation's management was the most appropriate and effective way to improve gender balance in the BoD.

The GEP received a preliminary approval by the Director and the Deputy Director of ELIAMEP in November 2018, and in April 2019 it was presented for approval to the Board of Directors in one of its regular meetings. The arguments put forth in support of having a GEP were the following: a) ELIAMEP would utilize an important 'soft' policy tool that the European Commission's Research and Innovation (R&I) policy urges member states and research organizations to implement on grounds of promoting excellence; b) ELIAMEP would elaborate internally a gender equality policy, coming in line with a practice of other reputable research foundations active on EU affairs, which were already implementing such a plan; and c) by adopting a GEP, ELIAMEP would set the trend and encourage other research organizations and universities in Greece to emulate it, in the light of the 2019 national legislation mentioned earlier. The BoD gave its categorical endorsement to the GEP, acknowledging ELIAMEP's participation in the TARGET project as a significant opportunity to acquire the capacity to establish such a Plan and to pursue gender change. ELIAMEP's GEP was drafted in English and subsequently translated into Greek. A complete version of it has been distributed to all staff members of ELIAMEP.

3. Main Activities Implemented

Since its approval by the BoD in April 2019, the GEP has a formal status among ELIAMEP's documents of internal operation, alongside the Internal Rules of Operation (IRO), the Foundation's statute, and the Code of Research Ethics. An announcement and brief summary of the GEP was also uploaded on the Foundation's website, both in English (<https://www.eliamep.gr/en/ισότητα-των-φύλων/>) and in Greek (<https://www.eliamep.gr/ισότητα-των-φύλων/>). A full version of ELIAMEP's GEP can be made available upon request. For the first time, ELIAMEP's GEP formulates gender equality into an explicit goal of our foundation and contains several concrete actions to advance this goal in practice. The GEP seeks to effectuate a longer-term process of organizational change and to embed a gender-sensitive culture in ELIAMEP's internal functioning and in the content of its research and policy proposals. It also aspires to generate interest in, and diffuse information about, the value of GEPs among its extended network of external collaborators, academics and researchers. Several activities have been implemented since 2019 to accomplish the action plan's broad objectives, as succinctly described in this section.

3.1 Institutionalize the Foundation's commitment to gender equality

ELIAMEP made a number of revisions to its internal operating documents in order to explicitly formulate its commitment to gender equality, alongside already espoused principles of non-discrimination and equality more broadly. In particular, it introduced in its Internal Rules of Operation (IRO) a) an Equal Opportunity Principle regarding recruitment and evaluation of its personnel⁶ and b) an explicit commitment to promote gender balance among its staff and management.⁷ These revisions explicitly formulated gender equality and the balanced representation of the sexes as fundamental organizational values. Following these, a statement was included on ELIAMEP's website and the opportunities section that states its commitment to equality and non-discrimination in the hiring of personnel (see <https://www.eliamep.gr/en/opportunities/>). Furthermore, gender-neutral language was applied to ELIAMEP'S internal documents (the IRO, the Appendix I, II and the Code of Ethics), while gender-neutral language is now systematically used in all internal and external communication. The most important challenge in the use of gender-neutral language in Greek is how to change the standard of using the male grammatical gender as a universal term even when referring to women or to many persons of different sexes.

3.2 Build organizational capacity for mainstreaming gender equality

In order to build the organizational capacity to implement gender changes, in 2019 ELIAMEP designated a Gender Equality Officer (GEO), which is included in Article 3 of the IRO. The GEO is responsible for a) the implementation and monitoring of the GEP beyond the end of the TARGET project, b) overseeing the collection of sex-disaggregated data on

⁶ This principle states that "ELIAMEP is committed to equal opportunities in the evaluation and recruitment of its personnel, and it does not discriminate on the basis of gender, race or ethnic origin, religious and other convictions, sexual orientation, age, or disability."

⁷ The IRO includes the following statement: "ELIAMEP is committed to the promotion of Gender Equality and ensures that an overall Gender-balanced participation is achieved in the recruitment process as well as in the Top Management positions".

recruitment, promotion and re-tention according to the GEP, c) preparing a gender equality report on an annual basis, and d) for taking initiatives to redress any emerging disparities and to ensure that ELIAMEP consistently promotes gender equality and diversity in practice.

In addition, in 2020 ELIAMEP developed an internal procedure for recording sex-disaggregated data collection regarding its personnel, recruitment and promotion, research and policy activities, public events and interventions in the media. Systematic data collection (on an annual basis) allows us to assess and monitor gender balance among staff and across all activities, including the composition of research teams, as well as the extent to which a gender dimension is integrated in the grant proposals and research projects that are carried out at ELIAMEP. The data is presented and analyzed in the annual gender reports. Systematic collection of sex-disaggregated data does not only allow us to monitor progress towards achieving the gender equality objectives defined in our Action Plan, it is also a key qualitative characteristic of Gender Equality Plans that the European Commission's Horizon 2021-27 Program requires from all organizations that apply for funding⁸.

3.3 Promote gender balance in research management and decision-making bodies

Gender balance in research organizations is a key step – a necessary albeit not sufficient one – for ensuring research excellence and quality performance. ELIAMEP has a relatively small number of permanent full-time staff members and a large number of researchers who are affiliated with ELIAMEP on a project basis. Its administrative and research staff is highly educated, with the vast majority of them having advanced education. Notably, 36 out of its 38 employees have a post-graduate degree, and 23 of them hold a Ph.D degree. As regards the occupational structure, overall ELIAMEP has a gender balanced distribution among its staff, with women making up about 55% of staff members (administrative staff and researchers, see Annex I) in 2020. In addition, ELIAMEP has a wide circle of external advisors and collaborators who provide ad hoc expertise and special-ized advice on ELIAMEP's activities and public interventions.

However, unlike in the overall composition of staff and top management, women's pres-ence among the 13-member Board of Directors (BoD) remains small, despite the progress that was achieved. Following the explicit commitment to gender balance included in the Internal Rules of Operation and the growing discussion and awareness around the issue, in 2019-2020, the num-ber of women in the BoD slightly increased from 2 to 3. In 2022, the overall number of the mem-bers in the BoD will be raised from 13 to 15, and we anticipate this will be an opportunity for enhancing the gender balance too. Further improvements can be made in due course, when the term of some members ends and their positions become open for new members to be appointed. The process of reflexivity and awareness that was raised in the frame of the TARGET project significantly contributed to strengthening the determination of existing BoD members to further improve gender balance in the composition of its members. Therefore, it is anticipated that they will look for and appoint highly accomplished women in the place of those Board members whose term expires in the near future.

⁸ On Gender Equality Plans as an eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe, see the information provided by the European Commission at the following link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-citizens-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en#gender-equality-plans-as-an-eligibility-criterion-in-horizon-europe

Unlike in the overall composition of staff and top management, women's presence among the 15-member BoD remains small, despite the progress that was achieved. Following the explicit commitment to gender balance included in the IRO, and the growing discussion and awareness around the issue, in 2019-2020, the number of women in the BoD doubled from 2 to 4. As the overall number of members in the BoD was also raised from 13 to 15 during that period, the increase in the number of women did not drastically improve the balance. Further improvements can be made in due course, when the term of some members ends, and their position becomes open for new members to be appointed. The process of reflexivity and awareness that was raised in the frame of the TARGET project significantly contributed to strengthening the determination of existing BoD members to further improve gender balance in the composition of its members. Therefore, it is anticipated that they will look for and appoint highly accomplished women in the place of those Board members whose term will expire in the near future.

3.4 Integrate the gender dimension in research content

In the frame of implementing a GEP, ELIAMEP has sought to encourage its researchers to incorporate the gender dimension in the content of their research and in the proposals that they submit for funding. In 2020, ELIAMEP was involved in and implemented twenty-four research and action projects, most of them with funding from the European Commission (Horizon 2020 or other funding instruments). Gender is a distinctive or central theme in only 4 of the 24 projects implemented in 2020, while it is a peripheral or marginal theme in another 7 projects. This reflects an increasing integration of gender-related themes in the content of research carried out at ELIAMEP, in comparison to the past. There is still room for improvement, as the gender dimension is not incorporated or addressed in the remaining 13 projects.

In the past few years, with the TARGET project under way, we have observed an increased interest expressed by ELIAMEP researchers, including advanced scholars, to pursue gender-related themes in their projects and the proposals that they submit for funding. However, they feel that they lack the knowledge and conceptual-theoretical tools to take this step. Increasing interest in learning more about gender aspects and in formulating questions that take into account gender differences in research projects and proposals for funding, was also confirmed by the responses to a survey that we conducted in 2019 among ELIAMEP staff. In ELIAMEP's regular researchers' meetings, the idea was raised and discussed that the heads of the various programs (i.e. migration, foreign policy, Southeast Europe, etc.) integrate a gender aspect in the activities that they organize (with a speaker, a panel, or other). This would help researchers become familiar with gender issues in their area of study, while also enhancing gender balance in panels and conferences. This idea was well-received, with researchers viewing it as both possible and desirable.

In June 2020, a workshop on "Gender in research in social and political sciences" took place with the participation of 20 post-graduate students and young scholars from within and from outside ELIAMEP. Through the presentation of research papers and their discussion and feedback by experienced scholars, the workshop sought to motivate and train young scholars to address gender themes in Ph.D or post-doctoral research. To promote gender in research content, ELIAMEP also plans to hold thematic conferences or workshops to promote the incorporation of gender themes in different areas of research.

3.5 Promote gender equality in Greek research and academia

In order to promote gender equality in Greek research and academia, the ELIAMEP TARGET team engaged in networking with stakeholders outside of our Foundation. In particular, the team maintained regular contact with the Greek Association of University Women (ELEGYP) and with the Network of Gender Equality Committees of Greek universities. We presented ELIAMEP's experience in setting up a GEP and the TARGET project in several meetings and events organized by these bodies, as well as by other entities. External members who participate in the Community of Practice (CoP) were instrumental in the forging of ties with stakeholders in Greek research and academia. In order to facilitate the transfer of knowledge and the methodology regarding how to develop institutional GEPs to Greek research institutions and universities, the ELIAMEP TARGET team prepared a comprehensive manual with guidelines, based on the reflexive approach. As the first comprehensive practical guide on this topic in Greek, this manual provides a valuable tool to research and higher education institutions that are currently in the process of developing GEPs. The manual was widely distributed to all Greek universities and to many research institutes across Greece.

We further published two policy briefs (in Greek and in English) in 2019 to disseminate information and knowledge about GEPs to Greek researchers, faculty members, institutes and universities, and to encourage them to implement such action plans (see Annex II). In reference to the European Commission's R&I policy, the policy briefs strongly argue for the need to incorporate and mainstream gender in the higher education reform, advocate the development of gender equality plans, and draw attention to the implementation of the GEP at ELIAMEP. One policy brief also contains concrete policy proposals on how decision-makers can support the development of GEPs in research, innovation and higher education. These two policy briefs were distributed to a list of over 80 individuals who are academic staff and researchers in Greek universities, as well as to the members of the Community of Practice.

4. Main Changes to the Status Quo of Gender Equality at ELIAMEP

In the preceding sections we already provided an overview of the activities (outputs) that we implemented in the frame of the GEP, and we included references to some behavioural changes (outcomes) that were sparked by those activities. Since the GEP was adopted in 2019, we have assessed its implementation and results in three monitoring rounds so far. A first attempt was made through the distribution of a written questionnaire to ELIAMEP staff. It sought to assess a) whether the ELIAMEP staff were informed about the GEP and the relevant changes introduced in our internal organization, and b) the possible influence that the GEP had had on the staff's views and thinking about gender issues. The responses to that questionnaire were discussed in detail in the third monitoring report in 2020. They clearly showed that the vast majority of ELIAMEP staff were well-informed about the GEP and overwhelmingly positively predisposed to the actions carried out.

In this section, we turn our attention to the broader impact of GEP implementation in contributing to cultural change and enhanced gender awareness within our Foundation. We rely on qualitative data collected through 11 interviews with ELIAMEP staff, management and BoD members, which were conducted in 2021. All interviewees were familiar with the TARGET project and the changes that were introduced in the frame of implementing a GEP. They talked very positively about the fact that a project like TARGET was carried out and that it had sparked an ongoing discussion about gender-related issues at ELIAMEP. They also appreciated this as a knowledge-producing process even at ELIAMEP, which is widely described as an open, egalitarian, and merit-based workplace. What strikingly and clearly emerges from the interviews is the profound effect that the GEP implementation has had in raising awareness around gender issues among ELIAMEP's research and administrative staff and management.

For a start, a conscious effort is widely made to apply gender balance as a principle across all activities; this was not the case in the past, prior to the TARGET project. The interviewees discussed how they opt for gender balance in the composition of research teams. They do so as a matter of principle, regardless of whether they consider this as directly productive. Staff members and researchers expressed uncertainty and varying views as to whether women actually bring different qualities and ideas into a working team. While some insisted that it is the individual personality traits that matter, others highlighted how women bring distinct and indispensable qualities into teamwork, such as a more holistic approach to running projects, more forthcoming inter-personal communication, and the ability to successfully carry out different tasks (such views were expressed mostly by female respondents). The issue of how to balance between work and family life was raised but was not discussed, even as the covid-19 pandemic exacerbated relevant tensions for women in particular. The flexibility provided regarding work routines and times at ELIAMEP, as well as the supportive approach of the top management, makes working conditions particularly family-friendly.

The GEP has sparked broad interest among ELIAMEP staff and researchers to pursue gender mainstreaming, both in terms of improving women's participation where they are under-represented, but also in terms of thinking about how to integrate gender themes in research proposals and all other activities. ELIAMEP staff and researchers affirmed how they now consciously and systematically seek to extend more invitations to women to participate in the various events and

panels that are organized. It was noted that the latter is easier to do in some areas than others that have traditionally been more male-dominated, as for example in foreign policy and security studies, where, however gender balancing efforts are all the more imperative.

The issue of quotas was often raised as a possible means to redress women's under-representation in decision-making bodies (and generally in both structures and events). While not flatly rejecting it, many interviewees expressed reservations or disagreed with their use, particularly if quotas are applied in a way that disregards or sets aside merit-based criteria and individual qualifications. Gender balancing measures are widely considered desirable and in the right direction, but clearly insufficient in bringing about substantive change. Quotas and gender balancing measures without educating men about critical gender-related issues, will end up maintaining the same gender stereotypes about the division of labor. Some interviewees considered it especially important when the key decision-making body, the BoD, pursues its commitment to enhancing gender balance in practice. This is seen to have a strong significance symbolically and psychologically, both within and beyond ELIAMEP. Concern was expressed about the still small number of women in the BoD, as was the expectation that this will change in the next rounds of appointing new members.

The GEP's implementation (and that of the TARGET project) apparently have had a tremendous awareness-raising effect as regards the use of non-sexist and gender-neutral language. Nearly all interviewees brought it up and applauded the use of such language. At the same time, they expressed varying views and disagreements as to the changes that should be applied in a language like Greek that has grammatical genders (unlike English). Disagreements were voiced regarding the practice of applying the grammatical female gender to words that are of male gender (i.e. from the word *pritanis* (m), meaning university rector, the word of *pritanissa* is introduced for female). Not everyone agrees that the existing standard of using the male grammatical gender even when referring to women or mixed groups is objectionable and needs to be avoided. On the contrary, some think that in today's society, maintaining the standard male grammatical gender in written or oral speech does not (or at least no longer) reproduce assumptions that different professions, and the world as a whole, is solely occupied by men. Interviewees urged caution against extremist views and the tendency to politicize the issue of gender-neutral language. They also noted the need to take into account the context in which specific words or phrases are used.

The ELIAMEP staff has been instructed to use gender-neutral language in all internal and external communication, written or verbal, and to apply such language in all policy papers and series published by ELIAMEP. At present, a process of rethinking and revising the way in which gender-neutral language was applied in the internal documents at ELIAMEP has been under way. The approach of using two grammatical genders (male and female) for all nouns and adjectives (with slash marks) has made texts difficult to read. Overall, the use of non-sexist and gender-neutral language is an issue about which all interviewed staff members were aware and concerned. The lively discussion and sensitivity around it reflect a change that has occurred in the past few years at ELIAMEP. Interviewees acknowledged that repeat discussions around gender issues have critically stimulated this awareness and helped change the way people express themselves, including at ELIAMEP.

Last but not least, the GEP implementation stimulated a considerable thinking and reflection around implicit biases and

entrenched gender-based assumptions, which are strongly, even if imperceptibly, reflected in the language that we use. For example, one staff member wondered why women are preferred for certain positions, such as administrative jobs, over men, as well as how we tend to automatically link certain professions to a particular gender, like engineer, or nurse. Staff members (male and female) have begun to question their own instinctive views and the assumptions that they mechanically make, even about everyday routine tasks. Last but not least, most interviewees thought that sex-disaggregated data collection was crucial and highly significant both in capturing how gender relations evolve and in sparking ongoing debate and re-reflection, that renders GEP implementation sustainable.

5. Looking forward

The adoption and implementation of a GEP at ELIAMEP for the first time opened up space for systematically considering and discussing gender and equality issues within our organization. It has started a process for systematically reflecting on whether and how gender influences, and is in turn shaped by, our organization's structures, practices and research output. The process of adopting a GEP that was set in motion alongside the TARGET project over the past two years - and the relevant activities that have been undertaken - have substantially improved the status quo of gender equality at ELIAMEP. While it was virtually absent from our organization's structures, values and practices, gender is now recognized as an important dimension that must be taken into consideration in the content of our research activities, as well as in the decision-making and operation of ELIAMEP. The designation of a Gender Equality Officer (GEO), the systematic collection of sex-disaggregated data, the use of non-sexist and gender-neutral language, the mainstreaming of gender balancing principle in all activities and structures, and the increasing interest in integrating a gender dimension in the content of research, are all changes that would not have taken place without a GEP.

Above all, the process of developing and implementing a GEP has had profound effects in raising the gender awareness of ELIAMEP staff, researchers and management. Many confessed to considering more consciously and becoming more sensitive to the manifold ways in which gender can interfere, often imperceptibly, in our activities and relations, and the need to tackle any distinctions that perpetuate disadvantage in work life and in society at large. This enhanced awareness was acquired in the frame of applying the GEP. It also fed into its implementation and provides a fertile ground for its sustainability beyond the end of the TARGET project.

The sustainability will also be ensured through the presence of the GEO who has a position in the Foundation's top management. The GEO will regularly monitor the gender situation through the collection and review of sex-disaggregated data and draft a relevant report at the end of each year. ELIAMEP is already in a position to fulfil the new requirement in the Horizon Europe framework (2021-2027), for all applicant institutions to have a GEP in order to qualify for funding. This requirement no doubt injects a powerful motivation to sustain the efforts for gender-related change, for the next six years at least. Beyond the TARGET project, ELIAMEP will step up its work to transfer knowledge and methodological tools to the broader research and academic community through a series of training workshops that will take place in 2022-23. These will train staff and faculty of research organizations and universities in Greece on how to develop and implement GEPs, with funding obtained from the EEA/Norway grants.

Annex I: Quantitative indicators

The gender distribution in the occupational structure of ELIAMEP for 2020 is indicated in Table 1: women make up 55% of ELIAMEP's staff overall (permanent and temporary), 75% of the administrative staff, and 51% of the research staff. One of the three top management positions at ELIAMEP is held by a woman. In 2020, ELIAMEP also had 24 trainees, eleven of them male, and thirteen of them female, who completed traineeships of duration between two and four months each.

Table 1: Sex-disaggregated data regarding ELIAMEP staff in 2020

Permanent/temporary staff	Total number	Male	Female
Management	2	1	1
Administration	11	3	8
Research	25	13	12
TOTAL	38	17	21

Table 2: Sex-disaggregated data regarding ELIAMEP research staff in 2020

Research staff (contracted)	Total number	Male	Female
Senior Research Fellows	9	7	2
Research Fellows	14	5	9
Post-doctoral Fellows	2	1	1
TOTAL	25	13	12

Annex II: List of publications, workshops and presentations

A List of publications and articles in the press

1. Dia Anagnostou, Gender Equality Plans in Universities and Research Organizations – A Practical Guide, Athens: ELIAMEP, January 2021 (in Greek, 100 pages)
https://www.eliamep.gr/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/TARGET_DIGITAL_WEBSITE_USE.pdf
2. Dia Anagnostou and Natalia Avlona, “The European Union and gender equality in research and higher education: A view from Greece”, ELIAMEP Policy Paper, No. 28, September 2019.
<https://www.eliamep.gr/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/The-European-Union-and-gender-equality-in-research-and-higher-education-4.pdf>
3. Dia Anagnostou Dia, “Gender Equality in Higher Education Reform in Greece”, ELIAMEP Policy Paper, No. 29, November 2019 (in Greek).
<https://www.eliamep.gr/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Policy-Paper-No-30-Anagnostou.pdf>
4. Dia Anagnostou, “Gender inequalities are deeply rooted” [Oi emfyles anisotites einai vatheia rizomenes]. Interview in Athens Voice, 10 February 2021.
https://www.athensvoice.gr/greece/701492_ntia-anagnostoy-oi-emfyles-prokatalipseis-einai-vathia-rizomenes
5. Dia Anagnostou, “Gender equality and lessons learned” [Emfyles anisotites and lessons learned], Ta Nea, 16 June 2020.
<https://www.tanea.gr/print/2020/06/16/world/emfyles-anisotites-kai-didagmata/>
6. Dia Anagnostou, “Gender equality in the reform of higher education” [I isotita ton fylon sti metarithmisi gia tin anotati ekpedevsi], To Vima, 17 November 2019.
https://www.tovima.gr/printed_post/i-isotita-lfton-fylon-lfsti-metarrythmisi-gia-tin-anotati-ekpaideysi/
7. Dia Anagnostou, “The ‘glass ceiling’ of the new government” [H gialini orofi tis neas kynernisis] To Vima, 14 July 2019. <https://www.tovima.gr/2019/07/20/opinions/i-gyalini-orofi-tis-neas-kyvernisis/>
8. “Greek researchers are seeking for Equality” [Oi ellinides erevnitries anazitoun tin isotita]. It included a section on ELIAMEP’s implementation of its GEP. It was published in the newspaper Nea Selida, 23 June 2019.

B Workshops

- 1.** First institutional workshop was held by ELIAMEP in Athens on **“Promoting and Improving Equality in Research and Higher Education: Views from Greece”**, 21 February 2018 (20 participants).
- 2.** Second institutional workshop was held by ELIAMEP on **“Integrating gender perspective in social science research”**, on 2 July 2018. It was a training seminar conducted by two trainers from the Research Centre for Gender Equality (KETHI) in Greece, and it targeted both ELIAMEP’s and external researchers (22 participants).
- 3.** Third institutional workshop on **“Gender & Diversity Leadership in Research and Academia”**, ELIAMEP, Athens, 15 March 2019 (33 participants).
- 4.** Fourth institutional workshop on **“Integrating the Gender Dimension into Social Science Research”**, ELIAMEP, Athens, 2 June 2020.
- 5.** **“Understanding Sexual Harassment”**, on-line event organized by ELIAMEP and moderated by Dia Anagnostou, 26 January 2021, 16.00 – 17.30. (90 participants live, total views 2,324 through youtube and facebook)
- 6.** Thematic workshop on **“Integrating gender in studies on South-East Europe and Turkey”**, on-line event, 10 December 2021, 13.30-17.30.

C Presentations (by Dia Anagnostou)

1. **“The TARGET Project: Supporting Gender Equality Innovating Institutions in the Mediterranean”**, presented in the conference on “Implementing Gender Equality Plans in Research Organisations” which was organized by the General Secretariat for Gender Equality, Athens, 3 April 2019.
2. **“Designing a Gender Equality Plan: Lessons learned from TARGET Project”**, at the training event ‘Enhancing Gender Equality and the Gender Dimension in Research and Innovation’, Athens, National Documentation Centre, 20 June 2019.
3. **“Adopting a Gender Equality Plan at the Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy”**, at the conference “Women’s Organizations Meet-up for Education and Networking (WOMEN)”. It was organized by the NGO “Women on Top” with the support of the USA embassy in Athens. Athens, 22 October 2019.
4. Seminar with lecture by Dia Anagnostou on **“Wither Away or Mainstream Gender? European Union Gender Policy in Higher Education and Scientific Research”**, in the seminar series of ELIAMEP’s Program on Southeast Europe, 17 July 2020, 15:00 - 16:30. [40 participants]
5. **“Customized Gender Equality Plans in research organizations: the experience of ELIAMEP”**, presentation at the meeting of the Gender Equality Committees Network of Greek universities, 6 November 2020, 17.00 – 19.00 (70 participants).
6. Dia Anagnostou spoke about GEPs in Greece in the panel on **“New opportunities for equality and inclusion in the ERA”** at the conference “Deepening the ERA through Gender Equality Conference” organized by the GENDERACTION Project jointly with the Slovenian Presidency, 8 July 2021.
7. Dia Anagnostou spoke about **GEPs in Greek universities and research organizations** at the inauguration event of the Gender Equality Committee of the Foundation for Research and Technology. Athens, 14 September 2021, 13.00 – 15.00. [90 participants]

Annex III:

Gender Equality Plan

Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy (ELIAMEP)

ΕΛΙΑΜΕΠ
ΕΛΙΑΜΕΠ

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΟ ΙΔΡΥΜΑ ΕΥΡΩΠΑΪΚΗΣ & ΕΞΩΤΕΡΙΚΗΣ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΚΗΣ
HELLENIC FOUNDATION FOR EUROPEAN & FOREIGN POLICY

30+ χρόνια | years

Gender Equality Plan (GEP)

*Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy
(ELIAMEP)*

September 2019

TARGET

} Taking a Reflexive approach
to Gender Equality for
institutional Transformation

1. Background

The Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy (ELIAMEP) is a private, independent, non-profit institute that conducts policy-oriented research. Through a wide range of research, training and awareness raising activities, ELIAMEP advances knowledge as a basis of decision-making. It also promotes open dialogue based on the free exchange of ideas and reasoned argumentation. By providing authoritative information and substantiated policy recommendations, ELIAMEP seeks to contribute to the development of evidence-based responses to major policy challenges. Its areas of focus range from security and foreign policy, human rights, migration, European integration, political economy and social policy, among others. In fulfilling its mission, our Foundation is committed to excellence and meritocracy as driving forces in research performance and policy innovation. At the same time, ELIAMEP's operative documents explicitly and firmly lay down the principles of equality and non-discrimination as fundamental values.

In this backdrop of entrenched organizational values and principles embraced by ELIAMEP, the promotion of gender equality is an implicit, even if unspoken (as yet) counterpart. Paying attention to how gender as a category of social hierarchy and differentiation permeates and influences the phenomena that we study, advances our knowledge. At the same time, being aware of and seeking to eradicate persistent gender bias and the invisible, gendered assumptions in rules and practices, can positively transform research and higher education institutions. It is a key step in promoting and achieving merit-based performance in research and academic organizations. The pursuit of gender equality also encourages openness to ideas, inclusiveness and diversity of views. It enhances an organization's potential for innovation and excellence in generating and advancing knowledge and in supporting evidence-based policy-making.

This Action Plan for the first time formulates gender equality into an explicit goal of our organization and pledges to undertake a series of actions to promote it in practice. It follows the blueprint of a Gender Equality Plan (GEP), a soft policy tool championed by the European Union, to mainstream gender and implement equality measures in different organizational settings, including in research and academic institutions.

By implementing a set of concrete actions, this GEP initiates a longer-term process of organizational change. It is aimed at embedding a gender-sensitive culture in ELIAMEP's internal functioning, and in the approach and content of its research and policy proposals. ELIAMEP is a relatively small organization in terms of the number of administrative and scientific staff at any point in time. At the same time, it is closely connected with a larger circle of external associates, many of whom are academic researchers and university professors. Thus, a further goal of the present GEP is to inform this extended network of academics and researchers about the value of such Action Plans, and, hopefully, to solicit their support and motivation. Having a nodal position in an extended community of academic and researchers, ELIAMEP shall also take action to advocate and support, to the extent possible, the adoption of GEPs by other university and research organizations in Greece.

2. The Greek legal and policy context in research and higher education

Greece is one of the few EU countries, whose constitution recognizes a substantive, as opposed to a merely formal conception of equality. A substantive conception of equality was enshrined with the constitutional revision of 2001. It was based on the acknowledgment that structural barriers preventing women from taking advantage of

the equal rights and opportunities guaranteed in law, persisted. To tackle such barriers, as the Greek Constitution stipulates (Article 116, para. 2), positive measures may be necessary and essential for achieving substantive equality between the sexes. In view of this, Greece has a highly favorable constitutional frame for advancing around gender equality, in comparison to other EU Member States. Yet, social change is a difficult and slow process even when a sufficient frame of norms and legal statutes exists.

Despite such a favorable normative frame, national laws and policies for promoting gender equality in research and higher education institutions have so far been limited and weak. Greece lags behind in the adoption and implementation of specific measures to tackle persistent inequalities in academic and research organizations. To be sure, the *Greek Strategy for the European Research Area (ERA) – National Roadmap, 2016-2020* defines gender mainstreaming as one of its priorities. Law 4386/2016 on “Regulations on research and other provisions” recognizes the need to achieve greater gender balance in the composition of evaluation and selection committees, and of various advisory bodies in the field of research, technology and innovation. It also establishes a quota, according to which at least one third of the members of these advisory bodies and of the scientific councils of research institutes must be from one sex, “as long as the candidates have the necessary qualifications as required by each position” (Law 4386/2016, Art. 25). The implementation of these legal provisions, however, has been limited, due to the lack of enforcement, sustained political will, as well as of assessment and monitoring.

Recognizing their potential to bring about change within research and academic organizations, the *Greek Strategy for the ERA 2016-2020* urges public research bodies “to establish Gender Equality Plans and to include relevant provisions in their internal regulations and strategic plans”. Over the past few years, legislative initiatives to promote gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research, academia and in the private sector have not – at least not yet – been adopted as laws. A draft law on “Promoting substantive equality between the sexes and combatting gender-based violence” merely “encourages” universities and research organizations to integrate gender in their study programs and research content (Article 13 of the draft law that was made public for consultation in May 2018). Private and commercial enterprises are also encouraged to adopt equal opportunity policies, including specifically through the adoption of GEPs (Article 18 of same draft law). For those companies that will adopt such policies, a reward of an official distinction of the “Equality Badge” (*Sima Isotitas*) is foreseen.

The need and perhaps the political will to tackle gender inequalities in Greek universities has been mounting. A recent draft law aimed at the restructuring of some universities, includes an article that for the first time provides for the establishment of Committees for Gender Equality (CGE) in all Greek universities (Draft law “University of Thessaly, National Kapodistrian University of Athens, Agricultural University of Athens, and other provisions”, Article 27). It envisions such committees as consultative bodies to assist the university administration in its efforts to promote gender equality. One of the main responsibilities of the CGEs will be to develop Action Plans to promote substantive equality in the educational, research and administrative structures of higher education institutions. Once this draft bill becomes law, the implementation of CGEs in practice will no doubt be a serious challenge but also a key opportunity.

3. *A GEP for ELIAMEP: A Call to Action*

With the present GEP, ELIAMEP demonstrates the value it places on gender equality and inclusiveness, and assigns responsibility to its staff members to implement actions towards these goals. This Action Plan is based on a gender audit that was conducted at ELIAMEP. It is supported by the TARGET project, which is funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Program, and it has benefited from the advice of experts and experienced professionals. Covering the Foundation’s decision-making structures, human resource management, and research content, it formulates a set of objectives and concrete actions, and determines a time frame for achieving them. Until now (September 2018), there has not been, to our knowledge, any research organizations or academic institutions in Greece to have adopted an Action Plan for gender equality. By developing and adopting such a plan, ELIAMEP can play a standard setting role. It can show the way for other research and academic institutions of the public and non-state sector to follow suit.

4. Main objectives

Based on the gender audit of ELIAMEP, this Action Plan sets objectives in three areas of organizational structure and practice: human resource management, decision-making, and gender in research content.

2.1 Human Resource Management

ELIAMEP’s operating documents and organizational values endorse the broad principle of equality. There is also a balanced representation of men and women among the Foundation’s administrative and scientific staff. Yet, there is a low level of institutional awareness around gender. This Action Plan defines three goals: first, include gender mainstreaming in ELIAMEP’s operational documents; and secondly, to build the institutional capacity to improve data collection and identify gender-specific patterns and discrepancies in hiring, promotion and retention of administrative and scientific staff. These goals are to be achieved through a series of specific actions that are listed in the table below: designate a Gender Equality Officer (GEO) collect sex-disaggregated data related to recruitment, retention and promotion, formalize a commitment to gender equality in its recruitment rules, and a commitment to gender equality and non-discrimination in its rules of internal operation (IRO). The GEO will be responsible for implementing the GEP within the institution in cooperation with ELIAMEP’s top management.

TABLE 1

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS	RESPON SIBILIT Y	TARGET	TIMEFRA ME
BUILD ORGANIZATIO NAL CAPACITY TO MAINSTREAM GENDER EQUALITY	Designate a Gender Equality Officer (GEO) Training of the GEO	Director Deputy Director BD	Assign responsibility for implementing the GEP within the organization	March 2019

IDENTIFY GENDER-RELATED PATTERNS IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT	<p>Systematic collection and of sex disaggregated on recruitment, promotion and retention</p> <p>Review of sex-disaggregated data on an annual basis</p>	GEO Deputy Director	Regular monitoring and assessment of gender balance in recruitment, procedures, promotion and retention	January 2020 ongoing to December 2021
MAKE A FORMAL ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT TO GENDER EQUALITY	<p>Revise IRO (Item 4) to include a statement that “ELIAMEP treats all its employees on the basis of equality and without discrimination on the basis of race or ethnicity, religion or belief, disability, age, gender or sexual orientation</p>	Gender Equality Officer (GEO) ¹ BD Deputy Director	Define gender equality and non-discrimination as fundamental principles and goals in human resource management	May 2019
	<p>Revise IRO (Item 7) to include a statement that ELIAMEP seeks to maintain a balanced representation of men and women through its recruitment of administrative and scientific staff</p>	GEO Director Deputy Director BD	Formalize an institutional commitment to the balanced representation of sexes in recruitment process	May 2019
			Include a statement that ELIAMEP is an equal opportunities employer, in all documents related to recruitment	May 2019
	<p>Revise gender-biased language in ELIAMEP’s IRO (Item 6) and Ethics Code</p>	GEO Director Deputy Director BD	Apply gender-sensitive language in ELIAMEP’s internal operating documents	May 2019

2.2 Decision Making

ELIAMEP does not have formalized policies regarding the gender composition in decision-making bodies in place or in the positions of senior and top-level staff. Women make up the majority among the Foundation’s administrative staff (89%), and they

¹ Designating a Gender Equality Officer is one of the transversal objectives of the GEP (see Table 4).

comprise 40-50% of its scientific personnel. Their presence, however, drops to 15% in the 13-member Board of Directors, the main decision-making body, alongside the Foundation’s Director (who is a member of the BD) and the Deputy Director (the Director and the Deputy Director are ELIAMEP’s two top management positions). Every two years, half of the BD members are selected. They are elected by existing BD members for a four-year term, and they must come from across the following sectors: academia, the diplomatic corps, the military, the business sector, and journalism. There has been growing awareness about the lack of gender balance in its composition among the Foundation’s BD members, and the issue has been discussed. This GEP sets two goals: first, to promote gender balance in decision-making structures, and secondly, to maintain such a balance in the Foundation’s top management (Director and Deputy Director). To achieve these goals, actions include a) a formal commitment to improve the gender balance in the Foundation’s IRO, and b) setting of a voluntary target in the gender composition of the BD. In terms of the latter, a voluntary target of at least 25% of each sex² can be attained over the next four years and 34%³ over the next five years.

TABLE 2

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	RESPONSIBILITY	TARGET	TIMEFRAME
Gender balance in decision-making structures	Include a statement in ELIAMEP’s IRO that the Foundation seeks to achieve gender balance in its BoD	GEO Director Board of Directors	Set the goal of gender balance in ELIAMEP’s decision-making	January 2020 ongoing to December 2021
	Indicative target of 25% increase of female members in the BoD over the next three years, and 34% over a period of five years			December 2022 and December 2024
Gender balance in top management	Include a statement in ELIAMEP’s IRO that the Foundation seeks to achieve gender balance in its top management positions		Maintain gender balance in top management	Ongoing

² This is still less than thirty percent, namely, the minimum level for a “critical mass” of women, which is considered necessary to make a difference in scientific and management committees. See Gerlind Wallon, Sandra Bendiscioli, and Michele S. Garfinkel, *Exploring Quotas in Academia*, Robert Bosch Stiftung and EMBO, August 2015.

³ Thirty-six to thirty-eight percent of women in scientific and management boards in academic is the EU average. See Gerlind Wallon, Sandra Bendiscioli, and Michele S. Garfinkel, *Exploring Quotas in Academia*, p. 7.

2.3 Gender Dimension in Research Content

While ELIAMEP’s researchers design and implement projects on themes, in which a gender dimension is potentially relevant, only a small number of projects explicitly consider or address it. A gender perspective is central to studying and understanding migration, a main research strand of ELIAMEP. It is also highly relevant to several topics related to European integration, as well as to the themes of regional and international security, political institutions, economic development, and radicalization. Yet, it is estimated that about ten out of 100 projects implemented since 2010 include explicitly a gender dimension. While many are open to and interested in integrating gender in their research agenda and projects, they express a hesitation due to limited background and knowledge on how to do this. Thus, it is necessary to increase knowledge and awareness about the relevance, salience and value of integrating a gender dimension in the research projects and proposals that ELIAMEP’s researchers and collaborators design and implement. This can be pursued through capacity-building targeting ELIAMEP researchers, as well as young researchers and Ph.D students who engage in social science research outside of ELIAMEP in collaboration with its researchers and associates.⁴ Promoting the integration of gender in research content can also be pursued by explicitly including it as a theme in the description of the main research strands, on which our Foundation focuses.

Achieving the goal of integrating gender dimension in research content will be monitored on the basis of the following indicators: a) number of researchers having received training in capacity building workshops, and b) number of projects implemented and project proposals submitted by ELIAMEP that include a gender dimension.

TABLE 3

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBILITY	TARGET	TIMEFRAME
INTEGRATION OF THE GENDER DIMENSION IN RESEARCH CONTENT	Training workshops targeting ELIAMEP researchers and young researchers	Researchers Community of Practice	Build the capacity of researchers on how to integrate gender in their research	June 2018 ongoing to December 2021
	Reformulate research themes in ELIAMEP’s website page and other communication documents	GEO Researchers Website officer	Include gender as a cross-cutting theme in ELIAMEP’s research strands	December 2019

⁴ ELIAMEP does not have PhD students, but its senior research fellows and research associates, many of whom are faculty members in Greek universities supervise PhD students.

	Collect data on research projects and proposals that incorporate the dimension of gender	GEO Researchers	Promote gender in research content	January 2019 ongoing
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5. Transversal Measures

In order to promote gender mainstreaming in research and academia, ELIAMEP shall pursue a number of transversal measures that have a twin objective: first, to build institutional capacity and establish a system of data collection within ELIAMEP; and secondly, to diffuse awareness about gender equality in other research institutes and universities in Greece. It is a particularly propitious time to do so, as ELIAMEP's management is intent on instituting a process of systematic data collection more broadly, which it considers important, not least for purposes of record keeping. In order to mainstream gender in a sustainable manner, a Gender Equality Officer (GEO) will be designated, with responsibility of overseeing and monitoring actions, initiatives and progress aimed at promoting gender equality within the organization (see section 2.1 on human resource management). The GEO will also be responsible for regularly collecting sex-disaggregated data related to recruitment, promotion, and retention.

As ELIAMEP is the only research institute in Greece that has adopted a GEP, we consider the dissemination of this experience as highly relevant and potentially impactful in inspiring other institutes and universities in Greece to do so. To this end, a series of actions are planned to communicate the importance of adopting a GEP, and sharing our experience of this process; and to network with university professors and researchers in order to discuss and exchange experiences and good practices, as well as to create an extended Community of Support and Practice (CoSP). In pursuing the latter, ELIAMEP can utilize its extended network of contacts and research associates in different universities, research institutes, and funding organizations in Greece. Indicators of the extent to which this goal is attained are: a) number of academics and researchers participating in the workshops to disseminate knowledge and share experiences in the adoption of GEPs, b) number of academics and researchers forming an extended Community of Support and Practice (CoSP).

TABLE 4

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	RESPONSIBILITY	TARGET	TIMEFRAME
PROMOTE GENDER EQUALITY IN GREEK RESEARCH AND ACADEMIA	Workshops and training events with university academics and administrative staff	GEO Deputy Director Director	Disseminate knowledge of and share experience in adopting the GEP to research organizations and universities in Greece	January 2019 to April 2021
	Workshops and other events to train young	GEO Deputy Director	Increase gender	January 2019

	researchers on leadership issues and gender	Researchers	awareness of, and empower young researchers to advance in academia	ongoing
	Establishment of an extended Community of Support and Practice (CoSP)	GEO Deputy Director	Create and maintain a network of academics and researchers outside of ELIAMEP who are active in gender equality issues	January 2019 ongoing

6. Monitoring indicators

In order to monitor and assess progress with the implementation of this Action Plan, ELIAMEP will develop tailored process and outcome indicators (both quantitative and qualitative) to measure the effectiveness and impact of the planned actions. For some of the objectives of this GEP, such as raising awareness, qualitative indicators must be developed. For other objectives, such as integrating gender in research, indicators have already been suggested. Responsibility for monitoring progress on the basis of specific indicators is assigned to the GEO. The CoP will have a role in creating a favourable environment for the effective implementation of the GEP actions, through regular meetings to discuss progress and to identify any problems arising.

TARGET } Taking a Reflexive approach to Gender Equality for institutional Transformation

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The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

EQUALITY PLAN FOR 2022–2023

The goals for equality and non-discrimination in our university community are based on current legislation on equality as well as JYU's strategy and its development programmes. We are a multicultural and international working community that values and inspires individuals.

The University conducts a range of surveys, from the staff survey and the teaching, research and career survey for teaching staff to the teaching, learning and studying survey for students. These surveys include questions related to equality and are used to monitor the development of the state of equality. The state of equality is addressed in an annual report to the University Board.

University management has the responsibility for implementing the planned actions. The Rector approves the Equality Plan.

As an equal and bias-free place for working and studying, JYU supports the development and success of the members of the university community. The University ensures the availability, accessibility and quality of guidance and teaching. By mainstreaming equality issues, we develop the structures and practices of administration, teaching and research so that equality impacts are included in the preparation and implementation of decisions. Increasing openness in decision-making and related preparation is an important cornerstone for the development of equality and non-discrimination.

We behave appropriately and are respectful and supportive in challenging situations. We do not tolerate inappropriate treatment, harassment, discrimination or bullying.

VALUES

OPENNESS

TRUST

QUALITY

INTEGRITY

JYVÄSKYLÄN YLIOPISTO

JYUnity. We are a close-knit, open multidisciplinary community.

JYUnique. We focus on solving the problems of tomorrow.

JYU. Since 1863.

THE STATE OF EQUALITY

Statistics about JYU staff and students

Our university community is diverse and multicultural: the community consists of students, full-time staff members, employees working on an hourly basis in teaching or in other duties as well as researchers and doctoral students who conduct grant research. The community also comprises interns, persons performing their non-military service, and visiting staff and students.

The state of equality is addressed in an annual report to the University management. Earlier the number of employees was reported in accordance with the situation on 31 December. From 2020, the amount of staff has been reported as person-years. The staff statistics of this document are based on the person-years of employees with monthly salaries in 2020. The data is collected from the staff data system.

The total number of person-years is 2,482, of which the percentage of women is 57% and men 43%. In total, 52% of the employees have a permanent employment relationship and 95% are full-time employees. International staff's share of person-years is 12% (286 person-years) and they represent 64 nationalities. The average age of the staff is 41.1 years; 41.1 for women and 41.3 for men. The largest age group is 40- to 49-year-olds (28% of person-years) and the next largest age groups are 30 to 39 (26%) and 50 to 59 (22%). The percentage of females on the person-years of teaching staff is 56%, research staff 50%, and other staff 65%. The percentage of women in the person-years of professors is 35% and assistant/associate professors 47%.

The University of Jyväskylä has 14,052 degree students, of whom 4% are international students (situation on 20 September 2021). The number of new bachelor's and master's degree students admitted in autumn 2021 was 2,514, of whom 64.6% were female. Of new students, men were in the majority only in the field of information and communication technologies (69% in 2021 according to the classification of fields of study, level 2). At the level of degree programmes, men were in the majority, for example, in the degree programmes of physics and mathematics and statistics in the field of natural sciences as well as in economics in the field of social sciences. In 2020, the shares of degrees completed by women are as follows: bachelor's degree 61%, master's degree 68%, doctoral degree 56% (data sources: Vipunen and the JYU data warehouse).

The majority of teaching and research staff are on job requirement levels 5 and 6 and have a personal performance percentage between 6% and 31%. The majority of other staff are on job requirement levels 5–9 and have a personal performance percentage between 19% and 42%. A salary survey will be conducted at the beginning of 2022, after which the data on the placement of men and women in the salary structure will be appended to the Equality Plan.

Equality in the survey and evaluation results

Based on the results of staff surveys, the state of equality has improved from 2017 to 2021.

Statement in the wellbeing at work survey	2017	2019	2021
We discuss difficult matters and we also work them out	3	3.3	3.4
Equality is achieved in our unit	3.6	3.7	3.9
My supervisor is impartial and fair	4	4.1	4.2
My supervisor takes into consideration that people are different	3.9	4.0	4.1
Have you experienced harassment, bullying or other inappropriate behaviour in the past year? (2021)			No 89%
I have not experienced harassment, bullying or other inappropriate behaviour in the past year (2017 and 2019)	4.3	4.3	
I have the opportunity to advance in my career laterally (more varied tasks) or vertically (more demanding tasks), if I want	2.9	3.2	3.2

According to the teaching, research and career survey (2017), women in teaching and research find that gender influences the division of labour, salary and career development more often than they do in other tasks. Career possibilities are diminished most if the first language is something other than Finnish as well as in the case of disability and other health-related restrictions.

Based on the teaching, learning and studying survey for students (2017), gender equality seems to be well-realised among students. According to the survey, studying was hampered especially by the indoor air problems of buildings, students' mental health problems and factors that hindered barrier-free moving. Disability and other health-related challenges have the biggest influence on the equality of study opportunities.

Material from the Finnish Bachelor's Graduate Survey has been taken into account up to the responses of autumn 2021. The overall impression based on open answers is similar to the student survey of 2017. The numerical answers suggest that, based on an exhaustion indicator consisting of nine statements, the exhaustion risk of female students is greater than the exhaustion risk of male students across disciplines, and the lengthened COVID-19 pandemic seems to have increased the difference. Across disciplines, female respondents also agreed less than males did with the statement that they feel well at the University.

When developing the diversity of the University, the following aspects related to the members of the community should be acknowledged: age, nationality, gender, language, disability and state of health as well as other person-related reasons.

The actions of two previous equality plan periods (2016–2021) have been implemented.

As an education provider, the Teacher Training School prepared its own equality plan, and equality audit measures were completed during 2018. By monitoring the realisation of equality in international mobility, JYU supported the international mobility opportunities of disabled students and the observation of recommendations. In addition, the University promoted the development of annual monitoring of equality issues as well as the observation of harassment and discrimination cases.

The equality and non-discrimination process based on the University's strategy was introduced with a participatory approach to engage JYU staff and students. A salary equality survey was implemented. JYU's good practices for the working community were defined and related house rules were introduced. Instructions related to irresponsible behaviour at work were created and introduced by the beginning of 2022.

GOALS AND ACTIONS

The University's Equality Committee recommends paying attention to the following goals and actions in all JYU activities.

Multimodal work and study environment and operating culture: Goals	
Leadership	The University adheres to a non-discriminating leadership culture. The University promotes the equality and non-discrimination of employees and students from different language and cultural groups, for example, when appointing members for committees. The expertise and special know-how of different age groups are valued equally at the University, and professional development is supported in all phases of work and study careers.
Recruitment and career development	JYU's career development model is transparent and based on clearly defined recruitment practices and job opportunities. International staff feel they are part of the university community and have equal opportunities to apply for various positions at JYU. The University follows open and transparent recruitment based on merits (HRS4R - OTM-R).
Orientation and competence development	As an equal and bias-free place for working and studying, JYU supports the development and success of the members of the university community. The University's current and future domestic and international staff and students integrate into the University and commit to the common goals of our community. Orientation is developed and a uniform employee experience is taken into account.
Work and study conditions	The whole community fosters behaviour that is in compliance with the University's values. The community behaves and communicates appropriately and politely. The membership of the university community is equal and non-discriminatory for staff and students. Diversity is considered a strength and the University is able to benefit from it. JYU acknowledges the diversity of genders in its surveys, systems and statistics.
Balance of work/studying and free time	JYU helps students and staff to combine studying and work with family life and aims at offering everyone equal opportunities for parenthood and taking care of older family members and next of kin. Especially men are encouraged to use their legal right to family leaves and look after a sick child at home.
Multimodal work and study environment and operating culture: Actions	
A functional and caring community	JYU house rules for good practices in the work community. Supervisors lead the processing of the house rules of good practices (JYU at Work) and for good leadership (JYULead) in the work community. Defining and introducing the principles of safe social space for the whole community.
A considerate and supportive community	Developing working methods for harmonising work/studying and family life, promoting the fulfilment of equal parenthood. Operating methods in compliance with the barrier-free and accessibility principles. Ensuring the accessibility of information systems and the healthiness of facilities => the Sustainable and Responsible JYU Development Group
Multicultural community	Developing a working culture for multilingual communication, sufficient skills in Finnish and the clarity of language. Internationalisation at home: equal consideration of members of the international university community (staff, grant researchers, students) in a multicultural community. Equal student wellbeing services for all (the Student Life concept).
Equality of the working environment	Monitoring the salary equality survey.

GOALS AND ACTIONS

Education: Goals	
Student admission, study guidance and counselling	The diversity of students is considered in student marketing and opportunities are expressed in an equal manner. Students are encouraged to select lines of studies and careers open-mindedly. Admission criteria do not favour or discriminate. Applicants with various cultural backgrounds have equal opportunities to succeed, with special attention given to the language skill requirements in studies. Students have equal rights to receive sufficient guidance and counselling.
Studying	Curriculum development, selection of teaching material, teaching, and assessment of completed studies are performed in an equal and non-discriminatory manner. The relationship of staff and students is based on mutual respect, which must not be weakened by either the teacher's or student's gender, gender identity or gender expression. The selection of representatives for administrative bodies and the preparation of decisions promote equality and non-discrimination and take into account the diversity of students. Any results from surveys the Student Union conducts among its members about equality, non-discrimination and possible related problems are taken into account in the promotion of equality.
Doctoral studies	Students are encouraged to apply for doctoral studies equally regardless of their gender or gender expression, ethnic background, nationality or native language. Equal treatment of doctoral students is developed.
Education: Actions	
Student admission	The diversity of students is acknowledged in the development of student admission. Our student admission is fair and appropriate.
Equal guidance and counselling	The availability of guidance and counselling is ensured in different phases of studies, with special attention on uniform individual arrangements regardless of the department.
Flexible pedagogy	When possible, individual needs and diverse life situations are acknowledged in the development of alternative and varied modes of completion.
Diversity of students	Developing communication and contents that acknowledge the diversity of students. Developing the activities of the Student Life concept.
Pedagogy and valuing of teachers	The continuous development of teaching skills is supported; the use of varying teaching methods is promoted and resourced.
Student representation	Student representation in the University's administrative bodies is ensured, with special attention given to the representation of international students in the working groups.
Research: Goals	
Researcher's career progress	The distribution of duties and workload is reviewed to enable career progress.
Grant researchers	Developing the status of grant researchers and ensuring the use of researcher agreements.
Research: Actions	
Researcher's career progress	The distribution of researcher's workload is monitored annually on each career level.
Grant researchers	JYU has a development group for staff without an employment relationship with the University. This "Capable, Creative and Healthy University Community" development group prepares common practices for the whole staff group. Researcher contract data are collected at departments annually, and it is estimated how many of the grant researchers have not made a researcher agreement.

Promoting appropriate behaviour in our community

Our university community does not tolerate inappropriate behaviour, bullying or sexual harassment. We intervene in problem situations and resolve them.

The University has principles (house rules) for appropriate behaviour as well as guidelines for intervening and preventing inappropriate treatment and harassment at the University.

The University has guidelines for the staff and students for handling serious harassment situations. Supervisors are responsible for observing and taking care of the state of wellbeing in the work community as well as intervening in and sorting out problematic situations. The University has an equality contact person.

New guidelines concerning the operating model for responsible conduct at work and serious occupational health and safety issues are available in Uno (1/2022)

[Appropriate conduct in work community](#)

Instructions for students

[Prevention of bullying and harassment among students](#)

Accessible, barrier-free University

[Accessibility and reachability](#) refer to the implementation of a physical, psychological, social and digital environment where each individual can, regardless of personal qualities, operate on an equal basis. Accessibility concerns all members of the JYU community, and is of special importance to those with a disability or learning difficulty, as well as to persons approaching retirement and members of cultural or linguistic minorities. The decision on the accessibility of education at the University of Jyväskylä includes principles and responsibilities for implementing accessible environments and practices as well as necessary individual arrangements. Actions and monitoring are the responsibility of the Sustainable and Responsible JYU development group.

ORGANISATION OF EQUALITY WORK

Responsibility for the implementation of equality belongs to the University management, unit leaders, supervisors and each member of the university community.

The purpose of the University's [Equality Committee](#) is to

- promote the goals of the Non-Discrimination Act and the Act on Equality Between Women and Men as well as to monitor the development of equality at the University
- influence the university community to strengthen positive attitudes and opinions towards equality at the University
- draft a proposal for the Equality Plan
- report on the University's Equality Plan to the Capable, Creative and Healthy University Community development group.

In August–November 2021, the Equality Committee has prepared an update of the Equality Plan for 2022–2023. For 2019–2021, the plan has been constructed within the framework of the University's strategy and the Act on Equality Between Women and Men so that the members of the university community participated extensively in the preparation work. Preparation work in autumn 2021 focused on updating the existing plan. The next equality plan preparation process, which is to engage the university community extensively, will be implemented in 2023. The process will also involve an assessment of the goals as well as the meters for indicating the realisation of the goals. University management has the responsibility for implementing the planned actions. The Rector approves the Equality Plan.

Impact and communication

The members of the university community will be informed of the Equality Plan via the University's communications channels, and they will be engaged in the implementation of related actions. Supervisors will get induction and training concerning the content of the plan. The effectiveness of the plan is monitored as part of the Equality Committee's work and the implementation of the University's strategy.

Regulations, concepts and statistics

Regulations, concepts and statistics related to equality and non-discrimination are available on our University's [equality website](#).

Piano di
uguaglianza
di genere
2022/2024

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Sezione I

I.I Il Piano di uguaglianza di genere e il coordinamento con gli altri documenti di programmazione della Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna

L'adozione del Piano di uguaglianza di genere (di seguito GEP¹) si colloca all'interno della strategia europea 2020-2025 per l'uguaglianza di genere ed è stata introdotta dalla Commissione Europea per promuovere l'uguaglianza di genere nella ricerca e nell'innovazione. Proprio per rafforzare l'impegno strategico e nel contempo ribadire la necessità di una continua integrazione della dimensione di genere nelle politiche e nei programmi dell'Unione Europea, tale misura costituisce un requisito di accesso ai finanziamenti del Programma Horizon Europe (2021-2027) per tutti gli enti di ricerca e gli Istituti di Istruzione Superiore.

Questa scelta della Commissione appare assolutamente coerente con le finalità della Scuola, che è pienamente consapevole della funzione formativa propria di tutte le istituzioni universitarie, pubbliche in particolare, e della speciale funzione sociale assegnata ad una istituzione universitaria che seleziona i propri allievi e le proprie allieve sulla base del merito. La Scuola si fa interprete dei valori costituzionali che sono alla base della ricerca scientifica, dell'insegnamento e di tutte le altre attività che si realizzano in ambito universitario, ed informa ad essi il suo operato per favorire l'eccellenza e la creazione di un ambiente di studio e lavoro caratterizzato dalla correttezza, dal confronto e dalla libertà.

Il GEP della Scuola è redatto nel rispetto delle Linee guida europee con riferimento sia ai requisiti procedurali sia ai contenuti che deve incorporare.² Inoltre esso si coordina con la normativa esistente nella realtà giuridica italiana, collegandosi al ciclo di programmazione di Ateneo e ad altri strumenti politici e operativi, quali il Piano delle Azioni Positive (PAP) e il Bilancio di Genere adottati dalla Scuola.

Il GEP ha lo scopo di definire la strategia per l'uguaglianza di genere, integrando tale prospettiva nella programmazione strategica della Scuola. In questo senso, il documento si pone in continuità con il Piano strategico pluriennale 2017-2020, che si proponeva di ridurre progressivamente il gender gap nel corpo docente e negli organi di governo della Scuola (obiettivo 10) attraverso alcune azioni riferite alla composizione delle commissioni,

¹ Acronimo di "Gender Equality Plan".

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans, 2021.

alle chiamate dirette e per chiara fama e alla conciliazione tra vita lavorativa e vita privata. Queste indicazioni sono state riprese nel Piano di orientamento strategico 2019-2025, nonché nel documento programmatico per il triennio 2020-2022. Il GEP contribuisce all'attuazione di questo scopo con la previsione di un programma strutturato di azioni per il triennio 2022-2024. Tali azioni costituiscono lo sviluppo e la razionalizzazione di policies e iniziative già praticate presso la Scuola. Una volta a regime, il GEP dovrà costituire parte integrante del futuro Piano strategico.

Altresì, il GEP si coordina con il Piano delle Azioni Positive (PAP) e, più in generale, con le attività intraprese dal Comitato Unico di Garanzia della Scuola (CUG) e in particolare con quelle che interessano la dimensione di genere.

Infine, il GEP attinge e informa il Bilancio di Genere: da una parte, viene predisposto a valle dell'analisi operata attraverso questo strumento che identifica le aree e i contesti in cui il gender gap è più evidente e richiede di adottare misure specifiche per contrastarlo; dall'altra parte, il GEP serve anche a predisporre azioni rivolte alla raccolta di dati aggiuntivi, non evidenziati nella prima edizione del Bilancio di Genere, in vista dell'adozione di politiche mirate a speciali bisogni della Scuola. La raccolta di informazioni a livello granulare è al tempo stesso una delle attività richieste per l'attuazione del GEP e un'azione propedeutica alla progettazione di iniziative future indirizzate a risolvere le criticità emerse.

Il GEP della Scuola si rivolge primariamente a pianificare, realizzare e controllare l'attuazione di politiche di genere, ma tiene in considerazione precipua anche la prospettiva dell'intersectionality: ossia, intende associare le politiche di genere al rilievo e al contrasto delle disuguaglianze basate su altri tipi di diversità (culturali, linguistiche, religiose, relative all'orientamento sessuale, alla disabilità, allo stato socio-economico, all'appartenenza etnica, ecc.). Secondo l'indicazione delle Linee guida europee, un GEP inclusivo considera come le disuguaglianze di genere possano interagire con altre forme di discriminazione e si preoccupa di contrastarne gli effetti attraverso pratiche apposite. La prospettiva dell'intersectionality trova compimento nella previsione di azioni come la creazione di una postazione per persone con disabilità nella biblioteca della Scuola. Può precludere inoltre all'avvio di policies di carattere più generale a partire dalla raccolta di dati disaggregati su condizioni individuali o di gruppo, diverse dal genere, che possono, combinandosi o meno con questa differenza, causare o amplificare le disuguaglianze.

I.II La dimensione di genere alla Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna

La Scuola ha adottato nel tempo organismi, procedure e pratiche che si propongono di contrastare le disuguaglianze di genere, raggiungendo una discreta efficacia di azione. Nel solco dell'esperienza del Comitato per le Pari Opportunità, ha costituito il Comitato Unico di Garanzia (CUG) al quale sono attribuiti compiti consultivi, propositivi e di garanzia rispetto alla realizzazione di un ambiente di lavoro caratterizzato dai principi di pari

opportunità, contrasto alle discriminazioni e promozione del benessere lavorativo. Il PAP 2020-2022, elaborato dal CUG e approvato dal Senato accademico, già prevede alcune delle iniziative cui si allineano, nell'intento di proseguire e ampliare le esperienze realizzate, le azioni incluse nel GEP: sul piano dei servizi di welfare, della formazione al personale docente e tecnico-amministrativo e alla componente allievi, dell'implementazione di forme di lavoro agile. Ancora, il PAP promuove le attività della Task Force "Per un'Accademia inclusiva e Antisessista" e lo sviluppo di procedure per il riconoscimento di carriere ALIAS richiamate nel GEP.

La Scuola ha istituito da anni la figura della/del Consigliera/e di Fiducia, che presta assistenza a chi si ritenga vittima di abusi o fastidi sessuali, di condotte discriminatorie o di violenza morale; deve monitorare le situazioni di rischio in relazione ai comportamenti indicati e svolgere attività di rilevazione dei disagi anche attraverso incontri individuali e/o di gruppo con le varie componenti della Scuola. La/il Consigliera/e di Fiducia presiede il Comitato Garante del Codice Etico (CGCE), che svolge attività di analisi, indagine e controllo rispetto all'attuazione delle norme del Codice etico.

La Scuola si è infatti dotata di un Codice etico che afferma i principi e valori in cui la Scuola stessa si riconosce: la promozione del merito, la valorizzazione delle differenze, la trasparenza, l'imparzialità e l'integrità. Il Codice condanna e reprime comportamenti quali abuso di potere, abusi e molestie sessuali, nepotismo e favoritismo, indicando nel/la Consigliere/a di Fiducia e nel CGCE i canali di ascolto per le eventuali violazioni del Codice.

Nel 2014 la Scuola ha adottato anche un Codice di Comportamento che integra e specifica il codice di comportamento nazionale obbligatorio per le amministrazioni pubbliche (d.P.R. 16 aprile 2013, n. 62). La Scuola ha inteso tuttavia mantenere lo strumento del Codice etico già vigente dal 2010. Il coordinamento e il raccordo tra i due strumenti, nonché la loro eventuale revisione, costituiscono oggetto di un'azione prevista nel GEP.

La Scuola ha elaborato un Bilancio di Genere 2020 che compie un'analisi di contesto della dimensione di genere relativamente alla componente studentesca, al personale docente e ricercatore, al personale tecnico-amministrativo, agli incarichi istituzionali e di governo. Grazie al risultato prodotto da questa valutazione ex ante, è stato possibile pianificare le azioni inserite nel GEP, partendo dalla conoscenza e dall'approfondimento di situazioni e processi concreti, rendendole così maggiormente orientate a rispondere alle esigenze specifiche della Scuola.

Tra gli strumenti istituzionali disponibili per rilevare informazioni relative al clima culturale presente alla Scuola in relazione ai principi di pari opportunità e non discriminazione, nonché al livello di soddisfazione rispetto alle pratiche attive per garantirli, vi sono le indagini periodicamente somministrate al personale, docente e tecnico-amministrativo, e alla componente studentesca (ad esempio, il questionario sul benessere organizzativo). Il GEP prevede di arricchire la raccolta dei dati necessari all'attivazione e al monitoraggio delle politiche di genere sia con questionari appositi sia con l'inserimento di domande

dedicate all'interno dei sondaggi già operativi.

La base di esperienze attivate finora alla Scuola è molta ricca sia rispetto agli strumenti di analisi del gender gap sia in relazione alle misure assunte per contrastarlo. Essa si è realizzata attraverso le decisioni adottate dagli organi di governance e le pratiche attuate da altri organismi, commissioni, gruppi di lavoro di carattere progettuale, operativo e di monitoraggio.

Sezione II

II.I Il Piano di uguaglianza di genere della Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna: struttura e contenuti

Il GEP si articola nelle 5 seguenti aree di intervento: 1) Equilibrio vita privata/vita professionale e cultura dell'organizzazione; 2) Equilibrio di genere nelle posizioni di vertice e negli organi decisionali; 3) Uguaglianza di genere nel reclutamento e nelle progressioni di carriera; 4) Integrazione della dimensione di genere nella ricerca e nei programmi degli insegnamenti; 5) Contrasto della violenza di genere, comprese le molestie sessuali.

Per ciascuna area il GEP individua gli obiettivi da raggiungere e indica le azioni (in numero variabile) da intraprendere a tale scopo. La definizione degli obiettivi è fatta sulla base dell'analisi di contesto ottenuta con il Bilancio di genere, tenendo conto delle esperienze di pratiche orientate al genere già realizzate, e del loro livello di penetrazione rilevato attraverso sondaggi periodici. A ciascuna azione è dedicata una scheda che comprende una breve descrizione, i destinatari a cui è rivolta, i responsabili istituzionali e operativi, la timeline, gli indicatori di valutazione e le risorse umane, materiali ed economiche che vi sono dedicate.

Considerata la finalità, il GEP non è per sua natura un documento statico e immutabile e potrà essere soggetto a continue evoluzioni, modifiche ed integrazioni alla luce delle esigenze che emergeranno durante il periodo di implementazione.

L'aggiornamento del GEP potrebbe dipendere da molti fattori come, ad esempio, un eventuale cambiamento all'interno della struttura dell'organizzazione o l'introduzione di una nuova legislazione o di nuove politiche che si applicano alle organizzazioni di ricerca e/o alle università.

II.II Obiettivi specifici e misurazioni per Aree chiave

Le azioni descritte nel GEP sono finalizzate a perseguire una molteplicità di obiettivi attraverso una complessa rete di misure attuative.

Per questa ragione, appare evidente come il monitoraggio delle iniziative realizzate risulti essenziale al fine di capire se queste rispondano concretamente alle esigenze della Scuola e sostengano il cambiamento in modo efficace.

La previsione di indicatori di valutazione chiari, già in fase di elaborazione del GEP, consentirà di monitorare la realizzazione delle attività previste nel piano, il raggiungimento degli obiettivi prefissati, nonché agevererà il processo di conoscenza del cambiamento in atto da parte di tutte le componenti della Scuola.

Per consentire una più snella ed efficace interlocuzione tra le diverse strutture coinvolte nell'implementazione delle azioni indicate nel GEP, si ritiene opportuno prevedere l'individuazione di un/una referente per ogni Area e struttura della Scuola che supporterà nelle attività di raccolta dati e monitoraggio.

Alla luce della tipologia e del contenuto delle azioni previste nel GEP, sono state individuate due tipologie di indicatori:

1. indicatori quantitativi, volti alla misurazione e al raffronto delle informazioni contenute nel Bilancio di Genere al fine di monitorare l'aggiornamento e l'eventuale variazione dei dati a seguito dell'introduzione e dell'implementazione delle misure descritte nel GEP;

2. indicatori qualitativi, necessari a valutare il cambiamento nelle diverse dimensioni e attività della Scuola attraverso l'inserimento nel questionario sul Benessere Organizzativo di quesiti rivolti a verificare la percezione dell'effettivo impatto sulle componenti della Scuola delle azioni descritte nel GEP.

Di seguito è riportata l'articolazione del GEP:

AREA 1

Equilibrio vita privata/vita professionale e cultura dell'organizzazione

Obiettivi

1. Sostegno alla conciliazione tra lavoro e vita privata
2. Adozione della prospettiva di genere nella cultura organizzativa
3. Adozione di un linguaggio corretto dal punto di vista del genere
4. Costruzione di un ambiente di lavoro e di studio inclusivo

Azioni

1. Disponibilità di forme di lavoro flessibili in termini di orario e/o luogo di lavoro
2. Elaborazione di Linee guida per una migliore pianificazione e organizzazione delle riunioni coerentemente con le necessità di conciliare il lavoro e la vita privata
3. Previsione di un benefit mensile della durata di un anno per il periodo di maternità
4. Piani di fattibilità per la creazione di nuovi servizi di welfare

5. Adozione di un linguaggio istituzionale/amministrativo rispettoso della dimensione di genere

6. Diffusione e promozione dei contenuti del Regolamento sulle “Carriere Alias”

7. Formazione per il personale docente e di ricerca sui temi della gender equality, delle pari opportunità e della non discriminazione

9. Definizione di informazioni di facile accesso che offrano una panoramica sulle iniziative, azioni e servizi della Scuola che promuovono l'uguaglianza di genere

10. Raccolta dei dati disaggregati per genere relativi a: allocazione delle risorse, presentazione di pubblicazioni, progetti e brevetti, valutazione delle eccellenze della Scuola

AREA 2

Equilibrio di genere nelle posizioni di vertice e negli organi decisionali

Obiettivi

1. Armonizzazione dei processi decisionali e delle fonti interne con le attività incluse nel GEP al fine di rafforzare e sensibilizzare ad una maggiore equità di genere ed incrementare la presenza femminile nei processi decisionali
2. Promuovere le pari opportunità nella cultura, nei processi e nelle pratiche istituzionali attraverso l'equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative”

Azioni

1. Equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative”
-

AREA 3

Uguaglianza di genere nel reclutamento e nelle progressioni di carriera

Obiettivi

1. Miglioramento delle pari opportunità nel reclutamento accademico
2. Miglioramento delle pari opportunità nella progressione di carriera

Azioni

1. Produzione di Linee guida per il reclutamento del personale, delle allieve e degli allievi nel rispetto della parità di genere
 2. Promozione di campagne informative interne ed esterne per dare visibilità ai ricercatori del genere sottorappresentato in ogni campo di ricerca
-

3. Corsi di mentoring ed empowerment

4. Revisione dei criteri di valutazione nel reclutamento del personale docente e di ricerca al fine di supportarne il percorso di carriera in caso di genitorialità

5. Campagne social per la pubblicizzazione dei concorsi e delle opportunità lavorative mirate al genere meno rappresentato

6. Iniziativa “STEM, le ragazze si mettono in gioco”

AREA 4

Integrazione della dimensione di genere nella ricerca e nei programmi degli insegnamenti

Obiettivi

1. Promozione dell'integrazione delle variabili sesso e genere nel processo di ricerca

2. Favorire l'integrazione di una dimensione di genere nei contenuti della didattica

Azioni

1. Formazione specifica rivolta a tutta la comunità accademica sull'integrazione della dimensione di genere nella ricerca e nella didattica

2. Promuovere l'attivazione di Bandi 150 ore finalizzati al supporto ad attività legate alle tematiche di genere

3. Promozione di reti multidisciplinari di personale docente e ricercatore interessato alle tematiche del genere e del diversity management

4. Premi annuali per promuovere l'integrazione di una dimensione di genere e pari opportunità nella ricerca

AREA 5

Contrasto della violenza di genere, comprese le molestie sessuali

Obiettivi

1. Contribuire alla riduzione di pregiudizi e stereotipi di genere

2. Aumentare la consapevolezza sulle problematiche relative alla gender equality all'interno della comunità della Scuola e al suo esterno, contribuendo anche alla decostruzione di stereotipi di genere

3. Prevenire, individuare e gestire casi di molestie sessuali tra personale docente, personale tecnico e amministrativo, studenti e studentesse

Azioni

1. Costituzione “Sportello Antiviolenza” congiunto SSSA-UNIFI-SNS
2. Promozione delle attività di sensibilizzazione della Task Force “Per un’Accademia Inclusiva e Antisessista”
3. Analisi delle fonti pertinenti (Codice etico e Codice di comportamento) ed eventuale revisione e coordinamento
4. Stesura di FAQ per la segnalazione di comportamenti discriminatori, situazioni di molestie sessuali, violazioni del Codice etico
5. Formazione per il personale in posizione di leadership e per il personale docente e ricercatore
6. Formazione obbligatoria del corpo studentesco sul tema dell’educazione di genere e prevenzione della violenza di genere

Area 1

Equilibrio vita privata/vita professionale e cultura dell'organizzazione

Obiettivo 1: Sostegno alla conciliazione tra lavoro e vita privata

Obiettivo 2: Adozione della prospettiva di genere nella cultura organizzativa

Obiettivo 3: Adozione di un linguaggio corretto dal punto di vista del genere

Obiettivo 4: Costruzione di un ambiente di lavoro e di studio inclusivo

Azione 1.1 - Disponibilità di forme di lavoro flessibili in termini di orario e/o luogo di lavoro

Introdurre e/o prorogare e/o ampliare, compatibilmente con le esigenze organizzative dell'Ente, misure relative a forme di flessibilità dell'orario e delle modalità di lavoro, con particolare riferimento all'articolazione dell'orario di servizio, a forme di rapporto di lavoro parziale, Lavoro Agile (smart working) e Telelavoro.

Riferimento Obiettivi	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Obiettivo 1 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 2 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 3 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 4						
Target diretto	Personale tecnico-amministrativo						
Responsabili istituzionali	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Risorse Umane						
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Risorse Umane						
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Risorse Umane, Organizzazioni Sindacali, RSU, Servizi ICT						
Output	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Adozione Regolamento sul Lavoro Agile Raccolta organica delle disposizioni (Contratto integrativo, Regolamenti in materia) adottate dalla Direzione Generale e approvate dagli Organi della Scuola (da pubblicare in pagina intranet dedicata) 						
Outcome	Maggiore conoscenza e consapevolezza degli strumenti a disposizione attraverso la raccolta organica delle disposizioni (Contratto integrativo, Regolamenti in materia) adottate dalla Direzione Generale e approvate dagli Organi della Scuola che contemplino l'introduzione e/o la proroga e/o l'ampliamento delle forme di lavoro flessibili (da pubblicare in pagina intranet dedicata)						
Timeline	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>2022</th> <th>2023</th> <th>2024</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	2022	2023	2024			
2022	2023	2024					
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Verifica adozione del Regolamento sul Lavoro Agile (smart working) ed eventuali successive modifiche ed integrazioni Pubblicazione sulla pagina intranet dedicata delle disposizioni adottate in materia di forme di lavoro flessibili in termini di orario e/o luogo di lavoro 						
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive						

Azione 1.2 - Elaborazione di Linee guida per una migliore pianificazione e organizzazione delle riunioni coerentemente con le necessità di conciliare il lavoro e la vita privata

Elaborazione di Linee guida per un'organizzazione family friendly, finalizzate all'equilibrio famiglia-lavoro, attraverso una migliore pianificazione e organizzazione delle riunioni nell'ambito di attività didattiche, istituzionali e amministrative.

Riferimento Obiettivi	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Obiettivo 1 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 2 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 3 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Personale docente e ricercatore, personale tecnico-amministrativo
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili Amministrativi/e Aree e Istituti
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Risorse Umane, CUG
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Senato Accademico, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili Amministrativi/e Aree e Istituti, CUG
Output	Linee guida per una migliore pianificazione e organizzazione delle riunioni
Outcome	Miglioramento nelle modalità di pianificazione e organizzazione delle riunioni collegate ad attività didattiche, istituzionali e amministrative e rafforzamento di misure di benessere orientate alla conciliazione vita privata-lavoro
Timeline	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;">2022 </div> <div style="text-align: center;">2023 </div> <div style="text-align: center;">2024 </div> </div>
Indicatori di valutazione	1. Adozione delle Linee guida 2. Verifica/monitoraggio sull'implementazione attraverso apposito quesito nell'indagine sul Benessere Organizzativo
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 1.3 - Previsione di un benefit mensile della durata di un anno per il periodo di maternità

Il Senato Accademico e successivamente il Consiglio di Amministrazione nel 2021 hanno approvato la proposta della Retttrice di attivare misure di sostegno finalizzate al supporto della maternità per le assegniste di ricerca, le ricercatrici e le allieve PhD, tali da consentire loro un pronto rientro al lavoro e quindi alle attività di ricerca, al termine del periodo di astensione obbligatoria.

Il contributo dovrebbe permettere alle destinatarie di poter contare su un supporto di babysitting o servizi di nido per avere il tempo e la possibilità di proseguire nella propria attività di ricerca.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ○ Obiettivo 3 ○ Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Assegniste, Ricercatrici ed Allieve PhD
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Risorse Umane
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Risorse Umane, CUG
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Risorse Umane, CUG
Output	Assegnazione del benefit
Outcome	Supporto alle carriere femminili
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Report/statistiche sul numero di domande pervenute e di benefit assegnati
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate al supporto economico della maternità per le assegniste di ricerca, le ricercatrici e le allieve PhD come da Budget allegato

Azione 1.4 - Piani di fattibilità per la creazione di nuovi servizi di welfare

Studio sulla possibile estensione e il miglioramento dei servizi di assistenza all'infanzia e alla maternità, dalla stipula di convenzioni con enti esterni, alla creazione di una baby room fino al progetto di una ludoteca aziendale. L'azione comprende un'indagine e la conseguente mappatura del fabbisogno attraverso la somministrazione di questionari ad hoc a tutto il personale della Scuola e uno studio di fattibilità delle varie ipotesi. In particolare, l'azione si articolerà in:

1. Implementazione di accordi contrattuali con enti erogatori di servizi di cura e di assistenza e ampliamento delle possibilità di accesso a contributi finalizzati al sostegno delle politiche di welfare
2. Avvio di uno studio di fattibilità per lo sviluppo di aree dedicate all'allattamento e alla cura degli/delle infanti (baby room)
3. Avvio di uno studio di fattibilità per la realizzazione del progetto pilota "Ludoteca aziendale" da parte di un gruppo di lavoro appositamente costituito per l'analisi e la valutazione degli adempimenti tecnici e giuridici necessari (es. sicurezza, assicurazione RC, ecc.)

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ○ Obiettivo 3 ○ Obiettivo 4						
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica						
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili Amministrativi/e Aree e Istituti, CUG						
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Risorse Umane, Area Tecnica, Area Acquisti, CUG						
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili Amministrativi/e Aree e Istituti, Area Risorse Umane, CUG, Area Tecnica, Area Acquisti, CUG, RSU						
Output	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduzione e/o ampliamento di convenzioni con enti erogatori di servizi di cura e di assistenza 2. Report sullo studio di fattibilità per lo sviluppo aree per allattamento e cura degli/delle infanti (baby room) 3. Report sullo studio di fattibilità per la realizzazione del progetto pilota "Ludoteca aziendale" 						
Outcome	Rafforzamento di misure di welfare finalizzate ad una migliore conciliazione famiglia-lavoro						
Timeline	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>2022</th> <th>2023</th> <th>2024</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>■ ■</td> <td>■ ■</td> <td>■ ■</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	2022	2023	2024	■ ■	■ ■	■ ■
2022	2023	2024					
■ ■	■ ■	■ ■					
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verifica del numero di convenzioni con enti erogatori di servizi di cura e di assistenza attivate/rinnovate 2. Verifica dei contenuti del Report: disponibilità degli spazi ed eventuali costi necessari per l'allestimento 3. Verifica dei contenuti del Report: presenza di tutti gli aspetti necessari all'implementazione del Progetto pilota 						
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse dedicate all'attivazione e/o rinnovo di convenzioni con enti erogatori di servizi di cura e di assistenza come da Budget allegato						

Azione 1.5 - Adozione di un linguaggio istituzionale/amministrativo rispettoso della dimensione di genere

Promozione dell'uso del linguaggio di genere nelle comunicazioni istituzionali attraverso l'adeguamento delle fonti interne e della modulistica standard alle regole del linguaggio inclusivo.

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3 ● Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, CUG
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Risorse Umane, CUG, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione
Output	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Linee guida per un linguaggio amministrativo inclusivo della dimensione di genere 2. Fonti interne armonizzate con i contenuti delle Linee guida 3. Modulistica adeguata alle Linee guida
Outcome	Promozione di una cultura inclusiva rispetto al genere
Timeline	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;">2022 </div> </div>
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adozione delle Linee guida elaborate dal CUG 2. Monitoraggio sullo stato di avanzamento dell'adeguamento delle fonti interne rispetto ai contenuti delle Linee guida 3. Monitoraggio sull'utilizzo del linguaggio inclusivo della dimensione di genere nelle campagne informative istituzionali
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 1.6 - Diffusione e promozione dei contenuti del Regolamento sulle “Carriere Alias”

Il dispositivo della carriera Alias, un’identità transitoria, si colloca nell’ambito della tutela dei diritti fondamentali e incontra il bisogno di garantire condizioni in cui il riconoscimento dell’identità di genere è fattore dirimente rispetto al benessere e alla qualità di studio e di lavoro. Tale strumento è finalizzato a garantire ambienti inclusivi e rispettosi delle differenze, anche in tema di identità di genere, e a promuovere il benessere fisico, psicologico e relazionale delle persone che studiano e lavorano.

Gli organi della Scuola, il Consiglio di amministrazione in data 29/10/2021 e il Senato accademico in data 16/11/2021, hanno approvato il Regolamento e pertanto si ritiene utile promuoverne la diffusione al fine di aumentare la sensibilità della Comunità Accademica sul tema dell’identità di genere.

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3 ● Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area della Formazione, Area Risorse Umane
Responsabili dell’implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area della Formazione, Area Risorse Umane, Area Staff
Attori coinvolti nell’implementazione	Area della Formazione, Area Risorse Umane, Area Affari Generali, Area Staff, CUG
Output	1. Maggiore conoscenza da parte della Comunità Accademica dei contenuti del Regolamento sulle Carriere Alias 2. Report/statistiche sulle richieste pervenute
Outcome	Miglioramento della percezione della Scuola come ambiente inclusivo e rispettoso delle differenze, anche in tema di identità di genere
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Raccolta dati anonimizzati relativi alle richieste di attivazione delle carriere Alias e monitoraggio tempi di risposta della Scuola
Risorse Finanziarie	L’azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 1.7 - Formazione per il personale docente e di ricerca sui temi della gender equality, delle pari opportunità e della non discriminazione

Formazione specifica sui temi della gender equality, delle pari opportunità e della non discriminazione, rivolta a tutto il personale docente e di ricerca, con particolare riferimento alla loro rilevanza:

- nell'ambito dei rapporti di tutoraggio e supervisione
- nella valutazione di studenti/esse, come anche di candidati/e a posizioni di docenza e ricerca (unconscious bias).

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3 ● Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Personale docente e di ricerca
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, Area Staff, Area Formazione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, Area Staff, Area Formazione, Personale incaricato di svolgere attività di tutoraggio e supervisione
Output	Corsi di formazione sulle tematiche della gender equality, delle pari opportunità e della non discriminazione specifici per personale con responsabilità di tutoraggio e supervisione e/o partecipante a commissioni di valutazione
Outcome	Diffusione tra il personale docente e di ricerca della cultura gender sensitive e conseguente aumento della sensibilità sulle tematiche della gender equality, delle pari opportunità e della non discriminazione, al fine di una migliore inclusività, della valorizzazione delle diversità e della rimozione degli unconscious bias
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoraggio del numero dei corsi attivati 2. Monitoraggio della partecipazione ai corsi 3. Verifica dell'efficacia dei corsi in termini di aumento della sensibilità dei e delle partecipanti sulle tematiche affrontate
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'eventuale onorario dei Relatori e delle Relatrici ed organizzazione corsi di formazione come da Budget allegato

Azione 1.8 - Allestimento di una postazione attrezzata per utenti con bisogni speciali presso la Biblioteca della Scuola

Studio di fattibilità e allestimento di una postazione attrezzata per utenti con bisogni speciali (disabilità motorie e visive).

Riferimento Obiettivi	<input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 1 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 2 <input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 3 <input checked="" type="radio"/> Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Utenti con disabilità motorie e visive
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Delegato/Delegata alle iniziative in materia di persone diversamente abili e inclusione
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Servizi ICT, Area Formazione, Area Acquisti, Area Tecnica, Delegato/Delegata alle iniziative in materia di persone diversamente abili e inclusione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Servizi ICT, Area Formazione, Area Acquisti, Area Tecnica
Output	Postazione attrezzata per utenti con bisogni speciali
Outcome	Aumento della sensibilità sulle tematiche della diversità e delle pari opportunità e diffusione di una cultura inclusiva
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Verifica della disponibilità e dell'uso della postazione
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'allestimento della postazione attrezzata per utenti con bisogni speciali come da Budget allegato

Azione 1.9 - Definizione di informazioni di facile accesso che offrano una panoramica sulle iniziative, azioni e servizi della Scuola che promuovono l'uguaglianza di genere

Progettazione e realizzazione di una apposita sezione sul sito istituzionale che offra una panoramica sulle iniziative, azioni e servizi della Scuola che promuovono l'uguaglianza di genere.

All'interno di tale sezione, sarà inserita la traduzione in lingua inglese del GEP nonché di tutti i documenti ufficiali della Scuola rilevanti per le policies di genere.

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ○ Obiettivo 3 ● Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Comunità accademica
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, CUG
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, CUG, Consigliere/Consigliera di Fiducia
Output	1. Realizzazione di una apposita sezione sul sito istituzionale 2. Traduzione in lingua inglese del GEP nonché di tutti i documenti ufficiali della Scuola, rilevanti per le policies di genere
Outcome	Promozione della visibilità della Scuola come ambiente inclusivo
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio sull'aggiornamento e l'implementazione dell'apposita sezione del sito istituzionale, con particolare riferimento alla verifica sul numero degli accessi e di iniziative pubblicate
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 1.10 - Raccolta dei dati disaggregati per genere relativi a: allocazione delle risorse, presentazione di pubblicazioni, progetti e brevetti, valutazione delle eccellenze della Scuola

Raccolta sistematica, da parte delle diverse strutture della Scuola e degli Istituti, di dati quantitativi e qualitativi disaggregati per genere in formato digitale, per agevolare la stesura del Bilancio di Genere e per altre raccolte dati.

L'azione si pone altresì l'obiettivo di ampliare gli indicatori prevedendo l'inclusione di dati relativi alla partecipazione in qualità di membri/coordinatori a progetti internazionali/nazionali, progetti con industrie, progetti con pubbliche amministrazioni; all'importo del finanziamento; alla partecipazione a board, a comitati di selezione e gruppi di lavoro; al numero di giorni di assenza e motivo.

Oltre alla raccolta di dati quantitativi, si prevede la realizzazione di climate surveys per esplorare l'esperienza e la percezione sul gender balance nella Scuola.

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ○ Obiettivo 3 ● Obiettivo 4
Target diretto	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Organi della Scuola
Responsabili istituzionali	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, CUG
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, CUG, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Terza Missione, Area Formazione, Gruppo di Lavoro sul Bilancio di Genere
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, CUG, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Risorse Umane, Area Formazione, Area Terza Missione, Area Formazione, Gruppo di Lavoro sul Bilancio di Genere
Output	Bilancio di Genere aggiornato
Outcome	Aumento della base di informazioni sulla gender equality
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio sullo stato di avanzamento dell'aggiornamento periodico del Bilancio di Genere
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Area 2

Equilibrio di genere nelle posizioni di vertice e negli organi decisionali

Obiettivo 1: Armonizzazione dei processi decisionali e delle fonti interne con le attività incluse nel GEP al fine di rafforzare e sensibilizzare ad una maggiore equità di genere e incrementare la presenza femminile

Obiettivo 2: Promuovere le pari opportunità nella cultura, nei processi e nelle pratiche istituzionali attraverso l'equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni "operative"

Azione 2.1 - Equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative”

Previsione nelle fonti interne della Scuola dell’equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative” (a titolo di esempio: Commissione paritetica, Comitato etico congiunto, Comitato Garante del Codice Etico, Gruppi di lavoro).

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica presente negli organi Collegiali e nelle commissioni operative
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell’implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali
Attori coinvolti nell’implementazione	Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Responsabili di Area e Responsabili di Istituto, CUG
Output	Aggiornamento ed armonizzazione delle fonti interne rispetto all’equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative”
Outcome	Equità di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative”
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Verifica sullo stato di aggiornamento ed armonizzazione delle fonti interne rispetto all’equilibrio di genere negli organi collegiali e nelle commissioni “operative”
Risorse Finanziarie	L’azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Area 3

Uguaglianza di genere nel reclutamento e nelle progressioni di carriera

Obiettivo 1: Miglioramento delle pari opportunità nel reclutamento accademico

Obiettivo 2: Miglioramento delle pari opportunità nella progressione di carriera

Azione 3.1 - Produzione di Linee guida per il reclutamento del personale, delle allieve e degli allievi nel rispetto della parità di genere

Elaborazione di Linee guida volte a:

1. promuovere l'uso di un linguaggio inclusivo nella scrittura dei bandi nonché la consapevolezza e la rimozione dei pregiudizi di genere nella valutazione
2. rispettare la parità di genere nella composizione delle Commissioni valutatrici per il reclutamento del personale e delle allieve e degli allievi
3. prevedere il criterio del genere meno rappresentato come prioritario rispetto a quello della più giovane età nelle ipotesi di parità di punteggio nelle graduatorie di selezione.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Componenti delle Commissioni di concorso Candidate e candidati alle procedure di selezione della Scuola
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Risorse Umane, Area Formazione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Risorse Umane, Area Formazione, CUG
Output	Linee guida
Outcome	Equità di genere nelle procedure di reclutamento, nella redazione dei bandi, nella composizione delle commissioni valutatrici nonché nella determinazione dei criteri di selezione
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Approvazione Linee guida 2. Monitoraggio dell'attuazione delle Linee guida
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 3.2 - Promozione di campagne informative interne ed esterne per dare visibilità al genere sottorappresentato in ogni campo di ricerca

Organizzazione di campagne informative interne ed esterne (ad esempio workshop, newsletter, comunicazioni tramite canali social) interne ed esterne con role model nei vari ambiti disciplinari.

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Personale docente e ricercatore, personale di ricerca, allievi ed allieve, dottorandi e dottorande
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttori/Diretrrici di Istituto, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Direttori/Diretrrici di Istituto, Responsabili Scientifici di progetti di ricerca, Project Manager, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Promozione, Coordinamento e Valutazione Ricerca
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttori/Diretrrici di Istituto, Responsabili Scientifici di progetti di ricerca, Project Manager, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Servizi ICT
Output	Campagne informative realizzate
Outcome	Promozione della missione della Scuola come ambiente di ricerca equo ed inclusivo
Timeline	<p>2022 2023 2024</p>
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio del numero di campagne informative realizzate e dei/ delle partecipanti e raccolta dati sulle visualizzazioni
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'implementazione di campagne di comunicazione istituzionale come da Budget allegato

Azione 3.3 - Corsi di mentoring ed empowerment

Progettazione e organizzazione di percorsi e workshop orientati a sviluppare empowerment, valorizzazione di sé e leadership diretti al genere numericamente sottorappresentato.

In particolare, l'azione intende promuovere:

1. workshop focalizzati sulle soft skill; pianificazione annuale di attività finalizzate al confronto con figure femminili senior e role model; progettazione e pianificazione di attività di formazione sulla gender equality nell'accademia;
2. corsi su programmi di finanziamento (es. Horizon Europe/MSCA)
3. progettazione e pianificazione della attività di orientamento e formazione sull'influenza dei bias di genere nelle scelte professionali e di carriera attraverso la definizione di progetti di orientamento per le scuole volti a contrastare gli stereotipi di genere.

Riferimento Obiettivi	<input type="radio"/> Obiettivo 1 <input checked="" type="radio"/> Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Comunità accademica di genere numericamente sottorappresentato
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, Area Staff, Area Formazione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, Area Staff, Area Formazione, Personale incaricato di svolgere attività di tutoraggio
Output	Percorsi e workshop orientati a sviluppare empowerment, valorizzazione di sé e leadership e negoziazione diretti al genere numericamente sottorappresentato
Outcome	Aumento di scelte professionali e di carriera non stereotipiche
Timeline	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;">2022 </div> <div style="text-align: center;">2023 </div> <div style="text-align: center;">2024 </div> </div>
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Numero di percorsi e workshop attivati 2. Report/statistiche sull'adesione alle iniziative
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'eventuale onorario dei Relatori e delle Relatrici ed organizzazione percorsi e workshop sulle tematiche specifiche come da Budget allegato

Azione 3.4 - Revisione dei criteri di valutazione nel reclutamento del personale docente e di ricerca al fine di supportarne il percorso di carriera in caso di genitorialità

Revisione dei criteri di valutazione da applicare nel reclutamento del personale docente e di ricerca: introduzione di un criterio di valutazione della produzione scientifica e/o dell'anzianità accademica che tenga conto di un congedo parentale "esteso" (non limitato all'effettivo congedo parentale goduto), come già previsto dalle regole di partecipazione di alcuni programmi di finanziamento in ambito comunitario (ad esempio ERC) e nazionale (ad esempio Fondo Italiano per la Scienza).

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Personale docente e di ricerca
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Risorse Umane, Presidenti e Presidentesse di Commissione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Risorse Umane, Presidenti e Presidentesse di Commissione, Membri delle Commissioni
Output	Adozione di policy relativa ai criteri di valutazione per il reclutamento del personale docente e di ricerca
Outcome	Pari opportunità nei processi di reclutamento per personale docente e di ricerca con o senza figli
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verifica adozione policy 2. Monitoraggio sull'attuazione della policy nelle procedure di reclutamento
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 3.5 - Campagne social per la pubblicizzazione dei concorsi e delle opportunità lavorative mirate al genere meno rappresentato

Progettazione e organizzazione di campagne di comunicazione social mirate al genere meno rappresentato per la pubblicizzazione dei concorsi e delle opportunità lavorative.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ○ Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Media e società
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Risorse Umane
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Risorse Umane, Area Staff, RSU, Servizi ICT
Output	Campagne social tematiche realizzate
Outcome	Maggiore capacità della Scuola di attrarre nei propri percorsi di studio, formazione e ricerca persone del genere meno rappresentato
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio del numero di campagne social realizzate e raccolta dati disaggregati sul numero di visualizzazioni
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse dedicate all'organizzazione e promozione degli eventi e delle campagne di informazione come da Budget allegato

Azione 3.6 - Iniziativa “STEM, le ragazze si mettono in gioco”

Iniziativa “STEM, le ragazze si mettono in gioco” al fine di promuovere la scelta di iscriversi ai corsi di laurea STEM (acronimo di “Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics”) da parte di studentesse di alto merito, figlie di genitori non laureati, selezionate in tutta Italia e che hanno concluso nel mese di giugno il quarto anno di scuola secondaria superiore.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Studentesse iscritte alla quarta superiore
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell’implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Affari Generali, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Formazione, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche
Attori coinvolti nell’implementazione	Area Affari Generali, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Formazione, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Personale docente e ricercatore
Output	Sviluppo e valorizzazione dell’iniziativa “STEM, le ragazze si mettono in gioco”
Outcome	Aumento di scelte professionali e di carriera non stereotipiche
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Previsione dell’iniziativa “STEM, le ragazze si mettono in gioco” quale corso di orientamento da svolgere annualmente
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all’orientamento ed alla creazione di apposite campagne di comunicazione istituzionale come da Budget allegato

Area 4

Integrazione della dimensione di genere nella ricerca e nei programmi degli insegnamenti

Obiettivo 1: Promozione dell'integrazione delle variabili sesso e genere nel processo di ricerca

Obiettivo 2: Favorire l'integrazione di una dimensione di genere nei contenuti della didattica

Azione 4.1 - Formazione specifica rivolta a tutta la comunità accademica sull'integrazione della dimensione di genere nella ricerca e nella didattica

Progettazione e pianificazione di percorsi di formazione specifica per tutta la comunità accademica, in particolare:

1. corsi su bandi specifici per la promozione della gender equality
2. per il personale di ricerca, corsi su come integrare la dimensione di genere nella ricerca
3. per il personale docente, corsi su come integrare la dimensione di genere nella didattica

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2						
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica						
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale						
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Formazione						
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Formazione, Area Promozione, Coordinamento e Valutazione Ricerca, Personale incaricato di svolgere attività di tutoraggio						
Output	Corsi di formazione specifica attivati						
Outcome	Promozione dell'integrazione della dimensione di genere nella ricerca e nella didattica						
Timeline	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>2022</td> <td>2023</td> <td>2024</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	2022	2023	2024			
2022	2023	2024					
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio del numero di corsi attivati e raccolta dati relativi ai partecipanti ed alle partecipanti						
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'eventuale onorario dei Relatori e delle Relatrici ed organizzazione corsi di formazione come da Budget allegato						

Azione 4.2 - Promuovere l'attivazione di Bandi 150 ore finalizzati al supporto ad attività legate alle tematiche di genere

Elaborazione e pubblicazione di Bandi per collaborazioni a tempo parziale, ai sensi del D. Lgs. n. 69/2012 e del Regolamento delle attività formative della Scuola (art. 104 e segg.) - cosiddetti Bandi 150 ore - rivolti ad allieve ed allievi finalizzati allo svolgimento di attività di supporto legate alle tematiche di genere.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Allieve ed Allievi
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, CUG
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, CUG
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, CUG, Area Risorse Umane, Servizi ICT
Output	Bandi 150 ore sulle tematiche di genere
Outcome	Diffusione di una cultura inclusiva rispetto al genere
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pubblicazione di Bandi 150 ore su base annuale 2. Raccolta dati sul numero di richieste di partecipazione
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate a n. 2 borse annuali come da Budget allegato

Azione 4.3 - Promozione di reti multidisciplinari di personale docente e ricercatore interessato alle tematiche del genere e del diversity management

Promozione di reti multidisciplinari di personale docente e ricercatore interessato alle tematiche del genere e del diversity management, rafforzamento e consolidamento della partecipazione della Scuola a network tematici attraverso appositi contributi dedicati alla partecipazione delle ricercatrici a gruppi scientifici e reti sui temi di genere, promozione dello sviluppo di una cultura inclusiva anche attraverso la partecipazione attiva degli studenti e delle studentesse.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2						
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica						
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto						
Responsabili dell'implementazione	CUG, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto						
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	CUG, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Affari Generali, Personale docente e ricercatore						
Output	Adesione della Scuola a reti multidisciplinari nell'ambito delle tematiche del genere e del diversity management						
Outcome	Diffusione delle conoscenze e dell'approccio interdisciplinare della ricerca scientifica sulle tematiche di genere						
Timeline	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>2022</td> <td>2023</td> <td>2024</td> </tr> <tr> <td>■ ■</td> <td>■ ■</td> <td>■ ■</td> </tr> </table>	2022	2023	2024	■ ■	■ ■	■ ■
2022	2023	2024					
■ ■	■ ■	■ ■					
Indicatori di valutazione	Report/statistiche sulla adesione della Scuola a reti multidisciplinari						
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive						

Azione 4.4 - Premi annuali per promuovere l'integrazione di una dimensione di genere e pari opportunità nella ricerca

Pubblicazione di bandi finalizzati all'erogazione di premi annuali per la migliore tesi che includa una dimensione di genere e pari opportunità destinati a laureandi/laureande e dottorandi/dottorande.

Riferimento Obiettivi	○ Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2
Target diretto	Allievi/Allieve, Dottorandi/Dottorande
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Area Formazione, Area Staff, CUG
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Area Formazione, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione, Area Staff, CUG
Output	Bandi e relative graduatorie di attribuzione dei premi
Outcome	Incremento di progetti di ricerca e di tesi sulle tematiche legate alla gender equality e alle pari opportunità
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Pubblicazione di almeno un bando e raccolta numero delle richieste di partecipazione pervenute
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate a premi rivolti agli studenti ed alle studentesse come da Budget allegato

Area 5

Contrasto della violenza di genere, comprese le molestie sessuali

Obiettivo 1: Contribuire alla riduzione di pregiudizi e stereotipi di genere

Obiettivo 2: Aumentare la consapevolezza sulle problematiche relative alla gender equality all'interno della comunità della Scuola e al suo esterno, contribuendo anche alla decostruzione di stereotipi di genere

Obiettivo 3: Prevenire, individuare e gestire casi di molestie sessuali tra personale docente, personale tecnico e amministrativo, studenti e studentesse

Azione 5.1 - Costituzione “Sportello Antiviolenza” congiunto SSSA-UNUPI-SNS

I Comitati Unici di Garanzia dell’Università di Pisa, della Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, della Scuola Normale Superiore convergono sulla necessità di intensificare il proprio impegno sul fronte della tutela delle persone offese da atti di violenza di genere, di omo- e trans-fobia, e di comportamenti discriminatori, sia attraverso attività di carattere formativo, informativo e divulgativo, sia mediante un servizio di ascolto, assistenza, informazione e sostegno rivolto a tutti/e gli/le appartenenti alla comunità universitaria, istituendo all’uopo un apposito sportello che abbia competenze specifiche in ambito universitario.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3						
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica						
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, CUG						
Responsabili dell’implementazione	CUG, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali						
Attori coinvolti nell’implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, CUG, Consigliere/Consigliera di Fiducia, Area Affari Generali, Area Staff						
Output	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Istituzione sportello antiviolenza congiunto SSSA-UNUPI-SNS 2. Campagna di comunicazione mirata alla promozione e pubblicizzazione dei servizi offerti dallo sportello 						
Outcome	Rafforzamento di strumenti a tutela delle persone offese da atti di violenza e di discriminazioni di genere						
Timeline	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>2022</th> <th>2023</th> <th>2024</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>■ ■</td> <td>■ ■</td> <td>■ ■</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	2022	2023	2024	■ ■	■ ■	■ ■
2022	2023	2024					
■ ■	■ ■	■ ■					
Indicatori di valutazione	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Istituzione sportello antiviolenza congiunto SSSA-UNUPI-SNS 2. Raccolta dati sul numero di accessi e di richieste di assistenza e sostegno 						
Risorse Finanziarie	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Costi di funzionamento dello sportello (risorse umane dedicate e spazi) come da Budget allegato 2. Campagna di comunicazione sportello (Ideazione strategica e creatività campagna) come da Budget allegato 						

Azione 5.2 - Promozione delle attività di sensibilizzazione della Task Force “Per un’Accademia Inclusiva e Antisessista”

Promozione di campagne di comunicazione, momenti di riflessione e dibattito che si collegano a temi quali pari opportunità, inclusione, marginalizzazione, violenza di genere, questioni LGBT+, con la partecipazione di tutta la comunità accademica.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ○ Obiettivo 3
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, CUG, Area Affari Generali, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione
Responsabili dell'implementazione	CUG, Area Affari Generali, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	CUG, Area Affari Generali, Area Relazioni Esterne e Comunicazione
Output	1. Calendarizzazione di eventi ed incontri 2. Progettazione di campagne di comunicazione, momenti di riflessione e dibattito che si collegano a temi quali pari opportunità, inclusione, marginalizzazione, violenza di genere
Outcome	Sensibilizzazione alle tematiche legate a temi quali pari opportunità, inclusione, marginalizzazione, violenza di genere e promozione della visibilità della Scuola come ambiente inclusivo
Timeline	<p>2022 2023 2024</p>
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio e raccolta dati relativi al numero di eventi organizzati nel triennio 2022-2024
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse dedicate all'organizzazione e promozione degli eventi e delle campagne di informazione come da Budget allegato

Azione 5.3 - Analisi delle fonti pertinenti (Codice etico e Codice di Comportamento) ed eventuale revisione e coordinamento

Analisi ed adeguamento delle fonti interne pertinenti (Codice etico e Codice di Comportamento) a partire dalla verifica del rispetto del linguaggio inclusivo, armonizzazione con i contenuti del GEP.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, CUG
Output	Codice etico e Codice di Comportamento aggiornati
Outcome	Promozione di una cultura inclusiva rispetto al genere
Timeline	<p>2022 2023 2024</p>
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio sullo stato di avanzamento delle attività di analisi ed adeguamento del Codice etico e del Codice di Comportamento
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive

Azione 5.4 - Stesura di FAQ per la segnalazione di comportamenti discriminatori, situazioni di molestie sessuali, violazioni del Codice etico

Recepimento delle raccomandazioni in vigore a livello europeo e nazionale attraverso l'aggiornamento delle procedure per la segnalazione di comportamenti discriminatori e situazioni di molestie sessuali e successiva elaborazione di FAQ che chiariscano gli adempimenti da porre in essere e le competenze dei diversi soggetti coinvolti.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3						
Target diretto	Comunità Accademica						
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale						
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Staff, CUG, Consigliere/Consigliera di Fiducia						
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Staff, CUG, Consigliere/Consigliera di Fiducia, RSU, Servizi ICT						
Output	FAQ per la segnalazione di comportamenti discriminatori, situazioni di molestie sessuali, violazioni del Codice Etico						
Outcome	Rafforzamento del ruolo della Scuola quale organizzazione di contrasto delle discriminazioni						
Timeline	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>2022</td> <td>2023</td> <td>2024</td> </tr> <tr> <td>						
2022	2023	2024					
Indicatori di valutazione	Pubblicazione delle FAQ sul sito istituzionale ed elaborazione report per monitorare il numero degli accessi alla pagina						
Risorse Finanziarie	L'azione non richiede risorse economiche aggiuntive						

Azione 5.5 - Formazione per il personale in posizione di leadership e per il personale docente e ricercatore

Organizzazione di moduli formativi obbligatori - destinati al personale in posizione di leadership ed al personale docente e ricercatore - orientati alla sensibilizzazione sulle tematiche legate alla violenza di genere al fine di creare consapevolezza sui fenomeni di sessismo e molestie sessuali e a sviluppare empowerment e inclusività nei processi decisionali.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3
Target diretto	Personale docente e ricercatore, Componenti degli organi della Scuola, Personale collocato in posizioni apicali
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Direttore/Direttrici di Istituto, Organi della Scuola, Area Risorse Umane, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Responsabili di Area e di Istituto, Presidi delle Classi Accademiche, Direttori/Direttrici di Istituto, Area Formazione, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Risorse Umane
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Area Formazione, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, Area Formazione, Area Staff, Area Affari Generali, CUG, Area Risorse Umane
Output	Corsi destinati al personale in posizione di leadership ed al personale docente e ricercatore sul tema dell'educazione di genere, prevenzione della violenza di genere, empowerment ed inclusività nei processi decisionali
Outcome	Diffusione di una cultura inclusiva rispetto al genere
Timeline	
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio del numero di corsi attivati e raccolta dati relativi ai partecipanti ed alle partecipanti
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'eventuale onorario dei Relatori e delle Relatrici ed organizzazione corsi di formazione come da Budget allegato

Azione 5.6 - Formazione obbligatoria del corpo studentesco sul tema dell'educazione di genere e prevenzione della violenza di genere

Organizzazione di moduli formativi obbligatori - destinati al corpo studentesco - orientati alla sensibilizzazione sulle tematiche legate alla violenza di genere al fine di creare consapevolezza su violenza di genere, sessismo e molestie sessuali.

Riferimento Obiettivi	● Obiettivo 1 ● Obiettivo 2 ● Obiettivo 3
Target diretto	Corpo studentesco
Responsabili istituzionali	Rettore/Rettrice, Presidi delle Classi accademiche, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Formazione
Responsabili dell'implementazione	Rettore/Rettrice, Presidi delle Classi accademiche, Direttore/Direttrice Generale, Area Formazione
Attori coinvolti nell'implementazione	Presidi delle Classi accademiche, Area Formazione, Personale docente e ricercatore, Personale incaricato di svolgere attività di tutoraggio, CUG
Output	Corsi obbligatori destinati al corpo studentesco sul tema dell'educazione di genere e prevenzione della violenza di genere
Outcome	Diffusione di una cultura inclusiva rispetto al genere
Timeline	<p>2022 2023 2024</p>
Indicatori di valutazione	Monitoraggio del numero di corsi attivati e raccolta dati relativi ai partecipanti ed alle partecipanti
Risorse Finanziarie	Risorse destinate all'eventuale onorario dei Relatori e delle Relatrici ed organizzazione corsi di formazione come da Budget allegato

Il presente documento è stato approvato dal Senato Accademico della Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna nella seduta del 15 dicembre 2021 e dal Consiglio di Amministrazione federato nella seduta del 20 dicembre 2021, ed è reso disponibile nell'apposita sezione del sito istituzionale della Scuola al fine di consentirne la massima diffusione.

La Rettrice della Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
Prof.ssa Sabina Nuti

(Documento sottoscritto digitalmente ai sensi del D.Lgs. 82/2005 e s.m.i)

KADİR HAS UNIVERSITY GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

KADİR HAS UNIVERSITY GENDER EQUALITY POLICY

Gender inequality is still one of the most common social problems both in Turkey and throughout the world in particular as a matter of justice and human rights. The problem of gender inequality includes the types of marginalization and discrimination faced by individuals based on gender. This covers all types of current practices and power imbalances concerning social patterns that appear as gender-based violence and discrimination. To attain the target of gender equality, it is required to question the power imbalances and unequal gender dynamics and, encourage fair access to resources and opportunities.

All people must be treated fairly and with dignity without any discrimination based on gender, ethnic origin, belief, sexual orientation, gender identity, nationality, and similar grounds, which is a matter of human rights. As an academic institution embracing universal values, Kadir Has University also accepts this approach. As it is provided in article 10 of our Constitution, “Everyone is equal before the law without distinction as to language, race, color, sex, political opinion, philosophical belief, religion, and sect, or any such grounds.” Article 10 of the Constitution guarantees that it is the positive and direct obligation of the state to put into practice gender equality and, that positive action will not mean discrimination **(Additional paragraph: 7/5/2004-5170/Article 1)**.

Our country is also one of the parties to the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. Gender equality is one of the Sustainable Development Goals that are explained in 17 articles by the United Nations. Likewise, gender equality is one of the priority policies of the Council of Europe of which Turkey is a member, and the Council of Europe sets forth the targets and methods in the Gender Equality Strategy documents in order to put into practice this policy.

Considering the academic principles and the objectives of the Policy on Prevention of Harassment and Discrimination; the Policy Document Intended to Prevent Gender-Based Harassment, Sexual Harassment and Sexual Assault as well as the Directives and Practices of the Unit to Prevent Gender-Based Harassment, Sexual Harassment and Sexual Assault; the research, projects and activities of the Gender and Women Studies Research Center on gender inequality and the Gender Studies Ph.D. Program, Kadir Has University is one of the few universities that directly deal with gender-based inequalities in Turkey and, has committed itself to serving as a role model developing the best practices in terms of gender equality.

The main objectives the KHAS Gender Equality Plan (GEP) are as follows:

1. Eliminate gender-based discriminatory practices in the fields of recruitment, employment security and career development of employees and, create practices intended to improve gender equality.
2. Make visible gender unbalances in the decision-making processes and take measures to establish gender equality to improve collaborative and coherent working processes, engagement, and transparency.

3. Create and make sustainable a safe and supportive working environment, where there is no gender-based violence, and there is no discrimination in conducts and behaviors for academic and administrative staff, the outsourced personnel, and the students.
4. Strengthen the balance of gender by means of considering the gender perspective in all the scientific fields for both the content of research and various processes of research such as the formation of teams, and the publication of results.

In order to attain these objectives, **within the framework of the GEP, Kadir Has University** aims to take necessary steps in:

- Corporate culture, management, and leadership mechanisms as well as corporate directions, encouragements and directives,
- All the areas and processes forming the campus climate and during the procedures intended to further strengthen the gender equality perspective among the academic and administrative staff, the outsourced employees, and the students,
- Career development, the management of recruitment and promotion processes, the consideration of work-life balance, as well as private/temporary conditions concerning private life such as birth, having children, the necessity to take care of relatives for leaves and promotions,
- Educational processes and curricula and,
- Research processes,

in order to ensure and enforce the gender equality policies and principles.

KADİR HAS UNIVERSITY GENDER EQUALITY ACTION PLAN

To prevent any type of gender-based discrimination and sexist attitudes and behaviors within the framework of the main themes listed in detail above within the organization of Kadir Has University, **the KHAS Gender Equality Action Plan** has been drafted in a way that contains the details on the information, enforcement and application aspects thereof.

1. Corporate Culture, Management, and Leadership

Gender Equality Committee

A **Gender Equality Committee (GEC)** will be established, which is to be identified by and will operate reporting to the President. This committee will consist of academic staff, administrative staff and students, and meet on a regular basis to determine policies and make efforts in respect of gender equality. For the formation of the GEC, those who work in the field of gender equality and who are trained in this field will be prioritized. The GEC makes efforts to ensure not only the permanent staff and students of the university but also the businesses serving to our university and their employees accommodate themselves to the policies in the field of gender equality. Accordingly, the main tasks of the committee will be the activities of due diligence, continuing education, and monitoring and evaluation. The efforts made within the organization of the GEC will be reported to the senior management on a regular basis.

Due Diligence: The GEC will carry out necessary quantitative and qualitative data collections intended to determine the current condition of Kadir Has University in respect of gender equality. Within the scope of these efforts, the data will be analyzed in respect of the titles of researchers and academic staff, the male & female percentages by faculties, departments and units, and the male female male percentages among the conductors and researchers of the research projects and, the authors of the publications. In addition, the conditions and needs of those who feel that they are exposed to discrimination due to their gender identity and sexual orientation among the university staff and students will be identified by means of the reports from the Unit to Prevent Sexual Harassment and Sexual Assault (UPSHSA).

Continuing Education: Seminars, workshops and projects will be organized with the participation of all the stakeholders within the scope of a time schedule that is to be jointly prepared by the faculties and the **KHAS GEC** in order to enhance the knowledge and awareness of the academicians, researchers, administrative staff, outsourced personnel and students in respect of sexual discrimination, and the affects thereof will be measured in a structured way.

Monitoring and Evaluation: After the formation of the **KHAS GEC**, the statistical and qualitative studies detailed under the title “Due Diligence” will be renewed every year, and the developments will be monitored and reported by the **KHAS GEC** to the President.

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Corporate Governance	Leadership & Management	Improvement of gender equality in the main commissions where decisions are made	Guarantee the continuity of an egalitarian gender balance	X	X	X	President	At least %40 female members in all the commissions	
Corporate Governance	Leadership & Management	Lack of education in respect of gender equality	Integration of the online gender equality training to the administrative and academic staff in the promotion and employment contract renewal processes		X		The Gender and Women Studies Research Center, The Directorate of Human Resources	50% of the academic and administrative staff receiving the training	

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Corporate Governance	Audit Policy & Practices	Improvement of the policies and the respective units to fight harassment, mobbing, sexual assault, and violence	Ensure that the policy and the respective unit are announced (through MyKhas and on the website) and all the KHAS society members are informed accordingly	X			The UPSHSA, The Directorate of Human Resources	The policy is available on the MyKhas and KHAS website, and both the policy and unit are announced to the KHAS society	
Corporate Governance	Audit Policy & Practices	Improvement of the processes for data collection, publication, and reporting based on gender	Ensure that the data are maintained and reported on the basis of gender in order to monitor the progress and, correct the deficiencies if any	X			The Directorate of Institutional Research and Assessment, the UPSHSA, The Directorate of Human Resources, The Directorate of Operation and Purchasing	Maintain and report the data separated based on the gender equality	
Corporate Governance	Audit Policy & Practices	Improvement of the University's Quality System with the aims for gender equality	Integration of the gender equality policies and the Gender Equality Plan with the Quality System and the strategic plan of the university		X		The Directorate of Institutional Research and Assessment	A page on the KHAS website, where the Gender Equality Plan and the data on gender equality are made available	

2. Campus Climate

Our university aims to create a campus climate, which is egalitarian, libertarian, dialogue-based, engaging, inclusive, accessible to all the society members and where any type of gender-based discriminatory attitude, behavior and practice are completely excluded. It is one of the priorities of our university in respect of the campus climate to ensure that all the members, in particular, the students, academic and administrative personnel and outsourced personnel, are aware of the concept of gender equality.

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Campus Climate	Awareness	Lack of knowledge of the students in respect of the perception of gender at the campus	Planning of focus groups with the students		X		The Directorate of Institutional Research and Assessment, The Gender and Women Studies Research Center	Focus groups	
Campus Climate	Awareness	Enhance the visibility of gender at the campus	Use of stickers, posters and other materials on the boards; organization of gender-based exhibitions, theaters and forums		X		The Campus Life Office, The Corporate Communication	Physical and online materials, exhibitions, plays, forums and similar events	
Campus Climate	Awareness	Enhance the awareness of gender at the campus	Provision of training on gender equality		X		The Gender and Women Studies Research Center	Training on gender equality, the number and percentages of the participants	

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Campus Climate	Awareness	Awareness of the sub-employers and the outsourced personnel	Questionnaires with the sub-employers and outsourced personnel; improvement of gender balance in the process of recruitment; challenging the gender stereotypes in the process of recruitment (e.g. female shuttle vehicle drivers); directives on the expectations from the sub-employers		X		The Directorate of Operation and Purchasing	Preparation of a code of conduct for the sub-employers and employees and, inclusion thereof into their contracts Additional training on gender-based violence to the security staff	
Campus Climate	Engagement	Enhance the engagement of the students and student clubs	<p>Training to the students and student clubs on gender; training of trainers; development of a co-presidency system for the student clubs</p> <p>Gender projects with the participation of the students</p>		X		The Campus Life Office, Core Program	Training and projects to the student clubs	
Campus Climate	Engagement	Increase the number of male participants in the Gender Equality Plan	Organization of training programs and workshops with both the employees and students in order to discuss on how to increase the number of male participants in the efforts for gender equality		X		The Gender and Women Studies Research Center, Core Program	Training programs focusing on males	

3. Career Development, Recruitment Process and Work-Life Balance

There is already a gender balance established in our university in respect of the number of both the students and the academic and administrative staff. In addition, significant steps have been taken with the intention to ensure gender equality in the employment and performance directives after the updates thereon in 2018, 2019 and 2020. There have been some improvements, for example, an academic person who takes a maternity/parental leave will not be included in the annual performance for a period of one year following the year they restarted to work, and the period used for these leaves will be added to the periodic performance period. Nevertheless, the concept of gender equality is a dynamic area so that it must be continuously monitored in the career development and recruitment processes, and thus the current improvement areas must be identified and, new practices must be developed accordingly. Our university takes necessary steps in cooperation with the **KHAS GEC** and the Directorate of Human Resources in order to ensure gender equality in the career development and recruitment processes.

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Career Development	Professional Development	The percentage of female employees is getting decreased as the position is getting higher	Development of a mentorship system for female employees	X			The President, The General Secretary, The Directorate of Human resources, The Gender and Women Studies Research Center	The number and percentage of female employees receiving mentorship and, the percentage by gender and position	
Career Development	Professional Development	Lack of representation of the female doctoral students	Encourage the female students in the undergraduate programs to apply to the master's degree and doctoral programs	X			The School of Graduate Studies, The Scholarship Committee	Percentages of female graduate and doctoral students	
Career Development	Professional Development	Enhancement of support mechanisms for the researchers at the beginning of their careers (Ph.D. Candidates, Assistant Professors, Research Assistants)	Training in respect of career development, funding opportunities and publication methods/tips		X	X	The Directorate of R&D Resources	3 training programs organized in a year and at least 70% of the female employees attending these training programs	

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Career Development	Professional Development	Mentorship for undergraduate students	Joint efforts with non-governmental organizations such as KAGİDER, TurkishWIN, CampusWIN for the development of mentorship and leadership for female students		X	X	The Career Office, The Campus Life Office, The Student Clubs, The Gender and Women Studies Research Center	Training and mentorships provided	
Career Development	Employee Profile	Improvement of the respective processes in the HR system concerning the data separated by gender	Ensure that the HR system maintains the data separated by gender for all the areas	X			The Directorate of Human Resources	The HR keeps the data on the following subjects on the basis of gender equality. personnel, recruitment, promotions, those quitting, and use of the business-life balance provisions	
Career Development	Recruitment	Improvement of the recruitment practices	Formation of regulations/procedures intended to create a recruitment system established based on gender equality and diversity containing practices to enhance the diversity of candidates and employees; preparation of a text for job adverts referring to gender equality and diversity		X		The President, The General Secretary, The Directorate of Human Resources, The Directorate of Corporate Communication, The Gender and Women Studies Research Center	Regulations and procedures drafted Addition of a text for job adverts highlighting the concept of gender equality and diversity	
Career Development	Recruitment	Provision of training on gender equality to all the university members within the scope of the employee orientation programs	Creation of training and workshops on gender equality; inclusion of gender equality into the employee orientation programs	X			The Directorate of Human Resources, The Directorate of Student Affairs, the Directorate of Operation and Purchasing	Training and workshops Informing all the employees of the gender equality policy and practices	

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Career Development	Business & Life Balance	Ensure that the paternity leaves are efficiently used.	Announcement of the paternity leave policy (MyKhas and website) ensuring that both the academic and administrative staff benefits from this policy Training on paternity to the employees who are to take their paternity leaves	X			The President, The General Secretary, The Directorate of Human Resources	The paternity leave policy made available on MyKhas and KHAS website	

4. Educational Processes and Curriculum

All the faculties and departments will set and announce their targets for the gender equality in compliance with the KHAS Gender Equality Plan detailed hereunder, monitoring the results thereof and, considering them in the respective performance evaluation processes.

A short paragraph, which summarizes the policies against any type of violence and discrimination in all the processes of the university including the courses and activities affiliated therewith, and the rules and sanctions considering thereto, to all the curricula, and this text will highlight the safeguarding of gender equality. In addition, it will be encouraged to include the gender equality aspect in the respective course into the curricula.

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Gender in Education	Culture & Curriculum	Courses on gender across the university	Provision of gender courses to all the students		X		Faculties, The School of Graduate Studies, Core Program	Addition of new courses to the pool of (elective) courses	
Gender in Education	Culture & Curriculum	Gender equality in STEM	Planning and enforcement of activities for STEM		X		Faculties, The School of Graduate Studies, Core Program	Education, workshops and events for STEM	
Gender in Education	Culture & Curriculum	Development of a sensitive language in respect of gender equality	Directives for inclusive communication (Language and visual descriptions)		X		The Gender and Women Studies Research Center, Directorate of Corporate Communications	Development and enforcement of directives for inclusive communication	
Gender in Education	Culture & Curriculum	Ensuring gender equality in education; enhancement of the dialogue and engagement among the male and female students	Informing the academic personnel to enhance gender equality and engagement in the classrooms		X		The Gender and Women Studies Research Center	Informing the academic staff of gender equality and engagement in the classrooms	

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Gender in Education	Culture & Curriculum	Ensuring that the students are efficiently informed of the university's anti-discrimination and gender-based policies	Addition of a chapter focusing on anti-discrimination, gender equality and diversity aspects in all syllabi	X			The Education Committee	Addition of a chapter based on gender equality and diversity in syllabi	

5. Research

It is one of the priorities of our university in the field of research to monitor the gender data in the research deliverables such as research projects and publications, and to develop and put into practice a mentorship system in the respective areas. It is aimed to ensure improvement through a merit-based system in terms of fulfilling the criteria of appointments and promotions by means of enhancing the research competencies and deliverables of all the faculty members and researchers, leading to equality between men and women among the academic staff for all positions.

It is one of the main approaches of our university to safeguard gender equality in all the research processes and all the events, where the research deliverables are shared internally and externally such as conferences and panels in line with our gender equality approach.

	Theme	Subject/Evidence to Discuss	Planned Action	Time Schedule			Responsible Person/Unit/Department	Success Indicators	Link with Sustainable Development Goals
				2022	2023	2024			
Gender in Research	Gender & Research	Gender equality in research processes and deliverables	Monitoring the gender data within the scope of the research processes and deliverables	X	X	X	The Gender and Women Studies Research Center, The Directorate of R&D Resources, The Directorate of Institutional Research and Assessment	Percentages of male and female coordinators and researchers in research projects Percentages of male and female authors of publications and articles	
Gender in Research	Gender & Research	A supporting mechanism aiming for gender equality in research processes	Development of a mentorship system aiming for gender equality in the scope of research projects and publications	X			The Gender and Women Studies Research Center, The Directorate of R&D Resources, The Directorate of Institutional Research and Assessment	The number and percentage of female employees receiving mentorship and, the percentages of male and female researchers by research deliverables	

Disclaimer

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